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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Potential consequences of implementing the EU Landing Obligation on marine ecosystems can be listed in two categories:

Food shortage: Reduction in the discard flow may lead to a food shortage for some scavenger species including birds, benthic and demersal fish and invertebrates.

Altered exploitation: New constraints for fishing fleets are expected to translate into changes in the exploitation (reduced fishing mortality, changes in the spatial and seasonal distribution of effort, improved selectivity ...) having a direct effect on fish stocks.

Both can then lead to longer term effects arising from changes in the relative abundance of different species or group of species. These effects are considered as “**ecosystem effects**” since they arise from the interactions between species and the change in energy flows through the system.

In this work package, using existing or developing modelling tools implemented across the DiscardLess case studies, we had two objectives:

- i) Addressing the question of the long term ecosystem effects of the LO in the most homogeneous way across models and case studies: what are the impacts of reduced discard flows into marine environments and how does it compare with the impact of changes in the exploitation?

Overall, the trophic models used found little effect of a discard ban (landing the fish previously discarded, with no changes in the fishing pressure) on the ecosystem, except for birds. On the other hand, not catching the fish that were previously discarded had a significant effect in our simulations, which confirms that the ecological effects of the Landing Obligation will be through reduced fishing pressure rather than anything else.

- i) Exploring the question of the altered exploitation: how the LO will change the fishing strategies and how will it impacts the fish stocks? and the ecosystem? (for some case studies)

In the Eastern Channel, the 2 models used (Isis Fish and Osmose/DSVM) suggest that the implementation of the LO will benefit fish stocks, although in the case of Osmose/DVSM the biomass increases are buffered by trophic interactions, particularly through cod and whiting predations on other commercial species. Both models also suggest a long term benefit to fleets, following a 10 year long period of decreased revenues.

In the Bay of Biscay, the results of the FLBEIA bioeconomic model (WP2) have been used to drive forecast simulations with EwE, to analyze the status of the Bay of Biscay ecosystem in the short-medium term (from 2013 to 2024). The results illustrate “winners” and “losers” and particularly how seabirds and carnivorous benthic invertebrates are likely to be those suffering from the LO, while hake will increase its overall abundance.

Finally in the North Sea, the StrathE2E model was extended spatially and refined in terms of the description and dynamics of the fishing fleets. The general outcome is similar to what was stated in the previous version, i.e. simply changing discarding practices while fishing as usual, has a negligible conservation benefit at the level of the ecosystem as a whole. On the other hand, tacking the curtailment of discarding by reducing the capture of unwanted fish has the potential to deliver noticeable conservation benefits.

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1 Introduction

Discarding is a common practice in fisheries, especially those targeting mixed demersal species with non-selective gears such as trawls. Fish are discarded for a variety of reasons that include fish caught below marketable size, low value species or catch limits that prevent fish being retained. It is a generally held view that discarding, for whatever reason, is wasteful and not an efficient use of a valuable resource. In an effort to address public concern about discarding the European Union introduced the Landing Obligation (LO) (EU, 2013) which requires fishing vessels to retain and land all species in the catch that are subject to quota management.

Potential consequences of implementing the EU Landing Obligation on marine ecosystems have been described in the deliverable 1.1, they can be listed in two categories:

Food shortage: Reduction in discards may lead to a food shortage for some scavenger species including birds, benthic and demersal fish and invertebrates.

Altered exploitation: New constraints for fishing fleets are expected to translate into changes in the exploitation (reduced fishing mortality, changes in the spatial and seasonal distribution of effort, improved selectivity ...) having a direct effect on fish stocks. In mixed fisheries (i.e. most of our case studies), changes in the fishing strategy of a given fleet affect not only the target or the most limiting stock, but all the stocks fished.

Both can then lead to longer term effects arising from changes in the relative abundance of different species or group of species. These effects are considered as “**ecosystem effects**” since they arise from the interactions between species and the change in energy flows through the system.

The consequences of the LO on marine ecosystems thus involve a variety of interacting processes, ranging from fishermen behaviour to the recycling of detrital organic matter through fishing technology, which are not easy to study all together, although some modelling tools exist which can allow us to carry out at least qualitative explorations.

In this work package, using existing or developing modelling tools implemented across the DiscardLess case studies (Figure 1), we organised our work around two objectives:

- ii) Addressing the question of the long term ecosystem effects of the LO in the most homogeneous way across models and case studies: what are the impacts of reduced discard flows into marine environments and how does it compare with the impact of changes in the exploitation?

All the case studies were covered, but only the models describing trophic interactions and including a discards compartment were used in this section, i.e. EwE, Atlantis and StrathE2E. The changes in the exploitation tested were limited to simple changes in fishing mortality applied group by group (assuming the different groups to be fished independently).

- iii) Exploring the question of the altered exploitation: how the LO will change the fishing strategies and how will it impact the fish stocks? and the ecosystem? (for some case studies)

Only the North Sea, Eastern Channel and Bay of Biscay were covered in this section.

Figure 1: Operational models used in Discardless case studies

2 Modelling the impact of the Landing Obligation on marine foodwebs

2.1 Introduction

Discarding is considered in existing ecosystem models evaluating the effects of various fisheries management measures (Fulton et al. 2014; Kaplan et al. 2014; Libralato et al. 2015; Mackinson et al. 2018), but very few have focused on exploring the effects of varying discard flow on marine food webs (Lauria 2012; Heath et al. 2014; Fondo et al. 2015). Here, we used eight ecosystem models implemented across Europe to illustrate the lessons learnt and challenges still ahead in modelling discard flows in marine food webs.

2.2 Material and methods

Three ecosystem modelling framework have been used: Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE), StrathE2E and Atlantis (Table 1). They differ in their representation of space, time, and processes but all of them aim at modelling the whole food web by using functional groups (representing species sharing similar life history traits).

Table 1: Main features of the three modelling frameworks used.

Model type	Principle	Functional groups	Space	More details
EwE	Mass balanced	Biomass pool (with life stanza possible) Functional groups and singled-out species	No	Heymans et al. (2016)
StrathE2E	Tracks the flows of nitrogen in groups of functionally similar taxa and materials, spanning the entire ecosystem from biogeochemistry to seabirds and marine mammals	Biomass pools (with life stanza possible)	Vertical layers	Heath (2012)
Atlantis		Age structured population (abundance) and growth (average individual weight) dynamic for vertebrates and biomass pools for invertebrates Functional groups and singled-out species	Irregular horizontal polygons and regular vertical layers	Fulton (2010)

Eight models were considered in this study. They are generally implemented at the scale of fisheries management regions (Figure 2). The food web description in each region is specific to its general ecology, fisheries and conservation stakes (see Table 2 and section **Error! Reference source not found.**); however, in the outputs presented here, biomasses of functional groups were pooled in aggregated categories for the purpose of comparison. Discard flows are specific to each model and have been parametrised using data from fisheries monitoring programs (section **Error! Reference source not found.**).

All models and their case studies applications were already under development at the beginning of the DiscardLess project, and most of the work in the project was dedicated to update and adapt them for the specific frame and scenarios as described below. A notable exception was however the specific needs for model development for the EwE model. Although widely used in many ecosystem analyses worldwide, the EwE was initially not well suited for the analyses of discarding scenarios, as the temporary dynamic model did not distinguish between landings and discards in the parameters linked to fishing mortality. Some changes in the core model algorithm were thus required. A collaboration took place between the EwE users of both DiscardLess and MINOUW (GA no 634495) and the EwE development team (Ecopath International Initiative) to identify the needs. These were listed and prioritized in 2016 during the first reporting period of DiscardLess (See Appendix 4.3) and implemented in 2017 during the second period. The development costs were shared between the two H2020 projects.

We evaluated five scenarios using the design in Table 2 (see also Figure 3):

1. “Discard as Usual”: fishing mortalities and discard rates are fixed per group and constant throughout the simulation, the discard survival rates are all assumed to be null;
2. “No Discards”: total fishing mortalities per group remain the same, but the discard rates are all set to 0, leading to no discards being released in the system², which allows to test the ‘pure’ effect of the discard flow into the marine food web.
3. “Landing Obligation”: Only the quota species, or the species with a MCRS in the Mediterranean Sea are all landed. The other species are discarded in the same way as in the Discard as Usual Scenario
4. “No Discards and Selectivity”: The fraction of the catch that was previously discarded is not caught anymore, for all groups
5. “LO and Selectivity”: The fraction of the catch that was previously discarded is not caught anymore, for the quota/MCRS species. The other species are discarded in the same way as in the Discard as Usual Scenario

These scenarios represent extreme cases to bracket the range of possible realities. The 2nd and 3rd ones allow us to isolate the ecosystem response to the flow of discards. The 4th and 5th ones allow us to test a theoretical drastic improvement in selectivity.

² In the case of the North Sea StrathE2E model however, a residual discard flow remains for the benthos, corresponding to 4% of the baseline discard flow (Heath et al. 2014).

Figure 2: Geographic implementation of the 8 models used: 6 EwE models (in green) in the Azores EEZ, the Bay of Biscay (ICES areas VIIIa and b), the Celtic Sea (ICES areas VIIe,h,f,g and j), the Balearic islands (GFCM GSA 5) and the Thermaikos gulf (part of GFCM GSA 22); the Eastern English Channel Atlantis model (ICES area VIId, in purple), and the North Sea StrathE2E model (ICES areas IV c, b and most of a, in orange).

Figure 3: Graphical representation of the F scenarios run by all the EwE, StrathE2E, and Atlantis models. The baseline and 4 scenarios correspond each to a bar, which height indicates the fishing mortality level. Yellow and red rectangles indicate the landing F_s (respectively quota species and other species landings F), and light blue and navy blue indicate the discards F (respectively quota species and other species).

The representation of fishing pressure varies across the models: the North Sea and the Atlantis model are forced directly with constant harvest rates (proportion of a given group being caught) and discard rates per group. The EwE models can be forced with harvest rates as well (time series in the hindcast and constant values for projections), or with fishing efforts per fleet (and capturability per functional group).

The North Sea StrathE2E model cannot be used to run LO distinct scenarios, due to highly aggregated fish groups (i.e. demersal and pelagic).

Table 2: Main features of the 8 ecosystem models used.

Area	Models	F forcing	Historical run	Projections	Outputs	Relevant section
Azores	EwE	Time series of fishing effort (E) per fleet and constant discard ratios	Ecosim fitted on 1997-2013	Run for 17 years (from 2013 to 2030) using an average E over the last 3 years of the historical run	Average of the last 3 years	2.6.4
Bay of Biscay1	EwE	Time series of harvest rates (F) and constant discard ratios	Ecosim fitted on 1980-2013	Run for 17 years (from 2013 to 2030) using an average F over the last 3 years of the historical run	Average of the last 3 years	2.6.3.22.6.2
Bay of Biscay2	EwE	Time series of fishing effort (E) per fleet and constant discard ratios	Ecosim fitted on 1996-2013	?	?	2.6.3.3
Celtic Sea	EwE	Time series of fishing effort (E) per fleet and constant discard ratios	Ecosim fitted on 1980-2013	Run for 17 years (from 2013 to 2030) using an average E over the last 3 years of the historical run	Average of the last 3 years	2.6.2
North Sea	StrathE2E	Constant harvest rate (F)	Model calibrated on averaged biomass/catch/effort over 1970-1999	Historical run = baseline "No discard" scenario based on the historical run (no projection)	Annual average once stationary annual cycle reached	Heath et al, 2014
Eastern English Channel (spatialised into 32 polygons)	Atlantis	Constant harvest rates (F) and discard ratios per functional group	Model calibrated on averaged biomass/catch/effort over 2002-2011	All scenario based on the historical run (no projection)	Annual average once stationary annual cycle reached	2.6.1
Balearic islands	EwE	Constant fishing mortalities and discard ratios	Ecosim fitted on 2004-2017	Run for 18 years (from 2017 to 2035) using an average F over the last 3 years of the historical run	Average of the last 3 years	2.6.5
Thermaikos Gulf	EwE	Constant fishing effort (E) per fleet and discard ratios	Ecosim fitted on 2001-2015	Run for 18 years (from 2015 to 2025) using an average E over the last 3 years of the historical run		2.6.6

2.3 Results

Stopping the inflow of discards into the ecosystem had a very low effect on the evaluated ecosystems (Figure 4), with the exception of seabirds, and mammals in the case of the Balearic Sea, i.e. the main surface discards consumers.

The decrease of turtles biomass is not fully understood at this stage.

The effect of removing the discards was small but noticeable on direct consumers of discards in the benthic area (i.e. benthic carnivores and scavengers, demersal fish). A small effect of a reduction in the recycling of detritus was also seen with the atlantis model (light reduction in the bacteria, phytoplankton and zooplankton biomasses). Finally, the decrease abundance of seabirds caused the pelagic fish biomass to increase slightly in the Celtic Sea. There are virtually no effect (<1.2%) on the Azores ecosystem, where the discard flow was the smallest.

Reducing the flow of discards into the ecosystem through the landing obligation scenario (where the discard flow is only reduced) logically produced intermediate results with smaller effects on the seabirds, mammals and turtles compartments (Figure 4).

The changes in the ecosystem were generally more important in the selectivity scenarios than in the first two ones (Figure 6 and Figure 7).

These changes are mainly positive for the North Sea and Eastern Channel case studies, with significant increase in the biomasses of demersal fish, mammals and birds. Pelagic fish are heavily discarded in the Eastern Channel, and the corresponding decrease in fishing mortality in the “no discard + selectivity” scenario compensates the increased pressure from mammals driving the decrease in biomass observed in the North Sea model.

In the Bay of Biscay and in the Celtic Sea, the reduced fishing pressure on heavily discarded predators modified the balance of the foodweb, with subsequent decreased biomasses of pelagic fish and their other predators (birds and mammals). On the contrary pelagic invertebrates benefitted from reduced predation pressure from pelagics.

Figure 4: % changes in the biomass of aggregated categories between the “No Discards” scenario and the “Discard as usual” baseline. Aggregated categories: ZOO: zooplankton, TUR: turtles, PEL_INV: pelagic invertebrates, CAR_SCAV: carnivorous and scavenging benthos, SUSP_DEP: suspension and deposit feeding benthos, DEM: demersal and benthopelagic fish, PEL: pelagic fish, MAM: mammals.

Figure 5: % changes in the biomass of aggregated categories between the "Landing Obligation" scenario and the "Discard as usual" baseline. Aggregated categories: ZOO: zooplankton, PEL_INV: pelagic invertebrates, CAR_SCAV: carnivorous and scavenging benthos, SUSP_DEP: suspension and deposit feeding benthos, DEM: demersal and benthopelagic fish, PEL: pelagic fish, MAM: mammals.

Figure 6: % changes in the biomass of aggregated categories between the “No Discards and selectivity” scenario and the “Discard as usual” baseline. Aggregated categories: ZOO: zooplankton, PEL_INV: pelagic invertebrates, CAR_SCAV: carnivorous and scavenging benthos, SUSP_DEP: suspension and deposit feeding benthos, DEM: demersal and benthopelagic fish, PEL: pelagic fish, MAM: mammals.

Figure 7: % changes in the biomass of aggregated categories between the “Landing Obligation and selectivity” scenario and the “Discard as usual” baseline. Aggregated categories: ZOO: zooplankton, PEL_INV: pelagic invertebrates, CAR_SCAV: carnivorous and scavenging benthos, SUSP_DEP: suspension and deposit feeding benthos, DEM: demersal and benthopelagic fish, PEL: pelagic fish, MAM: mammals.

2.4 Discussion

Discard flows may seem large when considered as absolute values, and with regards to the waste of natural resources it represents. When considered as a potential food source however, discard flows appear to be low relative to the living biomass in the ecosystem, and when compared with other sources of food (natural carrion).

Overall, the models found little effect of a discard ban (with no changes in the fishing pressure) on the ecosystem (except for birds). These results are in agreement with other modelling studies. Sánchez and Olaso (2004) confirmed the low importance of discards as a food source in the Cantabrian Sea in comparison to detritus, primary producers or other low trophic levels (0.07% of the total food intake, EwE model). Kaiser and Hiddink (2007) and Collie et al. (2017) estimated that fisheries-generated carrion could only sustain benthic carnivores for three days per year at the scale of the North Sea and scavenging fish for approximately 6 days per year. Depestele et al (2016) similarly estimated that discards in the Grande Vasière (northern Bay of Biscay) contributed to less than 2% of the scavenging benthic community total food requirements. Our findings are also consistent with the spatial analysis carried out by the Working Group on Ecosystem Effects of Fishing Activities (WGECO) of the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) who found no relationship between discarded biomass and scavenger abundance in the North Sea (ICES 2016; ICES 2017). Other modelling studies, in contrast, found an influential effect of discards on benthic scavengers (Catchpole et al. 2006; Fondo et al. 2015) but at a smaller spatial scale (respectively Moreton Bay, and the North Sea Nephrops English fishing grounds).

Ecosystem modelling can help extrapolating the available data and empirical knowledge (to a certain extent) on the fate of discards in the environment at the regional scale, and in testing a full discard ban scenario. However, important assumptions should be recalled. First, the discards are all pooled into one group in the models, while observational studies showed that the consumption of discards differs between the provided types of discards and dietary preferences of the scavengers. Second, the benthic and demersal scavengers tend to be aggregated into coarse functional groups in ecosystem models. The aggregation of benthic and demersal scavengers does not allow to fully accounting for the varying degree of importance of discards for specific taxa (e.g. Kaiser and Hiddink 2007). Further splitting the scavenger groups would help, but only if sufficient data are available for parametrization, which is unlikely at the scale of the presented models.

A major source of uncertainty in the modelling work is due to the quality of the discards data. The limited fleet coverage of discard monitoring programs hampers the possibility of discard estimations at a small spatial scale. Furthermore, current discards monitoring programs focus primarily on commercial species and have been designed to estimate discard rates per fleet and stock rather than to estimate a discard flow to the environment. Reliable quantitative information on the ratio of commercial versus non-commercial discards is relatively sparse (Uhlmann et al. 2013; Depestele 2015), but existing data could be used to speculate on the orders of magnitude changes that non-commercial discards may cause in the energy flow in the ecosystem. Here again, sensitivity analyses will be necessary to complete the present work.

Not catching the fish that were previously caught and discarded had a significant effect in our simulation, which confirms that the ecological effects of the Landing Obligation will be through reduced fishing pressure rather than through anything else.

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	Raja clavata Phycis phycis Pagrus pagrus Beryx splendens Beryx decadactylus Pagellus bogaraveo Lepidopus caudatus Rays and other sharks DW sharks	Rays&Skates			Plaice Demersal L Demersal M Demersal S		Gurnards Mulletts other gadoids Small demersals	
DET	Detritus	Detritus	Detritus	Detritus		Detritus	labile detritus refractory detritus	surface layer detritus deep layer detritus sediment detritus
DIS	Discards		Discards	Discards		Discards	Discards	fishery discards in the water column corpses on the seabed
MAM	Dolphins Baleen whales Toothed whales	Dolphins	Striped dolphins Bottlenose dolphins Common dolphins Long-finned pilot whales Harbour porpoises	Baleen_whales Toothed_whales	Baleen whales Toothed whales	Dolphins	Toothed whales Seals	
PEL	Pelagic S Pelagic M Pelagic L Mesopelagics Bathypelagic Mora moro Pelagic sharks	Pelagic sharks Large pelagics Medium pelagics Dolphinfish Transparent gobies Mesopelagic fish Horse mackerel	Blue whiting Mackerel Horse mackerel Anchovy Sardine	Sharks_L Blue_whiting Horse_mackerel Mackerel Anchovy Sardine Pouts	Sharks L Blue whiting Horse Mackerel Mackerel Sprat Herring Sardine	Picarels and bogue Anchovy Sardine Horse mackerels Mackerels Other small pelagics Medium pelagics	Mackerels Clupeids	pelagic fish adults

	Tunas	Sardine&Anchovy		Pelagic_L Pelagic_M	Pouts Pelagic L Pelagic M	Large pelagics		
PEL_INV	Cephalopods	Cuttlefish Squids	Pelagic cephalopods	Cephalopods	Cephalopods	Squids	Cephalopods	
PP	Phytoplankton	Phytoplankton	Large phytoplankton	Phytoplankton_L	Phytoplankton L	Phytoplankton	Phytoplankton	surface layer phytoplankton
			Small phytoplankton	Phytoplankton_S	Phytoplankton_S		deep layer phytoplankton	
SB	Seabirds	Sea Birds	Pursuit divers seabirds	Plunge_and_pursuit_ divers_seabirds	Plunge and pursuit divers seabirds	Seabirds	Seabirds	birds mammals
			Surface feeders seabirds	Surface_feeders_seabirds	Surface feeders seabirds			
SUSP_DEP	Shrimp	Bivalves&Gastropodes	Sub-surface deposit feeders invertebrates	Shrimps	Shrimps	Benthic small crustaceans	Shrimps	suspension deposit feeding benthos
			Surface suspension and deposit feeders inv	Subsurface_deposit_f eeders_inver.	Sub-surface deposit feeders invertebrates	Shrimps	suspension feeders	
			Benthic meiofauna	Surface_susp_and_de p_feeders	Surface suspension and deposit feeders	Benthic invertebrates	deposit feeders	
			Suprabenthic invertebrates	Benthic_meiofauna Suprabenthic_invertebrates	Benthic meiofauna Suprabenthic invertebrates	Scallops Bivalves		
TUR	Turtles	Turtle				Loggerhead turtle		
ZOO	Small Zooplankton	Gelatinous plankton	Macrozooplankton	Macrozooplankton	Macrozooplankton	Zooplankton	Zooplankton	omnivorous zooplankton
			Mesozooplankton	Mesozooplankton	Mesozooplankton	Carnivorous zoopk	carnivorous zooplankton	
			Micro-mesozooplankton	Microzooplankton	Microzooplankton	Gelatinous zoop	pelagic fish larvae demersal fish larvae	

2.6 Ecosystem models used

2.6.1 Eastern Channel

2.6.1.1 Introduction

The Eastern Channel (EC) is a shallow epicontinental sea (maximum depth 100 m) covering a total area of approximately 35,000 km² (Figure 8). It corresponds to the ICES division VIIId. France (46% of the total landings for 2006-2013³), Netherlands (22%), the UK (16%), and Belgium (8%) operate pelagic trawl (targeting herring, mackerel and horse mackerel), beam-trawls (targeting sole and plaice), otter trawl (targeting a mixed assemblage of quota and non-quota demersal species) and Danish seines (targeting mainly demersal non-quota species) fisheries. The mixed nature of these fisheries leads to high discards ratios, especially in the mixed demersal trawl fishery.

The Atlantis modelling framework was implemented in Eastern English Channel to study its ecosystem dynamics and explore the impact of spatial fisheries management measures (Girardin et al, 2018). This model was then slightly modified and used in the context of DiscardLess to explore a series of discarding scenarios.

2.6.1.2 Model and data

Atlantis is a modular modelling framework, deterministic and spatially resolved (irregular spatial polygons allowing to match the ecosystem spatial features). Processes are implemented via differential equations, using a time step of 24 hours. The ecosystem module tracks the nitrogen flows through a trophic network consisting of functional groups and single species groups.

The Eastern Channel Atlantis model covers the whole ICES division VIIId. The model grid uses 35 polygons with three water column depth layers on the vertical axis, and a single sediment layer (Figure 8). 40 functional groups were defined on the basis of their habitat, preys and predators, growth characteristics (mainly maximum size and longevity) and migration patterns (

³ Official Nominal Catches 2006-2013. Accessed 28-04-2015 via <http://ices.dk/marine-data/dataset-collections/Pages/Fish-catch-and-stock-assessment.aspx> ICES, Copenhagen.

Table 3). Vertebrates alone accounted for 21 of those groups, including a seabird and two mammal groups, seven groups of fish species of commercial interest and eleven other functional groups. 16 groups of invertebrates were also included, among which four planktonic groups and seven groups of commercial interest. Finally, detritus were binned into three separate groups as required by Atlantis.

Figure 8: Spatial structure of the Atlantis application in the Eastern English Channel. The number of layers are shown with different colours, yellow for one layer (<15m), green for two (<30m) and blue for three (<60m). Red dots represent the position of river estuaries. The river names are indicated for reference.

In this version of the model, fisheries are represented through a synthetic fishing mortality (F) per group/species.

Discard rates were estimated using the French national discard program Obsmer data (Cornou et al, 2017) available for the calibration period (2002-2017): (1) Discards data per species were aggregated per gear type and year, and raised by trips. (2) These estimated discard volumes, as well as French landings, were then summed per Atlantis group and used to calculate discard rates. (3) These discard rates were assumed to be applicable to the total landings (from all countries), which of course is a more or less reasonable assumption depending on how uniform is the distribution of the landings across gear types for the different countries, or the differences in the availability of quota or value for a given species across countries.

F were then calibrated to reproduce the average total catch per species over the calibration period, i.e. 2002-2011 (Official landings as communicated to ICES, aggregated per Atlantis groups, and scaled up using the discard rates previously estimated).

The model was run for 200 years to allow it to stabilise over a steady annual cycle, and to produce stable age structure populations.

Table 4: Description of functional groups species composition in Atlantis Eastern English Channel application. Harvested groups are in bold, quota species/groups are underlined.

Code	Group	Species
SB	Seabirds	Fulmar (<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>), Manx shearwater (<i>Puffinus puffinus</i>), Storm petrel (<i>Hydrobates pelagicus</i>), Gannet (<i>Sula bassana</i>), Cormorant (<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>), Gulls (<i>Larus melanocephalus</i> , <i>Larus ridibundus</i> , <i>Larus canus</i> , <i>Larus fuscus</i> , <i>Larus argentatus</i> , <i>Larus marinus</i>), Kittiwake (<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>), Terns (<i>Sterna sandvicensis</i> , <i>Sterna dougalli</i> , <i>Sterna hirundo</i> , <i>Sterna paradisaea</i> , and <i>Sterna albifrons</i>), Guillemot (<i>Uria aalge</i>), Razor bill (<i>Alca torda</i>), Puffin (<i>Fratercula arctica</i>)
CET	Toothed cetaceans	Harbour porpoise (<i>Phocoena phocoena</i>), Common dolphin (<i>Delphinus delphis</i>), Longfinned pilot whale (<i>Globicephala melas</i>)
SXX	Seals	Grey seals (<i>Halichoerus grypus</i>), Harbour seals (<i>Phoca vitulina</i>)
COD	Cod	North Atlantic cod (<i>Gadus morhua</i>)
RAY	Rays and Dogfishes	Cuckoo ray (<i>Raja naevus</i>), Common stingray (<i>Dasyatis pastinacus</i>), Spurdog (<i>Squalus acanthias</i>), Lesserspotted dogfish (<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>), Smalleyed ray (<i>Raja microcellata</i>), Greater-spotted dogfish (<i>Scyliorhinus stellaris</i>), Blonde ray (<i>Raja brachyura</i>), Longnosed skate (<i>Dipturus oxyrinchus</i>), Blue skate (<i>Dipturus batis</i>), Spotted ray (<i>Raja montagui</i>), Thornback ray (<i>Raja clavata</i>)
SHK	Sharks	Tope (<i>Galeorhinus galeus</i>), Porbeagle (<i>Lamna nasus</i>), Blue shark (<i>Prionace glauca</i>), Starry smooth-hound (<i>Mustelus asterias</i>), Smooth-hound (<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>), Thintail thresher (<i>Alopias vulpinus</i>)
CEP	Cephalopods	Veined squid (<i>Loligo forbesii</i>), European squid (<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>), Common cuttlefish (<i>Sepia officinalis</i>)
WHG	Whiting	Whiting (<i>Merlangius merlangius</i>)
POL	Pollack	Atlantis pollock (<i>Pollachius pollachius</i>)
LBT	Large bottom fishes	Hake (<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>), Anglerfish (<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>), Ling (<i>Molva molva</i>), Conger eel (<i>Conger conger</i>)
BSS	Seabass	European seabass (<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>)
SOL	Sole	Common sole (<i>Solea solea</i>)
PLE	Plaice	European plaice (<i>Pleuronectes platessa</i>)
DAB	Dab	Common dab (<i>Limanda limanda</i>)
OFF	Other flatfishes	Lemon sole (<i>Microstomus kitt</i>), Megrim (<i>Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis</i>), Topknot (<i>Zeugopterus punctatus</i>), Turbot (<i>Psetta maxima</i>), Brill (<i>Scophthalmus rhombus</i>), European flounder (<i>Platichthys flesus</i>), Sand sole (<i>Pegusa lascaris</i>), Thickback sole (<i>Microchirus variegatus</i>), Solenette (<i>Buglossidium luteum</i>), Scaldfish (<i>Arnoglossus sp.</i>)
MAC	Mackerels	North-east Atlantic mackerel (<i>Scomber scombrus</i>), Horse mackerel (<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>)
CLU	Clupeidae	Atlantic herring (<i>Clupea harengus</i>), European sprat (<i>Sprattus sprattus</i>), European pilchard (<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>)
SPA	Sparidae	Blackspot seabream (<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>), Common pandora (<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>), Gilthead seabream (<i>Sparus auratus</i>), Black bream (<i>Spondyliosoma cantharus</i>)
GUX	Gurnards	Red gurnard (<i>Chelidonichthys cuculus</i>), Tub gurnard (<i>Chelidonichthys lucerna</i>), Grey gurnard (<i>Chelidonichthys gurnardus</i>)
MUL	Mugilidae	Thinlip mullet (<i>Liza ramada</i>), Golden grey mullet (<i>Liza aurata</i>), Thicklip grey mullet (<i>Chelon labrosus</i>), Striped red mullet (<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>)
GAD	Other Gadoids	Pouting (<i>Trisopterus luscus</i>), Poor cod (<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>)
SMD	Small demersal fishes	Sand goby (<i>Pomatoschistus minutus</i>), Hooknose (<i>Agonus cataphractus</i>), Dragonet (<i>Callionymus maculatus</i>), Rokling fish, Greater weever (<i>Trachinus draco</i>), Lesser weever (<i>Enchiichthys vipera</i>), Blenniidae, Sandeel (<i>Ammodytes tobianus</i> , <i>Ammodytes marinus</i>)
LBE	Lobsters	European lobster (<i>Homarus gammarus</i>), Spiny lobster (<i>Palinurus elephas</i>)
CRA	Crabs	Shore crab (<i>Carcinus maenas</i>), Common hermit crab (<i>Pagurus bernhardus</i>), Hairy crab (<i>Pilumnus hirtellus</i>), Velvet swimming crab (<i>Necora puber</i>), Edible crab (<i>Cancer pagurus</i>), Spider crab (<i>Maja squinado</i>)
SHP	Shrimps	Common prawn (<i>Palaemon serratus</i>), Brown shrimp (<i>Crangon crangon</i>), Norway lobster (<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i>)

WHE	Whelks	Common whelk (<i>Buccinum undatum</i>)
SUS	Suspension feeders	Benthic cnidarians, Sponges, Bryozoans, Ascidians
DEP	Deposit feeders	Polychaeta, Amphipods, Nematodes, Gastropods, Isopods
SCE	Scallops	Common scallops (<i>Pecten maximus</i>), Queen scallops (<i>Chlamys opercularis</i>)
BIV	Bivalves	Cockles (<i>Cerastoderma edule</i>), Softshelled clam (<i>Mya arenaria</i>), Blue mussels (<i>Mytilus edulis</i>), Oysters (<i>Ostrea eduli</i> , <i>Crassostrea gigas</i>)
ECH	Echinoderms	<i>Asterias rubens</i> , <i>Astropecten irregularis</i> , <i>Spatangus purpureus</i> , <i>Psammechinus miliaris</i> , <i>Echinus esculentus</i> , <i>Solaster endeca</i> , <i>Ophiura ophiura</i> , <i>Crossaster papposus</i> , <i>Echinocarsium cordatum</i> , <i>Ophiothrix fragilis</i>
ZOO	Zooplankton	
ZOC	Carnivorous zooplankton	
ZOG	Gelatinous zooplankton	
PP	Phytoplankton	
BB	Benthic bacteria	
PB	Pelagic bacteria	
DL	Labile Detrital	
DR	Refractory Detrital	
DIS	Discards	

2.6.1.3 Results

2.6.1.3.1 Baseline run

The historical run aims at reproducing the average conditions over the period 2002-2011. The Figure 9, Figure 10, and Figure 11 illustrate how the results of the model compare with the knowledge available on the ecosystem.

Figure 9: Comparison of Atlantis biomasses averaged over the last 30 years of the simulation (red dots) and biomasses assessed (blue bars: ICES assessed minimum to maximum biomass over 2002 to 2011) or estimated from the CGFS survey (orange bars: minimum to maximum biomass estimated over 2002 to 2011). Please refer to Table 4 for the group codes.

Figure 10: Comparison of Atlantis catches averaged over the last 30 years of the simulation and the historical catch averaged over the period 2002-2011 (landings plus estimated discards, 2.6.1.2).

Figure 11: Comparison of Atlantis vertebrate lengths at age averaged over the last 30 years and initial lengths at age estimated with Von Bertalanffy age-length relationships.

2.6.1.3.2 Scenarios

Five scenarios were then run for another 100 years (see p. 9). Decreasing (the Landing Obligation scenario) or stopping (the No Discard scenario) the discards flow into the environment has very little effect on the Eastern English Channel as modelled here (Figure 12). Logically the abundance of discards in the system decreases drastically, which causes the detritus, as well as the bacteria, phytoplankton and zooplankton to decrease a little bit. Apart from those groups, no changes beyond 1% of the baseline biomass occurs, apart from the whelk group (+1.6% in the No Discard scenario), which seems to be due to a slightly lighter predation pressure.

On the other hand, increasing the selectivity, so that the previously discarded portion of the catch is not fished anymore, causes major changes to happen in the system. A great majority of the harvested groups benefits from the reduced fishing mortality, and particularly the groups which were heavily discarded such as plaice, dab, clupeids and mackerels. These benefits extend to vertebrates and seabirds through increased food resources. Benthic invertebrates show reduced changes comparatively, some of them benefiting from the reduced fishing mortality like scallops or crabs (No Discards scenario), but other groups have reduced abundance due to higher predation pressure (e.g. shrimps). This is also the case for the heavily predated small demersal fish groups. Please note that the discards rate used in this work are limited to fish and commercial invertebrates and therefore underestimate the effect of the LO on non commercial invertebrates.

Figure 12: Changes in the biomasses simulated for the scenarios "No Discards" and "Landing Obligation" relative to the "Discard as Usual" run.

Figure 13: Changes in the biomasses simulated for the scenarios "No Discards+ Selectivity" and "Landing Obligation + Selectivity" relative to the "Discard as Usual" run.

2.6.1.4 References

Cornou, A.-S., Goascoz, N., Quinio-Scavinner, M., Chassanite, A., Dubroca, L., Rochet, M.- J., 2017. Captures et rejets des métiers de pêche français. Résultats des observations à bord des navires de pêche professionnelle en 2016.

Girardin R, Fulton EA, Lehuta S, Rolland M, Thébaud O, Travers M, Vermard Y, Marchal P, 2018. Identification of the main processes underlying ecosystem functioning in the Eastern English Channel, with a focus on flatfish species, as revealed through the application of the Atlantis end-to-end model. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 201: 208-222.

2.6.2 EwE in the Celtic Sea

The Ecopath model previously developed in the Celtic sea (Moullec et al. 2017) was modified in order to allow for simulation of the landing obligation. In particular, the share between landing and discard was specified for every fleet.

2.6.2.1 Ecopath outputs; the detritus flows in the ecosystem

The model shed light on the major flows related to discards. In term of production, discards are issued mainly from demersal fish, and from the shark/rays and lobsters/crabs groups. In term of consumption, discards constitute a major part of the diet of seabirds (until 20% for the surface feeder seabirds), while the main flows in term of consumption also involve scavengers such as crabs and necrophage invertebrates. The model shows that more than 73% of the discards produced annually are consumed (0.137 ton/year⁻¹.km⁻² consumed, for 0.188 produced). But the total flow of discard is very limited, accounting for less than 0.01 % of the total ecosystem production, and less that 0.02 % of the flow to detritus. Therefore, even if almost fully consumed this flow may have only a very limited impact on the global ecosystem functioning.

Figure 14: Main flows to and from discards in the Celtic sea

2.6.2.2 Ecosim: simulations of changes in discards management

Using Ecosim fitted on the 1980-2013 period (on catch and abundance time series), 5 simulations were performed over the 2014-2030 period: the baseline Scenario 1 assuming no change in discarding practices; Scenario 2: landing obligation where all previous discards for stocks under TAC regulation are still caught and now landed; Scenario 3: landing obligation where all previous discards for all stocks are still caught and now landed; Scenario 4: landing obligation and selectivity where all previous discards for TAC stocks are avoided (thus unfished); Scenario 5: landing obligation and selectivity where all previous discards for all stocks are avoided. Results are expressed in term of mean relative values to the baseline scenario, for the last years of the simulation (2028-2030) (Figure 14)

Figure 15: Impact of the simulated scenarios on the biomass per trophic group, relatively to the baseline scenario (left: scenarios 2 and 3, right: scenarios 4 and 5).

Logically, the landing obligation mainly affects the groups whose diet significantly includes discards. Thus, the biomass of plunge and surface feeders seabirds are reduced by 2 and 26 % respectively in case where the landing obligation apply to TAC species and did not reduce the fishing mortality (i.e. Scenario 2, where former discards are landed). Reductions expand to 11 and 67 % respectively if all discards, including those of non-TAC regulated species, would be landed (Scenario 3).

Impacts of scenarios 4 and 5 are much stronger, suggesting that improving selectivity is the key challenge of the landing obligation. In these scenarios, the fishing mortalities are significantly reduced for highly discarded species, leading to an increase in the related stock biomass. This effect is especially marked for high trophic levels such as the sharks/ray group (with a doubling of the biomass), and for hake or haddock. Changes in

predators biomass result in cascading complex effects on lower trophic levels, which in some case counterbalance the positive impacts of reducing the fishing mortalities (for instance for whiting and megrim, whose biomass is lightly decreasing). Some groups such as cephalopods would benefit from a release of predation linked to the decrease in abundance of large pelagics, pouts or mackerel.

2.6.2.3 Biomass spectra: ecosystem effects of the landing obligation

Biomass spectra show that changes induced by the landing obligation on the ecosystem biomass would be very limited (less than 0.1 % in total, and less than 2 % for every trophic classes) in case the former discards would still be caught but landed. The impact would be much higher in case of a perfect selectivity allowing to avoid the catch of all former discards. In such case the total ecosystem biomass (for animals, i.e. TL >=2) would decrease by 6% because of more abundant predators. The trophic spectra seems to suggest that changes in abundance could reach about 45% for some trophic classes, around trophic level 2.7. But this decrease is mainly due to macro-zooplankton and is likely to be an artefact of the model.

Figure 16: Trophic spectra of the relative biomass and catch for the various scenarios

In term of catch, the landing obligation has almost no effect, with a less than 0.3 % on total landings. Improving selectivity, without increasing the mortalities related to the landings (and with a mortality for discards set to zero) would result in a 6% decrease in the total catch, mainly due to losses on intermediate trophic levels (around 3.6, corresponding to small pelagics). Nevertheless, it can be noticed that in such a situation of improved selectivity and increased biomass, a MSY management strategy would logically lead to accept higher fishing mortalities; leading to higher catches.

2.6.3 EwE in the Bay of Biscay

2.6.3.1 Introduction

In the Bay of Biscay, two Ecopath and Ecosim models (Moulllet et al., 2017; Andonegi and Prellezo, 2016, here denoted BoB1 and BoB2 respectively) have been considered and further developed during the Discardless project. These two models were initially built in an independent way, in the frame of two different projects, thus allowing for an inter-model comparison. BoB1 aimed to provide scientific advice on stock management in the context of ecosystems. Thus, its structure was defined in order to adjust to stocks identities and data available from ICES assessment. BoB2 was anyway more focussed on the Spanish fleets impacts on the ecosystem, and how different management measures affecting these fleets and in particular the landing obligation, could affect the status of that ecosystem. The configuration of the food web has been designed on a stock basis, and to adjust the available information at AZTI's data centre and ICES stock assessments. The first model also describes the long-term dynamics of this ecosystem since the 80's, while the second one is representing the dynamics of the Spanish métiers dealing with a shorter representation of the dynamics of the ecosystem (only since 1996), mainly due to the data availability.

Bay of Biscay (Figure 17) is a highly productive system. It creates the perfect conditions to multispecies trawling fleets to make use of this productivity. The two models used are centred on the French Continental shelf of the Bay of Biscay (ICES Subdivisions VIII a and b), where both Spanish and French vessels are operating. In particular, there is a trawl fleet based in the ports of Ondarroa (Basque Country, Spain) which was expected to be highly impacted by the Landing Obligation. This fleet is a multispecies fishery targeting more than 48 different species and landing and selling always back in Ondarroa. It is the major fleet of interest considered in the BoB2 model.

Figure 17: The Bay of Biscay. The study area is contained inside the blue square.

The operation of this fleet can be divided into métiers. These métiers are based on the target assemblage landed by trip, as stipulated in the Commission Decision 2008/949/EC⁴ Appendix IV footnote (b). However, this Commission decision only considered general and non-specific assemblage of species (crustaceans, cephalopods, demersal fish ...), which are not detailed enough to define the different fishing tactics followed by this fleet. Based on direct interviews with skippers, three different “group of target species” were identified; the percentage of each group within the landing is later used to allocate trips into define métiers.

A first métier, pair trawlers (PTB hereafter), use a very high vertical opening bottom trawl to target hake (*Merluccius merluccius*). The activity is constant along the year, with a slight effort reduction during summer period. Total landings reach 2293 tons in 2013, and hake landings (the main target species) 1682 tones.

A second métier, bottom otter trawlers targeting demersal species (OTD hereafter), has a constant activity along the year, with slight effort reduction during summer period. Total landings reach 2836 tons in 2013. Hake, anglerfishes (*Lophius piscatorius* and *Lophius budegassa*) and megrims (*Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis*) are the main landed species, but there are more than 65 other landed species (pouts, dogfish, triglids...).

The third métier, bottom otter trawlers targeting mixed species (OTM hereafter), concentrates its activity during winter seasons. Total landings reached 655 tons in 2013. Squids, cuttlefish, and mullets are the main target species in this métier.

PTB is mainly landing hake. Total discards are around 15 % of the total catch. Hake individuals under minimum conservation reference size (MCRS hereafter) and pelagic species (horse mackerel, and mackerel) are the main component of the discarded catch fraction. There are both market and regulation reasons for discarding within this métier. Hake (MLS) and mackerel (quota exhaustion) are discarded due to legal reasons. Market reasons lie behind horse mackerel discards.

OTD mainly lands hake, anglerfish and megrim, but there are more than 65 other landed species (pouts, dogfish, triglids...). Total discards are around 60-65 % of the total catch. Hake individuals under MCRS and pelagic species such as horse mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*) and mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*) are the main component of the discarded catch fraction.

OTM mainly lands squids, cuttlefish, and mullets are the main target species in this métier. However, this is a very mixed métier including many other species (pout, seabass, hake...), most of them not subject to any total allowable catch (TAC) or MCRS.

⁴ COMMISSION DECISION of 6 November 2008 adopting a multiannual Community programme pursuant to Council Regulation (EC) No 199/2008 establishing a Community framework for the collection, management and use of data in the fisheries sector and support for scientific advice regarding the common fisheries policy

2.6.3.2 BoB1 - EwE 1980-2030

The Ecopath model (Bentorcha et al., 2017; Moullec et al. 2017) was modified in order to allow for these simulation of the landing obligation. As a first step, the share between landing and discard was specified for every fleet, thus providing an overview of the major flux of discards, in term of production and consumption (Figure 19).

Figure 18: Flow diagram of the Bay of Biscay Ecopath model

Production of discards is mainly issued from hake and nephrops, while consumption is mainly due to seabirds, necrophagic benthic invertebrates and lobsters. The total flow to discards is estimated equal to 0.164 t/year/km².

Figure 19: Parameter for each Ecopath group; landing and discards, discards production and consumption, and part in diet

Using Ecosim fitted on the 1980-2013 period (on catch and abundance time series), 4 simulations were performed over the 2014-2030 period: the baseline assuming an implementation of Fmsy for five overexploited stocks, Scenario 1: baseline + Landing obligation, Scenario 2: + increasing the consumption of discards by Nephrops (10 %), Scenario 3: + survival rate of Nephrops = 30 %. Simulations of each scenario for year 2030 are compared to baseline.

Results show that the landing obligation logically affects groups whose diet includes a large amount of discards: seabirds and scavengers (Fig. XXX). Changes are less than 1 % for the total Biomass, or for all other groups, or for all trophic classes. In term of catch, the most affected group is nephrops (in scen. 2 & 3), at trophic levels around 3.

Figure 20: Relative changes induced by the landing obligation, compared to baseline (values equal to 1 means no change). Left: biomass per Ecopath group; right: trophic spectra of biomass (top) and catches (bottom)

Sensitivity analysis showed that the main parameter determining the impact of the landing obligation is the diet on discards. Detailed results have been presented in the WP1 - 18 months report from June 2016.

2.6.3.3 BoB2 - EwE 1996-2030

2.6.3.3.1 The Ecopath model

An Ecopath model represents how the dynamic of the Bay of Biscay - French continental shelf was in 1996. The food web is composed by 35 functional groups, from bacteria and primary producers up to marine mammals and birds (see Table 5). This configuration, though based on the one previously published by Lassalle et al. (2011), slightly differs from it in the sense that it contains more functional groups that are composed by single species rather than groups of species. This new configuration has been designed to provide the model with the ability of simulating the existing management measures related to the CFP, actually defined on a single stock level basis.

Table 5: Composition of the food web.

<i>Functional group</i>		<i>Functional group</i>	
1	Pursuit divers seabirds	19	Red mullet
2	Surface feeders seabirds	20	Benthic cephalopods
3	Striped dolphins	21	Pelagic cephalopods
4	Bottlenose dolphins	22	Carnivorous benthic invertebrates
5	Common dolphins	23	Necrophagous benthic invertebrates
6	Long-finned pilot whales	24	Sub-surface deposit feeders invertebrates
7	Harbour porpoises	25	Surface suspension and deposit feeders inv
8	Rays	26	Benthic meiofauna
9	Adult hake	27	Suprabenthic invertebrates
10	Monkfish	28	Macrozooplankton
11	Megrim	29	Mesozooplankton
12	Blue whiting	30	Microzooplankton
13	Juvenile hake	31	Bacteria
14	Mackerel	32	Large phytoplankton
15	Horse mackerel	33	Small phytoplankton
16	Anchovy	34	Discards
17	Sardine	35	Detritus
18	Sea Bass		

As explained in the introductory section, this model aims to explicitly represent the dynamics of the fishery the CS is focused on, but the activity of the other fishing activity in the study area still needs to be represented. So, Fleet components of these previous models have also been modified aiming to better reflect the dynamics of the different métiers operating in the study area, in particular the Spanish fleet operating there: the trawling fleet based in the ports of Ondarroa. The operation of this fishery is divided in métiers (EC, 2008), and three métiers have been identified depending on the group of target species: pair trawlers (PTB), bottom otter trawlers targeting demersal species (OTD) and bottom otter trawlers targeting mixed species (OTM). An additional fishery has been included, called 'others (OTH)' representing a non-real fishery to somehow simulate the activity of other existing fisheries and aiming to account for the total landings and discards produced in the study area (purse seines, long-lines, other trawls, etc.; see Table 6)

Table 6: Composition of the fishery in the model

	<i>Fleet name</i>
PTB	Pair trawlers
OTD	Bottom otter trawlers targeting demersal species
OTM	Bottom otter trawlers targeting mixed species
OTH	Others

The initial information required by the static Ecopath model (biomass (B), production per biomass ratios (P/B), consumption per biomass ratios (Q/B) and ecotrophic efficiencies (EE) for each functional group) has been derived from previous models already existing in the study area (Lassalle et al., 2011;2012), and has also been compared and combined with the information existing in the literature.

Results

The Bay of Biscay ecosystem is a very complex system where both the pelagic and the demersal realms are well connected. Figure 21 shows the existing trophic relationships between functional groups and the fleet, which are represented by coloured bubbles that are proportional to each species' biomass or the total catches in the case of the fleet groups.

Figure 21: Ecopath flow diagram. The size of the bubbles is relative to the total biomass of each functional group. The arrows represent energy flows between different functional groups.

The figure above shows that discards are a relevant food source for seabirds and necrophagous benthic invertebrates, but also for other demersal fish species and carnivorous benthic invertebrates.

The relative impact that each functional group and fleet is exerting on the whole ecosystem is shown in Figure 22. There are negative and positive impacts (black and white dots respectively). This figure shows that the groups that are most impacted by discards are the ones composed by sea birds.

Figure 22: Mixed Trophic Impact figure. White and black dots represent positive and negative impacts respectively, and the size of the dot is proportional to the impact.

2.6.3.3.2 The Ecosim model:

Ecosim is the time-dynamic module of EwE. Given the limitations of the previous EwE version that was publicly available in the beginning of the project to adequately distinguish landing and discards dynamics in Ecosim, the new beta version developed for DiscardLess and MinouW projects has been used to develop this work (Beta version 6.6). this new Beta version will be publicly available at the end of 2018⁵.

⁵ See more information in <http://ecopath.org/>

Ecosim has been fitted to data from 1996 to 2013. Observations coming from publically available data bases (mainly ICES database) and data recorded by AZTI (DCF and Spanish discard sampling programme). Survey data have also been used for biomass estimates when available. Time series used to fit the model are:

- a) Relative biomass: data coming from EVHOE, BIOMAN and JUVENA surveys.
- b) Fishign efforts: data from ICES database
- c) Fishing mortalities: data coming from ICES database.
- d) Landings and discards: -
 - i. for the three métiers of the CS: data coming from AZTI database
 - ii. for the OTH fleet: estimated using ICES database
- e) Discard proportion: derived from c)

Results

The model has been fitted to the available observations using the traditional fitting procedure available in Ecosim. The best fitting of the Ecosim model to the observations available for the period 1996-2013 ia shown inFigure 23, based only on Biomass data.

Figure 23: Best fitting of biomass time series in the Ecosim model

2.6.4 EwE in the Azores

2.6.4.1 Introduction

The archipelago of the Azores, is a Portuguese autonomous region located in the Northeast Atlantic Ocean, along the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. It is located about 1500 km west of mainland Europe and about 3000 km from North America, and is an EU outermost region. Composed of nine islands widespread over 600 km, the Azores occupies a vast territory with an Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) of approximately 1 million km² (Figure 24). With the absence of a continental shelf and surrounding great depths, fishing occurs around the island slopes and the many seamounts present in its vast exclusive economic zone of 1 million km² (Silva and Pinho, 2007; Morato et al., 2008). The Azorean fishing industry is composed of five main components (Pham et al. 2013):

- i) a pole-and-line tuna fishery, and its associated live-bait fishery;
- ii) deep-water bottom longline and handline fishery targeting mainly deep-sea demersal fishes such as blackspot seabream (*Pagellus bogaraveo*), wreckfish (*Polyprion americanus*), alfonsinos (*Beryx* spp.), and blackbelly rosefish (*Helicolenus dactylopterus*);
- iii) a small-net fishery for small pelagic species (blue jack mackerel, *Trachurus picturatus*, and chub mackerel, *Scomber colias*).
- iv) a pelagic longline fishery targeting swordfish (*Xiphias gladius*) and pelagic sharks. This gear is operated by fishing vessels registered in the Azores (regional), in mainland Portugal or in other EU countries (foreign);
- v) drifting deep-water longline fishery for black scabbardfish (*Aphanopus carbo*)

Additionally, there are other fishing activities in the Azores such as recreational fishing, seasonal squid fisheries targeting veined squid (*Loligo forbesi*), and collection of coastal marine invertebrates such as octopus (*Octopus vulgaris*) or slipper lobster (*Scyllarides latus*). Finally, there was an experimental bottom trawling fishing the Azores around in 2001 and 2002 (Melo and Menezes, 2002) targeting orange roughy (*Hoplostethus atlanticus*).

Figure 24: Map of bathymetry and main fishing regulations in place within the Azores Economic Exclusive Zone (EEZ).

The current fishery resource management in the Azores is based on the EU CFP, implemented primarily through total allowable catches (TACs) for various species including blackspot seabream, alfonsinos, greater forkbeard (*Phycis blennoides*), black scabbardfish, and deepwater sharks such as *Deania* spp., *Centrophorus* spp., *Etmopterus* spp., *Centroscymnus* spp., and kitefin shark (*Dalatias licha*) (EC Reg. 2340/2002; EC Reg. 2270/2004). The quota of alfonsinos is set for both species together, *Beryx splendens* and *B. decadactylus* and has been reduced and reached earlier in the recent years. For deep-water sharks, a zero TAC has been implemented since 2010 for 13 taxa (EC Reg. 1359/2008). A zero TAC has also been implemented for orange roughy (*Hoplostethus atlanticus*), but since 2017 the species has been declared “prohibited species” implying that under the landing obligation (LO) all catch must be discarded. While for deep-water sharks that are still under zero TAC, to date, it remains unsure how their catch will have to be handled under the LO in the Azores starting in 2019. Apart from the quotas system, the regional government of the Azores has implemented technical measures over the years, such as minimum landing sizes or weights, minimum mesh and hook sizes, limitation of licenses for some specific gears, area and temporal closures, and bans on the use of specific gear. An example is the regulation that prohibited deep-sea trawling in the Azores (Figure 24).

Main discarded species in the Azores fisheries are those under catch limit regulations (TAC or MLS), such as the splendid alfonsino, blackbelly rosefish and European conger in the deep-water fisheries. However, discards from the deep-sea fishery was described of most concern since it includes many deep-water sharks listed in the IUCN red list of endangered species, such as the “critically endangered” blue skate (*Dipturus batis*), the “near threatened” kitefin shark, greenland shark (*Somniosus microcephalus*), and Portuguese dogfish (*Centroscymnus coelolepis*), the “vulnerable” leafscale gulper shark (*Centrophorus squamosus*) and gulper shark (*Centrophorus granulosus*), and the “least concern” arrowhead dogfish (*Deania profundorum*), birdbeak dogfish (*Deania calcea*), longnose velvet dogfish (*Centroscymnus crepidater*), and the smooth lanternshark (*Etmopterus pusillus*). It was suggested that the establishment of a TAC system for the multispecific bottom fishery greatly increased discard rates of deep-sea species

without decreasing catch levels. Here, we developed a food-web model to evaluate ecosystem impacts of the implementation of the landing obligation in the Azores marine ecosystem.

2.6.4.2 Model and data

2.6.4.2.1 Modelling

We built an Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) food-web model of the Azores ecosystem. The trophic static mass-balanced snapshots (Ecopath) was adapted from Morato et al. (2016), while temporal dynamic (Ecosim) was built by calculating the Ecopath parameters for each time-step, taking into account changes in fishing effort, environmental factors or other parameters. Our model was fitted to time series data (Christensen and Walters, 2004).

For this study, we confined the study area based on the boundary of the EEZ, which covers an area of about 1 million Km² (Figure 24). The area includes the deep-sea, open-ocean, some seamounts, parts of the Mid Atlantic Ridge and island slopes. The year 1997 was chosen as reference since most of the data used to construct the base model (diet and growth parameters) originated from that year. A total of 11 Azorean fisheries were included in the model: the deep-water bottom longline and handline, the Azores pelagic longline, Portuguese mainland pelagic longline, and the foreign pelagic longline fisheries, the pole and line tuna fishery (including the live-bait), the small pelagic fisheries, the drifting deep-water longline, the commercial coastal invertebrates, the recreational fishing, the experimental bottom trawling, and the squid fisheries.

The current EwE framework allows to model discards jointly with landings within the definition of one fleet. However, discards mitigation scenarios involved modifying discarding practices temporally in the model, independently from landed catches. Therefore, each fishery was split into several fleets in Ecopath as following:

- (1) Always landed: catch of commercial value, landed in every scenario
- (2) Quota discarded: discarded catch due to regulation (TAC or MLS)
- (3) Non-quota discarded: discarded catch for other reason (e.g. prohibited species, no commercial value, etc.)
- (4) Quota landed: catch which should have been discarded due to regulation (TAC or MLS), but landed in some scenarios
- (5) Non-quota landed: catch which should have been discarded for other reason (e.g. prohibited species, no commercial value, etc.), but landed in some scenarios

Catches, by group and landed/discarded type, were therefore split between those fleets accordingly. The structure of Ecosim then allowed to transfer catches from fleets (2) and (3) to (4) and (5) (e.g. from discards to landings) during scenario projection. This was done duplicating the fishing effort time series for the corresponding fleets. During the model historical period (1997-2013), fishing efforts of fleets (4) and (5) were always 0, but would be attributed a value (average of the last 3 years for the projection (2013-2030) if the scenario required it (and reversely for fleets (2) and (3)).

2.6.4.2.2 Model construction and parametrization

The current version of the Azores model was built upon previous models developed for this region and associated seamounts (Morato et al., 2016). The present model focused mostly on intermediate and deep-water species present in the Azores ecosystem and used, when possible, recent and local data for model parameterization. Species with biological and ecological similarities were grouped into functional groups

or biomass pools. The present model took into consideration 387 fish species representing about 66% of the known marine fish biodiversity. With the exception of marine mammals (16 most common species, representing 66% of the known biodiversity; Mónica Silva, pers. comm.), seabirds (8 most common species, 73% of reported nesting species; Verónica Neves, pers. comm.), and sea turtles (3 most common species, 60% of the reported species; Marco Silva, pers. comm.), most of the non-fish groups were poorly represented in the model due to the limited amount of information available. In this model, energy related parameters are expressed in $t \cdot km^{-2}$ of wet weight and the temporal unit is year⁻¹.

Of the 387 fish species compiled, only 223 (representing 38% of the known fish biodiversity) were included in the model because of data limitations. All of the selected species were allocated stepwise to 29 functional groups after compiling a dataset with diet composition, asymptotic length and average habitat depth for each species, gathered from local studies and completed with Fishbase data (Froese et al., 2015). In addition, some fish were separated into single species functional groups because of their commercial interest or to allow specific management simulations. These are: *Helicolenus dactylopterus*, *Conger conger*, *Pontinus kuhlii*, *Raja clavata*, *Phycis phycis*, *Pagrus pagrus*, *Beryx splendens*, *Beryx decadactylus*, *Pagellus bogaraveo*, *Mora moro*, *Lepidopus caudatus*. The model presented here consisted of 46 functional groups: one detritus group, one detritus group consisting of discards, two primary producer groups, eight invertebrate groups, 29 fish groups, three marine mammal groups, one sea-turtle, and one seabird group. This ecosystem model was improved from Morato et al. (2016) by adding a group of detritus representing the discards (i.e. catch returned to the sea).

Model parameters, P/B, Q/B, and production of consumption ratio (P/Q) were estimated from the literature, with preference to studies within our area or from similar areas, or using empirical equations (Pauly, 1980; Palomares and Pauly, 1998). Habitat area fraction, which is the habitat area to total model area ratio, for each group was calculated using habitat depth ranges compiled from local studies (e.g. Menezes et al., 2006) and Fishbase, and converted into surface areas using bathymetric grid of the Azores.

A diet matrix was assembled using preferentially local literature on stomach content analyses, completed with other literature and adapted using empirical knowledge. Since it is almost impossible to distinguish discarded from live prey in the diet studies, the allocation of discards in the diet matrix followed a two steps approach. First, potential scavengers were ranked into categories using literature review and local knowledge, from null (not a scavenger group) to high (high chances of being a scavenger group). Then, the following discards consumption rate were used: “null” = 0; “low” = 0.07%; “medium” = 0.3%; “high” = 0.8%.

2.6.4.2.3 Fisheries catch and discards data

As part of the DiscardLess project, we built an updated version of Pham *et al.* (2013) catch reconstruction to disaggregate the portion of the catch which is returned at sea (i.e. discarded) from the unreported amounts for the 1950 to 2014 period, and to include exhaustive and detailed discard estimates at the species level for all fisheries, using fisheries observer data, published reports or local expert knowledge (Fauconnet et al., 2019). Discarding practices of the bottom longline and handline fishery, the drifting deep-water longline for black scabbardfish, the pole-and-line tuna fishery and its associated live bait-fishery, and the pelagic longline fishery were directly derived from observer data. For other fisheries, discard practices were derived either from observer data from similar fisheries or species that can be used as proxies, published reports, or local ecological knowledge. Most of the Azores fisheries are relatively selective compared to most fisheries in Europe (Fauconnet et al., 2019), due to higher

selectivity of the fishing gears and utilization of non-commercialized catch (Figure 25). The pole-and-line tuna fishery is responsible for the highest catches, but the discards rate is negligible (0.03% in weight). On the other hand, the regional pelagic longline fleet, although shows overall low catches, discards the highest proportion of catch (43.6%). Bottom longlines and handlines and artisanal purse-seine are also responsible for discards (10.3% and 13%, respectively). Discards' fate was assumed 100% mortality, of which around 98% was set to be consumed in the ecosystem by adjusting the diet matrix.

Species landings and discards data was assigned to the different fishing fleets and functional groups. Catch data that could not be assigned to a specific functional group or fleet (e.g. unidentified marine species) were redistributed into the groups exploited by the various fleets. Catch data was constructed for the reference year 1997 and then expressed in tonnes of wet weight per square kilometre of the model area.

Figure 25: Total catches (tonnes) in the model historical period (1997-2013), discriminated by retained, i.e. landed or kept for other uses (grey) and discarded (red), by fishery

2.6.4.2.4 Model calibration using times series of catch, relative abundance and fishing effort

Time series of fisheries catches and relative biomass for the period 1997-20134 were taken as historical comparison data. Time series of fisheries catch were obtained for the period 1997-2013 as described in the fisheries data section. Time series of an index of relative abundances (IRA) were obtained from the Azorean Spring deep-water bottom longline surveys as catch per unit of effort in weight standardized by depth and fishing ground (Menezes et al., 2006; Menezes et al., 2013). In addition to IRA time series for monospecific functional groups, *Polyprion americanus*, *Serranus atricauda*, *Pagellus acarne*, and *Galeorhinus galeus* were used as representative species for the large demersal fish group, large shallow-water fish group, medium shallow-water fish group, and benthic sharks and rays respectively.

Time series of fishing effort were used to drive the model over the same period. Fishing effort relative to 1997, was estimated as the number of landings events in the official database per fleet for the pole and line tuna fishery, the Azores pelagic longline fleet, the small pelagic fisheries, the drifting deep-water longline, the commercial coastal invertebrates, and the squid fisheries. This was the best available information for the purpose of this study and was considered a realistic representation of fishing effort

in the Azores (Hugo Diogo, personal communication). Fishing effort for the deep-water bottom longline and handline fleet was estimated as the number of hooks per year, while for the mainland Portugal and international pelagic longline fleets effort was estimated from unpublished VMS data. Fishing effort for recreational fishing was estimated based on local population fluctuations.

Model calibration in Ecosim was done following the best practices recommendation (Heymans et al., 2016). Model performance was assessed by the sum of squared (SS) deviations of observed log biomass (or catch) from log predicted biomass (or catch). The Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) (Akaike, 1974) and AICc (small sample size) (Burnham, 2004) was calculated to account for the use of an increased number of estimated parameters k and the number of data points n . The fitting procedure included mainly two different steps. First, a primary production anomaly was used as a forcing function applied to producer groups to reproduce primary production changes over time, impacting the total energy amount in the ecosystem by a bottom-up cascade (Christensen et al., 2008). Secondly, vulnerability parameter of the predator-prey interactions based on the foraging arena theory (Ahrens et al., 2012), was adjusted by identifying the most sensitive predator-prey interactions and optimizing their values. The default value 2, stands for a mixed effect control, while lower vulnerabilities indicate a bottom-up control and higher ones indicate a top-down control of the interaction (range 1-100). The best statistically significant model was built with forcing function on primary producers (Phytoplankton and Algae) with 5 spline points, and 16 modified vulnerabilities applied to predator groups. With a total of 21 estimated parameters, the SS dropped from 102 to 89 and the AIC from -1605 to -1670.

2.6.4.2.5 Discard scenarios

Five scenarios (Table 7) were run for the projection period 2013-2030 allowing to discriminate landings from the unwanted catch (Figure 26: Total catches (tonnes) in the first year of projection by scenario, discriminated by retained (grey) and discarded (red) in the Azores model.). These projections were run using the average of fishing and forcing function for the previous three years (2010-2012). A selection of ecosystem indicators were calculated, allowing for a comparison of ecosystem properties between scenarios. These were: biomass, landings, discards, total primary production, Total System Throughput (TST), development capacity, and total ascendancy. Outputs of the final stages of the runs (average of the 3 last years of the runs 2028-2030) of each scenario were compared to those of Business as Usual scenario to evaluate the impacts of the implementation of the landing obligation in the Azores marine ecosystem.

Table 7: *Scenarios and different types of catch attributed to each of them.*

Scenarios	Landed	Discarded
Business as Usual	Landings with commercial value	discards of quota and non-quota species
No Discards	landings with commercial value, plus discards of quota and non-quota species	no discards
Landing Obligation	landings with commercial value, plus discards of quota species	discards of non-quota species
Landing Obligation + Selectivity	Landings with commercial value	discards of non-quota species
Selectivity	Landings with commercial value	No discards

Figure 26: Total catches (tonnes) in the first year of projection by scenario, discriminated by retained (grey) and discarded (red) in the Azores model.

2.6.4.3 Results

2.6.4.3.1 Ecosystem indicators at final stage

Removing discards from the ecosystem and increasing fishing gear selectivity to avoid unwanted catch, had in general very low effects on the Azores ecosystem. The total biomass of the system was estimated to change from about -0.01% to 0.01% (Figure 27). Total landings, however, increased in all four scenarios (Figure 27) due to two main reasons. In the No Discards and Landing Obligation scenarios landings increased (10% and 8%, respectively) mostly because formerly-discarded catches were landed. Therefore, the higher amount of landings does not mean those scenarios would generate higher economical revenue. In the Landing Obligation + Selectivity and Selectivity scenarios, landings in the last years of the runs were higher than in the baseline (1.5 and 1.7%, respectively) mostly because of an increase in landings of commercially important species. The combined increase in landings and ecosystem biomass in the selectivity scenarios could highlight positive ecological and economical effects of these management strategies.

Figure 27: Biomass (purple) and landings (grey) difference in each scenario compared to Business as Usual at the final stage (average 2028-2030).

Little difference in the four ecological indicators were observed between the scenarios and the baseline at the end of the projections (Figure 28). However, the scenarios where discards were completely removed from the system (No Discards and Selectivity) had lower Total System Throughput and development capacity. Thus, scenarios with no discards as a food source, decreasing the nutrient availability, might pull down the complexity of trophic flows and therefore the resilience of the system.

Figure 28: Ecosystem indicators difference at the final stage of the runs (average 2028-2030) for each scenario compared to Business as Usual.

2.6.4.3.2 Biomass changes and trophic cascades

The biomass differences between the Business as Usual and other scenarios at the end of the runs were compared in order to identify the impact of the shortage of discards and selectivity measures on specific groups. Biomass changes were measured as proportion of change, ranging from -1 to 1 (0 meaning no difference), and giving positive results in case of higher biomass in the discard mitigation strategy scenario (and reversely).

Not surprisingly, the effect of removing the discard (No discards and LO scenarios) is highly dependent on the importance of discards in the diets of the different groups (Figure 29). Scenarios which also introduced selectivity had more complex outputs. On one hand, there was a shortcut of discards as a food source, and on the other hand, less biomass removal from fisheries. Therefore, those scenarios showed mixed tendencies, depending on each group's fishing mortality and diets.

Figure 29: Proportion of biomass change relatively to Business as Usual scenario of functional groups with different consumption rates on discards.

The no discards and the landing obligation scenarios showed very little impact on the biomass of the different groups (Figure 30). On the other hand both selectivity scenarios showed an overall increase on biomass of groups with higher trophic levels and negative effect on those groups of intermediate trophic levels. Selectivity measures released pressure on high trophic level groups which in turn generated higher predation on lower trophic levels. Different tendencies could be observed for some groups and scenarios. Groups feeding on discards and less caught under selectivity scenarios were of special interest. For instance, contrarily to other scenarios, *Beryx splendens* and the DW sharks group showed a clear increase in biomass in the Selectivity scenario. Thus, the shortage of discards as a food source might be overly compensated by the decrease in fishing pressure for those groups. On the other hand, a number of groups of intermediate trophic levels and commercial interest found their biomasses negatively impacted by selectivity measures, such as *Pagellus bogaraveo* or *Phycis phycis*.

Figure 30: Proportion of biomass change relatively to Business as Usual scenario of all functional groups, ranked by trophic level.

Finally, changes in the trophic spectrum of each scenario was built, therefore illustrating the changes in trophic spectrum of the scenarios (Figure 31). Similarly to Figure 6, the selectivity scenarios display very different patterns than the No Discards and Landing Obligation scenarios, and a clear “top-down” trophic cascade.

Figure 31: Changes in trophic spectrum for each scenario relatively to Business as Usual. . No Dis = no discard, LO = Landing obligation, Sel = Selectivity. Results of the LO+Sel scenario are overlapped with those of the No Disc+Sel scenario.

2.6.4.4 Discussion and conclusion

The differences in catches, biomasses and ecosystem indicators at the final stages of all scenarios were reduced compared to other studies (Celić et al., 2018; Fondo et al., 2015; Heath et al., 2014). Overall, measured differences were very small, and indicated likely no major impacts of implementation of the landing obligation in the Azores ecosystem. The current discarding rate in Azorean fisheries is rather low compared to other areas in the world, and behind the low values of discards dependencies in the model parametrization. On a modelling perspective, these results highlight the interdependence between model parametrization and the measured impact of a fishery scenario. On an ecological aspect, the reliance of living organisms to this food source might be mitigated in the Azores, and their adaptation to a potential shortage, although not modelled in the present study, could therefore happen faster than in other ecosystems. Nonetheless, although impacts of different discards mitigation strategies seem limited, these scenarios highlight the synergetic effects of trophic links and fisheries through the different patterns observed by the different ecosystem components. Functional groups feeding the most on discards were found to be negatively impacted by a discards' shortage, but showed mixed impacts if their fishing mortality was reduced by selectivity measures. Heath et al. (2013) found similar "top-down" trophic cascades in the case of light exploitation scenarios, and opposite trends in heavy exploitation scenarios. In this study, positive impacts observed in selectivity scenarios are rather low and subject to uncertainty (model uncertainty, implementation uncertainty and ecological/climatological uncertainty). A sensitivity analysis is undergoing, tackling the influence of the amount of discards in the system and initial model parametrization of the model results. Despite low realism of these models due to the assumptions of constant conditions and full implementation of the scenarios, they allow to explore how the ecosystem could respond under highly contrasted scenarios, which likely encompass more realist ones.

2.6.4.5 References

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2.6.5 EwE in the Balearic Islands

2.6.5.1 Introduction

The Balearic Islands (Figure 32) are constituted by four main islands (Mallorca, Menorca, Ibiza and Formentera) covering about 5000 Km². Compared to the nearest mainland, the Archipelago is one of the most distant insular areas in the Mediterranean, separated from the Iberian Peninsula by depths of 2000 m. Several decades ago the Balearic Islands were defined as an individualized fishing area in the western Mediterranean (Massutí, 1991). More recently, a comprehensive comparison including different aspects such as habitats, fisheries and exploitation state of resources and ecosystems between the Balearic Islands and the adjacent coast of the Iberian Peninsula, concluded that the Archipelago should be maintained as an independent unit for assessment and management purposes in the western Mediterranean (Quetglas et al., 2012).

Figure 32: Map of the study area showing the Balearic Islands and its location in the western Mediterranean.

The fishing grounds exploited by the demersal fisheries from the Balearic Islands are characterized by the presence of sensitive and essential fish habitats, especially on the coastal continental shelf. These essential habitats basically include maërl and *Peyssonnelia* beds (Ordines and Massutí, 2009), which are frequent down to 90 m depth. It has been demonstrated that both habitats are essential for the fishing resources (Ordines et al., 2009, 2015; Ordines, 2015), being catalogued with the term Essential Fish Habitats (EFH). Moreover, the maërl beds are sensitive habitats protected under the European fishing regulation EUNo 1967/2006. The crinoids beds, also considered an EFH (Colloca et al., 2004; Ardizzone, 2006; Ordines and Massutí, 2009; Ordines, 2015), dominate certain areas of the deep shelf, primarily between 120 and 200 m depth.

A total of 16 different ports exist in the Balearic Islands where the commercial fisheries include bottom trawl, small-scale, purse seine and longline, but recreational fishery is also important. Bottom trawl and small-scale, which are the main demersal fisheries, are characterized by their multispecific character, with more than 100 species in their landings.

Landings of the bottom trawl fleet have reported a 59% in terms of biomass. Commercial trawlers use up to four different fishing tactics (Palmer et al., 2009), which are associated with the shallow and deep continental shelf, and the upper and middle continental slope (Ordines et al., 2006; Guijarro and Massuí, 2006). Vessels mainly target striped red mullet (*Mullus surmuletus*) and European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*) on the shallow and deep shelf respectively, which are caught with a wide variety of fish and cephalopod species. The Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*) and the red shrimp (*Aristeus antennatus*) are the main target species on the upper and middle slope respectively. The Norway lobster is caught at the same time as a large number of fish and crustacean species, but the red shrimp is the only Mediterranean trawl fishery that could be considered monospecific.

Landings of the small-scale fishery have reported a 20% in terms of biomass, which targets the following eight fishing tactics and corresponding target species: i) purse seine: dolphinfish (*Coryphaena hippurus*); ii) purse seine: transparent goby (*Aphia minuta*); iii) handline: squid (*Loligo vulgaris*); iv) trammel net: striped red mullet (*Mullus surmuletus*); v) trammel net: cuttlefish (*Sepia officinalis*); vi) longline: dentex (*Dentex dentex*); vii) longline: red scorpionfish (*Scorpaena scrofa*); viii) trammel net: spiny lobster (*Palinurus elephas*). The three first fishing tactics are practically monospecific, having very low by-catches.

Recreational fisheries has important economic, social, and cultural roles in the Mediterranean, representing more than 10% of total fisheries production (European Commission, 2004), and it has been studied from mid-2000s (Morales-Nin et al., 2005, 2008).

Fisheries management in the Balearic Islands involves regulations at European, national and local levels. The main European regulations are: I) Council Regulation (EU) No 1967/2006 of 21 December 2006 concerning management measures for the sustainable exploitation of fishery resources in the Mediterranean Sea (amended on certain provisions by Regulation (EU) 2015/2102 of 28 October 2015); and II) Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 (amended on certain provisions by Regulation (EU) 2017/2092 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 November 2017). At national level, the Order AAA/2808/2012 of 21 December established an Integral Management Plan for the conservation of Mediterranean fisheries resources caught by purse seine, bottom trawl and small-scale fleets for the period 2013-2017 (extended by the Order APM/1322/2017 of 29 December). At local scale, regulations focused to local fisheries taking place, fully or partially, within external waters also exist.

2.6.5.2 Model and data

2.6.5.2.1 Baseline run: the Ecopath model

The data used in the initial Ecopath model are an average of three years (2001-2003), which included biomass, catches, diets, and production and consumption data. The model included 46 groups (Table 8). Data sources were as follows. For the biomass, information was obtained during bottom trawl and beam trawl surveys. For the catches, data was obtained from bottom trawl, purse seine, longliner, artisanal and

recreational fisheries; commercial data was based on daily sale bills from the fishing organizations and discards data was computed based in the information from an observers on board program. Information on diets was own data from analysis of stomach contents, isotops and bibliography. Finally, production and consumption data were obtained from empirical relationships and bibliography.

Table 8: Functional groups used in the Balearic islands EwE model.

Functional groups	Short description
1 Dolphins	main species of dolphins present in the Balearic Sea
2 Sea birds	main species of seabirds present in the Balearic Sea
3 Loggerhead turtle	<i>Caretta caretta</i>
4 Pelagic sharks	pelagic shark species <i>Prionace glauca</i> , <i>Isurus oxyrrhincus</i> and <i>Alopias vulpinus</i>
5 Large pelagics	large pelagic species <i>Thunnus thynnus</i> , <i>Xiphias gladius</i> and <i>Tetrapturus belone</i>
6 Medium pelagics	medium size pelagic species <i>Euthynnus</i> spp., <i>Brama brama</i> , <i>Sarda sarda</i> , etc
7 Dolphinfish	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>
8 Macrocarnivorous fishes	demersal carnivorous species
9 Juvenile hake	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i> < 250 m
10 Adult hake	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i> > 250 m
11 Anglerfish	<i>Lophius piscatorius</i> and <i>Lophius budegassa</i>
12 Demersal fish 1	shallow demersal species (< 50 m)
13 Demersal fish 2	shelf demersal species (50 to 200 m)
14 Deep sea fish	slope demersal species (200 to 800 m)
15 Transparent gobies	pelagic goby species, <i>Aphia minuta</i> , <i>Cristallogobius linearis</i> and <i>Pseudaphya ferreri</i>
16 Mulletts	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i> and <i>Mullus barbatus</i>
17 Flatfish	flatfish species present in the Balearic Sea
18 Mesopelagic	
19 Horse mackerel	<i>Trachurus</i> spp. and <i>Scomber scombrus</i>
20 Sardine & anchovy	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i> , <i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i> and <i>Sardinella aurita</i>
21 Benthopelagic feeders	schooling species - feeding either on zooplankton or fish
22 Demersal sharks (shelf)	
23 Demersal sharks (slope)	
24 Rays & skates	
25 Octopus	
26 Cuttlefishes	
27 Squids	
28 Bivalves & gastropodes	
29 Red shrimp	<i>Aristeus antennatus</i>
30 White shrimp	<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i>
31 Norway lobster	<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i>
32 Lobsters	main species of lobsters, <i>Palinurus</i> spp., and <i>Scyllarides latus</i>
33 Other shrimps	
34 Crabs (reptantia)	
35 Echinodermata	
36 Other benthic invertebrates	Porifera, Ascidiacea, Cnidaria (except jellyfish) and Bryozoa

37	Annelids	
38	Suprabenthos	Amphipoda, Mysidacea, Isopoda and Cumacea
39	Gelatinous plankton	including jellyfish
40	Macrozooplankton	including larvae of some species
41	Micro & mesozooplankton	
42	Benthic primary producers	
43	Seagrass	<i>Posidonia oceanica</i>
44	Phytoplankton	

This initial model was fitted with a time series from 2004 to 2017, which included biomass, catches, fishing effort, and fishing mortalities. To force the model we used fishing effort, fishing mortalities and discard proportions; to validate it, we used relative biomasses, and catches separated in landings and discards.

2.6.5.2.2 Scenarios: The Ecosim model

The simulations that have been carried out, go from 2018 to 2035 for the five scenarios (Sc):

1. Discards as usual: no changes in the fishery
2. No discards: there are no discards, so that everything which is not commercial, it is returned to the sea
3. No discards and selectivity: there are no discards, and, moreover, the selectivity of the gear is so high that nothing is returned to the sea
4. Landing obligation: contemplates the return to the sea of these species which have not Minimum Conservation Reference Size (MCRS).
5. Landing obligation and selectivity: the return to the sea of these species which have not Minimum Conservation Reference Size (MCRS), but the selectivity is so high that nothing is returned to the sea

2.6.5.3 Results

2.6.5.3.1 Baseline run: the Ecopath model

The Balearic Island ecosystem is a web trophic system with high complexity, with many connections among the functional groups. Figure 33 shows the existing trophic relationships among the functional groups which appear in the ecosystem and the different fleets that operate in the area (on the right of the figure). One of the peculiarities of the ecosystem is the great importance of the benthic primary producers and seagrass.

Figure 33: Flow diagram of the Ecopath model of the Balearic Islands, with the functional groups and the fleets involved. The size of the bubbles indicates the importance of the functional group in the ecosystem in terms of biomass.

2.6.5.3.2 Scenarios: the Ecosim model

The global effect on the 5 management scenarios simulated in the ecosystem did not produce big differences in the total biomass at sea (Figure 34), but the higher values were found for Scenarios 3 and 5. Regarding catches from the commercial fleets, Scenario 4 showed very similar results as Scenario 1 (current state) as the number of species subjected to MCRS in the Mediterranean is low and thus, the management measure applied in this scenario does not have a big effect on the ecosystem. In the case of Scenario 5, landings decrease, related to the high selectivity applied here. In this sense, an improvement of selectivity would be more beneficial to the environment than the application of LO. Improving the selectivity, that is shifting the size of the first capture towards the size at which fish cohorts achieve their maximum biomass would produce on average between two and three times higher economic yields and much higher biomass at sea for the exploited stocks. Moreover, it would contribute to restore marine ecosystem structure and resilience to enhance ecosystem services such as reservoirs of biodiversity and functioning food webs (Colloca et al., 2013).

Figure 34: General results of the 5 scenarios considered showing the biomass of the system (left) and the biomass discarded and landed (right).

As seen before, no big differences are detected at ecosystem level in the total biomass in any of the scenarios simulated (Figure 35). However, the effects in landings are important, with an increase of more than 13% in Sc 2 and around 3% in Sc4 and important decreases in Sc 3 (near 15%) and 5 (near 25%).

Figure 35: Biomass and landings different in each scenario compared to Scenario 1 (Business as Usual) at the final stage

2.6.5.4 References

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2.6.6 EwE in the Aegean Sea

2.6.6.1 Introduction

Northwestern (NW) Aegean includes the Gulfs of Thessaloniki (also known as inner Thermaikos) and Thermaikos as well as the gulfs of Chalkidiki Peninsula (Figure 36, see appendix in Dimarchopoulou et al. 2018). Thermaikos Gulf is the main fishing ground, which is considered one of the most productive in the Greek Seas. Thermaikos Gulf is a shallow water area having a maximum depth of 50 m. Large river systems (Gallicos, Axios, Loudias and Aliakmon) discharge into Thermaikos Gulf about 207 m³/s, with significant temporal variability (Kallianiotis et al. 2004).

According to the Fleet Register (CFR 2014), in 2014, 1460 vessels were registered in 7 ports of Thermaikos Gulf (Thessaloniki: 739 vessels; Skala Katerinis: 251 vessels; Nea Moudania: 232 vessels; Nea Michaniona: 82 vessels; Platamonas: 71 vessels; Agiokampos: 66 vessels; Stomio: 19 vessels). Based on the main gear used, 58 of these vessels are trawlers (using bottom trawls, OTB), 29 are purse seiners (using purse-seines, PS) and 1373 are small scale coastal vessels using a variety of fishing gears.

The most abundant species in the bottom trawl catches in Thermaikos Gulf are red mullet *Mullus barbatus*, cuttlefish *Sepia* spp., spottail mantis shrimp *Squilla mantis*, caramote prawn *Melicertus kerathurus*, deep-water rose shrimp *Parapenaeus longirostris*, musky octopus *Eledone* spp., anglerfish *Lophius* spp., European hake *Merluccius merluccius*, spotted flounder *Citharus linguatula*, and octopus *Octopus* spp. (Apostolidis et al. 2013). Red mullet and surmullet *Mullus surmuletus*, caramote prawn, deep-water rose shrimp, European hake, cuttlefish and octopus are the main target species of the trawl fishery in Thermaikos Gulf (Dimarchopoulou et al. 2018).

Figure 36: Map of Thermaikos Gulf and adjacent areas (redrawn with permission from Dimarchopoulou et al. 2018).

The number of non-target species is high including various species of the families Gobiidae, Labridae, Serranidae, Soleidae, Triglidae, among others (Dimarchopoulou et al. 2018). Anchovy *Engraulis encrasicolus*, sardine *Sardina pilchardus* and Atlantic chub mackerel *Scomber colias* are the main target species of the purse-seine fleet in the area. The purse-seine catch of non-target species is very low. The small-scale coastal fleet of Thermaikos Gulf targets a wide variety of species some of which are also targeted by the trawling fleet (e.g. red mullet and surmullet, and caramote prawn) and one by the purse seiners (European sardine) with very low discards as non-commercial catches are consumed or sold at very low prices, even given away.

The activities of trawlers, purse seiners and small-scale coastal vessels as well as recreational fishing are regulated by the Presidential Decree (P.D.) 68/2009 (Efimeris tis Kyverniseos No. 90, Part I, 12 June 2009, pp. 5127-5130) entitled "Regulation of fishing in the gulfs of Thessalonica and Thermaikos". The general fisheries regulations for the Greek seas, based on the European legislation, are valid unless stated or specified otherwise in the P.D. 68/2009. This Decree regulates the overall fishing activities within the major two gulfs in the region, Thessalonica and Thermaikos gulfs (see appendix in Dimarchopoulou et al. 2018 and Petza et al. 2017 for a map of fishing restrictions). It sets forth provisions for the allowable fishing gears and methods, provides specifically for trawling fishing (art. 3: bottom trawling is prohibited in Thessaloniki Gulf; in Thermaikos Gulf, bottom trawling is prohibited within 3 nm from coastline or 50 m depth should that depth is reached at shorter distance, and within 2 nm from the coastline regardless sea depth and over seagrass beds), purse-seining (art. 4: prohibited in Thessaloniki Gulf; in Thermaikos Gulf, purse-seining is prohibited within 300m from coastline or 50 m depth should that depth is reached at shorter distance), nets (art. 5: minimum stretched bar length is set at 36 mm, except for sardine nets in which it is set at 16 mm), fishing with light (art. 6: caramote prawn fishing is prohibited between January the 1st and July the 10th, and between the 11th and the 30th of September), mollusc fishing with traps (art. 7: each vessel is allowed to carry 500 pairs of fykenets or 300 traps), semi-permanent nets in the sea (art. 8), artisanal fishing (art. 9). It also makes provisions for fishing near the estuaries of rivers and for mollusc cultivation (art. 10). In article 11 are described the provisions regarding the marking of fishing gear. Some spatial restrictions also apply for trawling, purse-seining, and netting within Thermaikos Gulf (Petza et al. 2017; Dimarchopoulou et al. 2018). Regarding recreational fishing, spearfishing is completely prohibited and each fisher/boat is allowed to fish less than 3 kg of fish and cephalopods per 24h.

2.6.6.2 Model and data

An Ecopath base model has been previously constructed by Donna Dimarchopoulou (Laboratory of Ichthyology, School of Biology, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki) to quantitatively describe the trophic status of Thermaikos Gulf (Dimarchopoulou et al., submitted), one of the most important fishing grounds in the Aegean Sea (Figure 36). The prime aim for constructing this base model was to be able to test scenarios of varying fishing pressure and management practices (Dimarchopoulou et al., submitted). The Thermaikos Gulf base model included 4 fleets (trawlers, purse-seiners, boat seiners and coastal vessels) and was composed of 33 functional groups [1 primary producer (phytoplankton), 1 zooplankton, 7 benthic invertebrates, 19 fish, 1 marine mammals, 1 seabirds and 1 marine reptile, 1 discards and 1 detritus groups] (Dimarchopoulou et al., submitted). The model was confined to an area of 3339 km² (Thessaloniki Bay, Thessaloniki Gulf, inner and outer Thermaikos Gulf as they appear in Figure 36).

For assessing the effect of landings obligation on functional groups and ecosystems, the Ecopath model previously developed in Thermaikos Gulf (Dimarchopoulou et al., submitted) was slightly modified to allow the simulation of the landing obligation with landings and discards being specified per functional group per fleet. The model provides an overview of the major fluxes of discards, in terms of production (mainly from trawler fishing fleet) and consumption (mainly by seabirds, crabs and marine reptiles).

Using Ecosim fitted on the 2001-2015 period (on catch, biomass and effort time series), five simulations were performed over the 2015-2025 period (Scenario 0: the baseline assuming business as usual, Scenario 1: all discards are landed, Scenario 2: zero discards, Scenario 3: discards of the species with MCRS are landed, Scenario 4: previous discards of the species with MCRS are not caught). In Scenario 0, all dead unwanted catches are discarded at sea, into the functional group "Discards", and are consumed by the food web. In the implementation of Scenario 1 (all discards are landed), the quantities of unwanted catches are landed, whereas in Scenario 2 the unwanted catch is not caught at all through selectivity measures. In Scenario 3, only the quantities of unwanted catches of species regulated through MCRS are landed and those not regulated through MCRS are discarded. Finally, in Scenario 4, the quantities of unwanted catches of species regulated through MCRS are no longer caught and those not regulated through MCRS are discarded). Scenarios 2 and 4 are purely hypothetical scenarios and are not based on real selectivity data. Simulations of each scenario for year 2025 are compared to baseline Scenario 0. It should be noted here that the fishing effort trend was negative for most fleets during the hindcast period (2001-2015) and fishing effort was kept constant to the 2015 value for the simulation period (2015-2025).

2.6.6.3 Results

As expected, the landing obligation negatively (=biomass decline) affects the functional groups whose diets include discards and these are the seabirds, marine reptiles and crabs and to a lesser extent some other species such as other gadiforms, sharks and rays and skates (Dimarchopoulou et al. submitted). The biomass of seabirds, marine reptiles and crabs is reduced in all scenarios with the decline being higher in seabirds (ranging between 40 for Sc_1 and Sc_2 and 24% for Sc_3 and Sc_4), and crabs (ranging between 36% for Sc_1 and Sc_2 and 46% for Sc_3 and Sc_4) (Figures Figure 37 and Figure 38). The lines of scenarios 1 and 2 are overlapping in the figures because the differences between them were very small as in both scenarios the discards group becomes zero and is no longer available in the food web. Similarly for the scenarios 3 and 4.

Figure 37: ECOSIM model simulations of the biomass (kg/t2) of selected functional groups (A: crabs, B: Red mullets, C; anglerfish, D: other gadiforms) for four different scenarios of discarding (Scenario 0: the baseline assuming business as usual, Scenario 1: all discards are landed, Scenario 2: zero discards, Scenario 3: discards of the species with MCRS are landed, Scenario 4: previous discards of the species with MCRS are not caught). Lines of scenarios 1 and 2 and 3 and 4 are overlapping.

Some species such as the red mullets, anglerfish and large pelagics are benefited (=biomass increase) from landing obligation. The biomass of those groups increased in all scenarios being higher for red mullets (ranged from 8.5% for Sc_3 and Sc_4 to 19% for Sc_1 and Sc_2) and anglerfish (ranged from 8.2% for Sc_3 and Sc_4 to 17% for Sc_1 and Sc_2) (Figure 37), while it remained constant for all scenarios for large pelagics (around 15%). For all species that increase in biomass, the biomass increase was higher in scenarios 1 and 2 compared to scenarios 3 and 4. The increase in biomass of some functional groups with commercial interest could probably be also affected by the declining trend in fishing effort during the hindcast period (2001-2015) that continued in the simulation period (2015-2025). Very similar results have been recently reported as a result of the combined effect of LO and decline in fishing effort for the same functional groups (red mullets and anglerfish) in the Ionian Sea (Moutopoulos et al. 2018).

The biomass change for all other groups was less than 5% with some exceptions of decline at around 7-8% (other gadiforms and a group of demersal fishes), while the biomass of two other groups increased by 6-7% (picarels and bogue and hake).

The landings of a large number of functional groups were affected in scenarios 1 and 2 and less groups in scenarios 3 and 4 (Table 9). In terms of landings, the most affected group was crabs in all scenarios with declines down to 50%, followed by squids in scenarios 1 and 2 and shrimps across all scenarios (Figure 39, Table 9). The landings of octopuses and cuttlefish, anglerfish, other gadiforms, hake, rays and skates,

horse mackerels and two groups of demersal fishes also declined in scenarios 1 and 2, while only the landings of octopuses and cuttlefish and red mullets declined in scenarios 3 and 4 (Figure 39, Figure 40, Table 9).

Figure 38: ECOSIM model simulations of the biomass (kg/t²) of selected functional groups (A: marine reptiles, B: seabirds) for four different scenarios of discarding (Scenario 0: the baseline assuming business as usual, Scenario 1: all discards are landed, Scenario 2: zero discards, Scenario 3: discards of the species with MCRS are landed, Scenario 4: previous discards of the species with MCRS are not caught).

Despite the direction of the trend in catch (positive or negative), all scenarios resulted in lower catch compared to the baseline scenario, except for two functional groups, anglerfish and other gadiforms for which the MCRS scenarios (Sc_3 and Sc_4) resulted in higher catch in the long term (Figure 39, Figure 40, Table 9). The catch difference was higher for the invertebrate functional groups (Figure 40) compared to fish (Figure 39).

Figure 39: ECOSIM model simulations of the catch (kg/t²) of selected functional groups (A: Red mullets, B: anglerfish, C: other gadiforms, D: hake) for four different scenarios of discarding (Scenario 0: the baseline assuming business as usual, Scenario 1: all discards are landed, Scenario 2: zero discards, Scenario 3: discards of the species with MCRS are landed, Scenario 4: previous discards of the species with MCRS are not caught).

At the ecosystem level, the trends in the ecological indicators were negative for FiB and Total catch since the beginning of the time series (2001) and positive for Kempton's Q index (Figure 41). The ecological indicators showed that the values of FiB, and Total Catch were lower than the reference scenario during the whole simulation period, whereas only Kempton's Q diversity index was higher in Sc_2 (zero discards) and Sc_1 (all discards are landed).

Figure 40: ECOSIM model simulations of the catch (kg/t) of selected functional groups (A: shrimps, B: crabs, C: octopus and cuttlefish, D: squids) for four different scenarios of discarding (Scenario 0: the baseline assuming business as usual, Scenario 1: all discards are landed, Scenario 2: zero discards, Scenario 3: discards of the species with MCRS are landed, Scenario 4: previous discards of the species with MCRS are not caught).

Landing obligation will have negative ecological effect in Thermaikos Gulf by reducing the biomass of commercial and non-commercial species and the landings of economically important species, which has been previously reported for systems where fisheries are not regulated by quota such as the Mediterranean Sea (Moutopoulos et al. 2018, Celic et al. in press). Some commercial species will be directly impacted whereas indirect impacts are widespread across trophic levels as any change in the management of discards will cascade up the food web. The species of conservation concern whose biomass will decline (seabirds and marine reptiles) according to model simulations are depending on discards for their energy needs and will be directly affected by the landing obligation, at least in the Mediterranean Sea (Moutopoulos et al. 2018). Previous research reports that the discard ban alone is meaningless for the protection of the fisheries resources in the Mediterranean even if it is fully implemented (Moutopoulos et al. 2018).

Figure 41: Estimates of ecological and exploitation indices for four different scenarios of discarding (Scenario 0: the baseline assuming business as usual, Scenario 1: all discards are landed, Scenario 2: zero discards, Scenario 3: discards of the species with MCRS are landed, Scenario 4: previous discards of the species with MCRS are not caught).

Table 9: Percentage changes in biomass and landings of all functional groups in 2025 for each scenario compared to the baseline Scenario 0 (assuming business as usual) discarding (Sc 1: all discards are landed, Sc 2: zero discards, Sc 3: discards of the species with MCRS are landed).

Functional Group		Difference compared to Scenario 0 (%)							
		Biomass				Landings			
Code	Group name	Sc_1	Sc_2	Sc_3	Sc_4	Sc_1	Sc_2	Sc_3	Sc_4
1	Phytoplankton	0.00	0.00	0.18	0.18	-	-	-	-
2	Zooplankton	0.03	0.03	-0.26	-0.26	-	-	-	-
3	Benthic small crustaceans	-1.22	-1.22	-1.35	-1.35	-	-	-	-
4	Polychaetes	-0.67	-0.67	0.71	0.71	-	-	-	-
5	Shrimps	-3.21	-3.21	-9.29	-9.29	-19.68	-19.68	-24.73	-24.73
6	Crabs	-36.69	-36.69	-46.11	-46.11	-48.88	-48.88	-46.11	-46.11
7	Benthic invertebrates	-1.19	-1.19	-4.61	-4.61	-	-	-	-
8	Octopuses and cuttlefish	0.32	0.32	1.38	1.38	-17.92	-17.92	-17.05	-17.05
9	Squids	1.10	1.10	-3.21	-3.21	-22.69	-22.69	-3.21	-3.21
10	Red mullets	18.83	18.83	8.46	8.46	-1.80	-1.80	-10.36	-10.36
11	Anglerfish	16.57	16.57	8.20	8.20	-14.25	-14.25	8.20	8.20
12	Flatfishes	0.37	0.37	-7.85	-7.85	-8.13	-8.13	-7.85	-7.85
13	Other gadiforms	-8.19	-8.19	6.32	6.32	-15.67	-15.67	6.32	6.32
14	Hake	6.31	6.31	9.91	9.91	-10.41	-10.41	-7.38	-7.38
15	Demersal fishes 1	1.94	1.94	5.43	5.43	-13.61	-13.61	5.43	5.43
16	Demersal fishes 2	-2.34	-2.34	-0.46	-0.46	-5.40	-5.40	-0.46	-0.46
17	Demersal fishes 3	-10.59	-10.59	-7.43	-7.43	-15.36	-15.36	-7.43	-7.43
18	Demersal fishes 4	-6.50	-6.50	-7.00	-7.00	-7.96	-7.96	-7.00	-7.00
19	Picarels and bogue	8.39	8.39	-4.75	-4.75	2.21	2.21	-4.75	-4.75
20	Sharks	-1.12	-1.12	7.30	7.30	-7.44	-7.44	7.30	7.30
21	Rays and skates	-5.09	-5.09	-3.09	-3.09	-13.97	-13.97	-3.09	-3.09
22	Anchovy	2.32	2.32	1.43	1.43	-0.44	-0.44	-1.30	-1.30
23	Sardine	-3.86	-3.86	3.66	3.66	-5.72	-5.72	1.65	1.65
24	Horse mackerels	-12.20	-12.20	6.02	6.02	-15.17	-15.17	2.50	2.50
25	Mackerels	3.66	3.66	13.72	13.72	-0.52	-0.52	9.21	9.21
26	Other small pelagics	-0.45	-0.45	4.67	4.67	-4.51	-4.51	4.67	4.67
27	Medium pelagics	2.71	2.71	5.88	5.88	-2.91	-2.91	5.88	5.88
28	Large pelagics	14.55	14.55	15.24	15.24	-3.01	-3.01	-2.43	-2.43
29	Loggerhead turtle	-18.55	-18.55	-12.72	-12.72	-	-	-	-
30	Seabirds	-40.01	-40.01	-24.00	-24.00	-	-	-	-
31	Dolphins	9.70	9.70	-0.19	-0.19	-	-	-	-

2.6.6.4 References

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3 Modelling the impact of the Landing Obligation on fish stocks and marine ecosystems

3.1 Eastern Channel

3.1.1 Introduction

In the Eastern English Channel case study, the participatory approach implemented within DiscardLess allowed engaging in dialogue with fishers regarding the impact of the Landing Obligation (LO), the strategies for mitigating discards and the data and models used by scientists to evaluate management strategies. In the Eastern English Channel (EEC) (ICES Division VIIId), a diversity of fleets targets a large variety of species with various gears. While netters seasonally rely on sole and dredgers on scallops, cod, plaice, whiting and cephalopods occupy the rest of the year. Trawlers are more diverse in their catch along the year and also target red mullet. Together the netters, dredges and trawl fleets averaged 448 vessels over the period 2008-2014. The application of the LO is complicated for these fleets by the mixed nature of the fisheries and a regulatory system (cod plan, technical measures, licenses and quotas) that limits fleet adaptability. Two modelling frameworks were used to address these aspect.

3.1.2 Isis Fish

ISIS-Fish is a deterministic fisheries dynamic simulation model designed to investigate the consequences of alternative policies on the dynamics of resources and fleets for fisheries with mixed-species harvests (Mahevas and Pelletier, 2004; Pelletier *et al.*, 2009). It allows quantitative policy screening of combined management options, such as total allowable catch (TAC), effort control, licenses, gear restrictions, Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), etc. Fishing mortality is the result of the interaction between the spatial distribution of population abundance resulting from the population sub-model and the spatial distribution of fishing effort provided by the exploitation and management sub-models at a monthly time-step (Figure 42). Fishing effort is standardized per métier and fleet according to gear selectivity and efficiency, ability to specifically target a species and technical efficiency. The effect of management measures can therefore be explicitly modelled either through modifications of the standardization parameters for technical measures (e.g. change in the selectivity curve) or through modification of the level and spatio-temporal distribution of fishing time for seasonal closures or effort control for instance.

Fisher's response to management may be accounted for by means of decision rules conditioned on the population and exploitation variables, or explicitly implemented in the dynamic model via endogenous (e.g. fish prices and variable costs) or exogenous variables. Discarding behaviour is implemented through decision rules (by default being the consequence of catches under legal size or of quotas being reached). The model is flexible in its spatial resolution and level of complexity to accommodate the complexities of mixed fisheries. It has been applied to the Bay of Biscay hake fishery (Drouineau *et al.*, 2006) and pelagic fishery (Lehuta *et al.*, 2010, 2013), the European deep sea fishery (Marchal and Vermard, 2013), the New Zealand Hoki fishery (Marchal *et al.*, 2009), the Tasmanian costal mixed fishery, the cod fishery in the Baltic sea (Kraus *et al.*, 2008), and Mediterranean fisheries (Hussein *et al.* 2011a, 2011b).

Figure 42: Conceptual diagram of ISIS-Fish model functioning highlighting the exchanges of information between the management, fishing activity and population modules within a time step.

The Eastern Channel application focuses on the French fleets operating in ICES area VIId and on the most valuable species landed by French fleets: sole (*Solea solea*) and scallops (*Pectens maximus*). The majority of sole landings comes from netters and, to a more limited extend, bottom trawlers and mixed trawlers. Scallops are mainly landed by dredgers. The model therefore focuses on these four fleets, consisting of a total of 448 boats in average over 2008-2010. The fleet segmentation used is the segmentation created by the French Fishery Information System (Ifremer, SIH), which groups French vessels based on the main, or two main, gears used during the year. We further segmented these SIH-fleets according to length class of the vessel and home region, which results in 17 fleet segments. The other boats operating in the EEC (including international fleets) are pooled into an inexplicit fleet "OTHER", the impact of which is modelled through a fishing mortality adjusted to management constraints. The rest of the value landed by the selected fleets mainly consists in cephalopods, sea bass, whiting, red mullet, cod and plaice. The model currently describes the dynamics of cod, whiting, scallops (2 populations), sole, plaice, red mullet and cephalopods (2 populations of squids, a population of cuttlefish). The biological models build on the structure and parameters of the assessment models and parameters in use within ICES when available and on scientific survey data and literature otherwise. It accounts for spatial distribution and migration of populations in course of the year.

Population zones in the ISIS-Fish model of the Eastern Channel are based on the habitat structure identified by Girardin *et al.*, (2018) for the Atlantis model of the same region (Figure 43). Regarding métier zones, logbooks helped identifying the main ICES rectangles of practice for each gear and fleet. One métier per main rectangle is consequently created (e.g. OTB-27E9) while ICES rectangles with low effort for a given gear and fleet are pooled together in a unique métier (e.g. OTB-left). The structuring hypothesis of ISIS-Fish is the homogeneity of any variable (effort, abundance, etc.) within a zone. Fleet behavior is modeled through the dynamical modification of effort allocation on métiers in course of the simulation. A gravity model accounts for the mix of tradition and opportunist behavior of fishers when they choose which métier to practice. More details about the EEC application can be found in Lehuta *et al.* (2015) and below.

Figure 43: Spatial structure of the ISIS-Fish model of the EEC showing the overlap between population zones and métier zones (ICES rectangles).

3.1.2.1 Methods

3.1.2.1.1 Modeling effort distribution in ISIS-Fish

In ISIS-Fish, catches result from the distribution of fishing effort by several fleets on a variety of métiers which differ in the area of operation, the season, the gear and intensity of search on the different species. Monthly effort is constant but the distribution of effort on métiers is modified dynamically in course of the simulation to reflect the opportunist behaviour of fishers according to a gravity model. The gravity model allows balancing the level of traditional vs. opportunist behavior using a weighting factor α . For a given fleet, the proportion ($P_{\text{métier } i,t}$) of total effort of month t spent on a given métier i , is proportional for a part α to fisher's habits, which is approximated by the percentage of effort on métier in the year before ($t-12$), cf. equation 1, and for the rest $(1-\alpha)$, to the current ($t-1$) attractiveness of métier i , as reflected by the net value landed per unit of effort (PUE) and kg of catch (cf. equation 2). If $\alpha = 1$, fishers' behavior is completely dictated by their habits and reproduces identically from one year to the other. Inversely, if $\alpha=0$, fishers are completely driven by the current conditions and allocate their effort on métiers proportionally to their attractiveness. In the following, alpha is referred to as "level of tradition", while $(1-\alpha)$ is referred to as "level of opportunism".

$$Habits_{\text{métier } i,t} = \frac{Effort_{\text{métier } i,t-12}}{\sum_i Effort_{\text{métier } i,t-12}} \quad (1)$$

$$Attractiveness_{\text{métier } i,t} = \left(\frac{\text{Landed value PUE} - \text{Fuel costs PUE}}{\text{Landed quantity PUE}} \right)_{\text{métier } i,t-1} \quad (2)$$

Then the proportion $P_{\text{métier } i,t}$ of total effort of month t spent on a given métier i , is given by:

$$P_{\text{métier } i,t} = \alpha * Habits_{\text{métier } i,t} + (1 - \alpha) * \frac{Attractiveness_{\text{métier } i,t}}{\sum_i Attractiveness_{\text{métier } i,t}} \quad (3)$$

Opportunism was approximated by a function proportional to the landed value minus fuel costs per unit of effort and inversely proportional to landed quantity. This last term was introduced to account for the fact that for the same profit per unit of effort, fishers are expected to favor métiers minimizing unwanted i.e. unmarketable catches (under legal size fish, over-quota or non-commercial species). It compensates also for the lack of explicit account of ship's hold capacity in the model.

3.1.2.1.2 Modelling discards

In ISIS-Fish, catch results from an age/length-, fleet-, area- specific fishing mortality. The separation of the catch between landings and discards is realized afterward according to flexible decision rules. Only the landed quantities are considered for the computation of revenues. In the **status quo** simulations, discards occur if:

- 1- **Quota** for a species is reached: Catches cumulate monthly in course of the year until the quota of a species is reached. Thereafter the métier can still be practiced but the species for which their quotas are exhausted are discarded. If the revenues of the métiers concerned are significantly impaired, the gravity model that drives fishermen behavior will redirect fishermen toward more profitable métiers.
- 2- **Discarding behavior**: The analysis of data from onboard observers allowed the computation of discard rates per quarter, métier, species and fish age. It evidences that high-grading behaviors are common in the trawler fleets for species like whiting and plaice, with a large proportion of individuals above the minimum landing size discarded. The observed discard rates are applied to the catch in the Discard As Usual scenarios.

Under **LO** the assumptions are changed:

- 1- When **quota** is reached, the attractiveness of all métiers catching the species is set to zero reflecting the fact that vessels are no longer allowed to practice the métier. Exemptions can take place here, depending on the fleet or the métier or as a function of internal variables.
- 2- If fish under **minimum conservation size** are caught they are landed but their price is set to zero to reflect the absence of commercialization opportunities. The gravity model as implemented, accounts for these extra non-commercial landings, and decreases the attractiveness of the métier in consequence.

A (age-dependent) survival rate for discarded fish is possibly applied, when available (for now, the model assumes no survival of discarded fish for all species but scallops for which the survival rate is 1). Given that there is no trophic relationship in the model, the dead part of the discards is not considered in the dynamic any longer.

3.1.2.1.3 Data description

The model is parameterised and calibrated over the period 2008-2014. The population module is based on assessment model data when available (ICES, WGNSSK) and survey data for the spatial distribution and life history traits (CGFS survey, Ifremer and UK BTS survey, CEFAS). Parameters of the fishing activity module are estimated based on declarative data (Ifremer, SIH) and assessment data (ICES, 2015b). The database of model parameters can be freely downloaded at <http://isis-fish.org/download.html> and further details on the parameterisation are available in Lehuta *et al.*, (2015).

3.1.2.1.4 Scenarios

The simulation settings and design were discussed with fishers in the course of two meetings in order to ensure that scenarios will be relevant and acceptable by the fleets. The meetings helped also define the outputs of interest. Last, the assumptions regarding fleet flexibility were debated, resulting in additional scenarios for fishing behavior.

3.1.2.1.5 Fishing behavior

According to fishers, the flexibility of fleets (that is, their ability to change their behavior from one year to another) is limited due to boat characteristics (smaller boats are not able to expand their area of practice) and strategies (loss of skill to practice various métiers) and to regulatory constraints (quota availability and licenses limit their possibility to report their effort on other species). This was explored by testing three alternative values for α : 0.9 (very traditional), 0.7 (intermediate) and 0.5 (very opportunist). The impact of these assumptions is presented as intervals of variation (+/- standard deviation) around the average results.

3.1.2.1.6 Current CFP regulation and management plans

According to the common fisheries policy, a transition to F_{MSY} is implemented for the species under quota regulation (sole, plaice, cod and whiting). It is implemented in the model through TACs computed as much as possible the same way as ICES working groups do (Figure 44, Table 10). The main difference comes from the fact that ISIS-Fish is not coupled with the assessment models of the species, thus SSB is assumed perfectly known on December 31st of the previous year, and recruitment is assumed equal to the last three years average.

Figure 44: Annual computation of TAC for the species under management plan (transition to MSY between 2016 and 2020).

For each simulation year, the TAC depends on the management plan implemented, including biological safeguards ($B_{trigger}$, F_{pa}). Inter-annual variations in the TAC are limited to 15% and the transition from total allowable landing to total allowable catch assumes uplifts equal to the previously estimated discards. TACs and biological closures for scallops were carefully modelled.

Table 10: Parameters of the management plans for the modelled species.

Species	Sole	Plaice	Whiting	Cod
Discard rates	0.0924 (2014-2015 WGSSK 2016)	0.33 (2014-2016, WGSSK 2018)	0.33 (2014-2016, WGSSK 2018)	0.21 (2017, WGSSK 2018)
Fmsy	0.256	0.25	0.15	0.31
Fpa	0.256	0.36	0.28	0.39
Btrigger	19251	25826	241837	150000

3.1.2.1.7 Exemption scenarios

De minimis are under negotiation but still relatively uncertain, instead of simulating their impact, we designed two caricatural scenarios of exemptions. The first concerns métiers which catch is composed of less than 5% of the species of interest. The second targets métiers which catch represent less than 5% of the total catch of the species. Therefore the first one uses criteria at the métier scale while the second uses criteria at the stock scale.

3.1.2.1.8 Discard avoidance

Despite the doubt shown by fishers regarding their capacity to avoid catching potential choke species, avoidance strategies were discussed during the meetings. The main strategy proposed to avoid unwanted catches was the avoidance of areas and seasons with high probability of catch of the species at risk. A tool was designed within WP4 to help identify the areas and seasons of interest and used to draw three avoidance scenarios for sole and whiting.

Figure 45: Avoidance areas for Sole and Whiting as proposed based on WP4 results.

The first scenario Avoid-SolQ2 proposes to close areas located on sole coastal nurseries in the Baie de Seine and off the Baie de Somme during the second quarter for trawlers. In these areas and period more than 70% of the trips consist of more than 10% of sole (Figure 45). The two other scenarios Avoid-WhgQ1 and Avoid-WhgQ23 are closing an area located in the Strait of Pas de Calais (Figure 45) respectively in the first quarter and from April to September, where whiting constitute more than 30% of the catch in more than 50% of the trips.

3.1.2.1.9 Simulation settings:

Simulations are run for 15 years, starting in 2010 with a spin-up period of 6 years constrained with observed effort, quotas, recruitment and migrations before implementation of the management plans and LO (when appropriate). In projections recruitment is constant (last three years average), migrations and total effort per fleet are constant (2008-2014 average, corresponding to the calibration period).

3.1.2.1.10 Selected Outputs:

As required by fishers, results are evaluated both based on biological and economic outputs of the scenarios and at the fleet scale. Population biomasses, age structure, discards, as well as expected changes in revenues for each fleets and quota utilization are assessed relative to the base case scenario: Discard as usual (DAU). Results at short (4-6 years) and long term (10 years) are explored as fishers stressed the crucial importance of the transition phase.

Fishers show interest in the quantification of the sorting time as a result of the simulations. Different ways of approximating the value were discussed but it was finally considered too speculative given the time step of the model (month) and the likely multi-factorial determinism of this quantity.

Following the presentation of preliminary runs, fishers pointed out the necessity to present the result graphs in simple ways, and possibly sequentially make them more complicated in order to avoid confusion when displaying multi-dimensional results. Results were therefore made available through a shiny interface, where the type of outputs, years of interest, scale (cumulated or disaggregated), fleets, populations are user-selected thus the graphs may be built and modified by the fishers themselves.

3.1.2.2 Presentation of results

3.1.2.2.1 Impact of the landing obligation

Simulations suggest that plaice will be the choke species during the first years of implementation (2016-2018), with a late closure of the fishery around November or December, before sole takes over, and make the fishery close earlier between August and December (depending on fleet behavior and years, Figure 47). With the exception of sole, TAC are far from consumed.

Figure 46: Annual simulated TAC consumption of the four regulated species in the LO scenario.

Figure 47: Date when the TAC is reached for the four main species (month, numbered from 0 to 11, 12 meaning not reached). Boxes display the variability associated to inter-annual variations and fisher's behavior assumptions.

3.1.2.2.2 Long term results

The implementation of the LO produces long-term benefits both to the fish populations and the fleets. Biological impact is mainly apparent on Sole and Cod with a 20% and 13% increase in biomass respectively (Figure 2.3.5). Benefits also propagate to non-regulated stocks such as red mullet (+17%), squids and cuttlefish, although the results should be carefully interpreted given the high variability of these stocks' dynamics (recruitment and spatial distribution) that could not be accounted for in the model.

The LO also has an impact on population and catch age structures. Despite a constant recruitment, the early stop of the season causes a more important decrease in young fish catches than on bigger ones. It is particularly striking for Cod and Sole which display a -15% and -10% reduction in older fish (respectively) against -50% and 60% for age 1 fish over the last five years of simulation. The changes in population age structure consist in a displacement to the right of the distribution and are mostly remarkable for sole.

As for economic benefits, annual revenues after 10 years of LO implementation are 5% higher than in the base case scenario. The benefits mainly arise from higher sole revenues, since landed values for the other target species show no or negative change. Over the fifteen years of simulation though, LO produces lower revenues than DAU of about 7% (Figure 50)

Figure 48: Biomass in the last year of simulation with the LO (green) and LO-deMinimis (blue) scenarios relative to the DAU scenario. Arrows represent the standard deviation of the mean when fleet opportunism is varied.

Figure 49: Catch at age for Cod, Plaice, Sole and Whiting in the last 5 years of simulation with the LO scenario relatively to the DAU scenario.

Figure 50: **left panel** Average cumulated revenues per scenario (LO: purple, LO-Exemption1: green, LO-Exemption2: blue) relative to the DAU scenario. Arrows represent the standard deviation of the mean when fleet opportunism is varied. **Right panel**: Evolution of the average relative revenues of the fishery in LO (purple), LO-exemption1 (green) and LO-exemption2 (blue) scenarios compared to the DAU scenario. Shaded areas represent the standard deviation of the mean when fleet opportunism is varied.

3.1.2.2.3 Short term results

Simulations indicate that difficulties are expected for the fleets during the first 9 years of implementation with a temporary decrease in their annual revenues of about 20% compared to the DAU scenario (Figure 50). This corresponds to the time needed for Sole revenues to increase enough to compensate for the losses of other species.

3.1.2.2.4 Impact of exemption scenarios

Exemptions drastically reduce the benefits of the LO on population biomasses. Exemption 2 (based on catch share at the stock scale) in particular produces lower biomasses of Cod, red mullet and scallops than the DAU scenarios. It also generates important discards of sole, respectively a half and a third of the quantity obtained in the DAU scenarios. This is due to the report of the effort on métiers targeting these species. Conversely it has positive impacts on revenues with increases of up to 10% compared to DAU over the 15 years of simulation.

3.1.2.2.5 Avoidance strategies

Whiting closures for trawlers

Although whiting was not a choke species in the current simulations, variations in recruitment are expected to occur and possibly make the quota limiting. Two strategies were therefore

proposed to limit catches of whiting. Both are successful in diminishing catches of whiting, however the closure in Q1 allows a larger decrease in catch of whiting (-20%) for only 3% loss of revenues on the other species, mainly on cephalopods (Figure 51).

Figure 51: Average relative change in trawler catch per species over the simulation period with the whiting avoidance scenarios (Lo-avoid_WHG_Q1 in red, and LO-avoid_WHG_Q23 in green) compared to the LO scenario. Arrows represent the standard deviation of the mean when opportunism is varied.

Sole closure for trawlers

The avoidance strategy for sole did not show the expected effects. Indeed, the objective is a significant decrease in sole catches with maintenance of the catch level for the other species. Here however catch of sole are identical but a significant decrease in catch of whiting, red mullet and cod (-3 to -7%) are observed for trawlers. On the positive side however, the fishing mortality is displaced toward older individuals while global revenues are maintained (Figure 52). Although not directly relevant to mitigate the impact of the LO, this scenario is interesting to promote a more sustainable exploitation of the sole stock.

Figure 52: Relative change in sole fishing mortality at age in the sole avoidance scenario relative to the LO scenario.

3.1.2.3 Discussion, conclusions and perspectives

The participatory approach allowed drawing conclusions on the likely impact of the LO on the demersal fishery in the EEC. It confirmed expectations that quotas may not be limiting given the current stock conditions and if the uplifts correspond to the discard rates. The choke on sole was somehow unexpected as the discards are estimated to be quite low (9%) by the ICES working group.

The current parameterization assumes a global quota for French fleets when it is in fact distributed among fisher organizations. The choke effect might consequently be less important as it may concern only a portion of the fleet. The relationships with POs consolidated during the project should enable an easier access to this type of information in the future and quota per PO to be implemented in simulations.

Results evidenced the limited risk of choke for the species considered in the study and some opportunities to avoid unwanted catch. However recent concerns emerged regarding other species, which are important by-catch in the trawler fishery such as rays and mackerel. The wide distribution and relatively less informed dynamics of these species make it difficult to envision adding them to the model explicitly. An alternative would rather be to evaluate the impact of various choke dates attributed to these stocks and avoidance strategies on the fisheries dynamics. Similarly, further scenarios including fuel price increase and recruitment failures, or peaks would help evaluate the robustness of fishery's performances to the LO in an uncertain context.

3.1.3 Osmose

Fishers' response must be cautiously examined to anticipate any undesirable effects of the landing obligation (Fulton et al., 2011). Fleet dynamics modelling can provide answers to forecasting short-term fishers' behaviour (see Van Putten et al., 2012 for a review). One of the hypotheses used to model fishers' behaviour is that they will aim at maximizing their global revenue (Gordon, 1953). In a landing obligation context, they will thus try to reach the highest revenue possible without exceeding the quotas of

concerned species and keep fishing as long as they can throughout the year. Some studies tried to predict the impact of a discard ban on fishers' revenue (e.g. Condie et al., 2013) or ecosystems (e.g. Heath et al., 2014) with very simple assumptions on the fishers' reaction to the ban. On the other side, the reaction of fishers to a discard ban has been predicted by Batsleer et al. (2013), but they worked with the assumption that availability of fish in an area was independent of the fishing pressure, thus ignoring any ecological impact of fishers' activity. Here we aim at estimating the medium-term effects of a discard ban by modelling the interaction between fishers and ecosystem, and their co-evolution in a landing obligation context.

This study addresses the question by coupling a tropho-dynamic multispecies model, OSMOSE (Object-oriented Simulator of Marine Ecosystems Exploitation; Shin and Cury, 2001; 2004), and a fleet dynamic model, the Dynamic State Variable Model (DSVM; Houston and McNamara, 1999; Clark and Mangel, 2000) particularly adapted to forecast new management regimes (van Putten et al., 2012), and investigate the long-term changes on ecosystem and fisheries dynamics in the Eastern English Channel (EEC). To achieve this, a focus was made on exclusive French bottom otter trawlers (OTB) longer than or equal to 18m. This fleet will be highly impacted by the landing obligation due to their high species diversity found in catches (Marchal, 2008; ICES, 2017), and it is also one of the main fleets in the EEC (Carpentier et al., 2009). In this study we will only examine the spatio-temporal avoidance and not gear or selectivity improvements. The performances of current management regime and of the landing obligation on ecosystem health and fishers are evaluated and compared using different indicators such as species' biomasses, size spectra and fishers' revenue.

3.1.3.1 Material and methods

OSMOSE is a multispecies, spatially-explicit, individual-based model. It models a community of fish species (including cephalopods), explicitly representing their full life cycle, from eggs to adults. Each species is decomposed into super-individuals, corresponding to groups of individuals with common characteristics, e.g., species, size, age, spatial location and trophic level. OSMOSE is a tropho-dynamic model, meaning that the fish community fluctuations are led by predation and competition. Predation in OSMOSE is opportunistic and based on two key prerequisites: spatio-temporal co-occurrence and size suitability of a prey for a predator, without a priori diet setting.

The current study is mostly based on an existing EEC configuration (Travers-Trolet et al., submitted), with few adaptations before being coupled with a fleet dynamics module. The model is composed of 15 species representing the major part of the 2008-2015 biomass and catches: lesser-spotted dogfish (*Scyliorhinus canicula*), red mullet (*Mullus surmuletus*), pouting (*Trisopterus luscus*), poor cod (*Trisopterus minutus*), cod (*Gadus morhua*), mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*), horse mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*), sole (*Solea solea*), plaice (*Pleuronectes platessa*), whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*), dragonets (*Callionymus lyra*), sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*), herring (*Clupea harengus*), squids (*Loligo spp*) and cuttlefish (*Sepia officinalis*).

Every time step (here two weeks), each super-individual can move into a square of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ in the 2-dimensional grid representing EEC, following either distribution maps or foraging random walk. Then, super-individuals interact between themselves and with their local environment following different processes (Figure 53). Different mortalities can affect a super-individual: predation by other super-individuals, starvation, fishing, other natural mortalities (i.e. due to diseases or non-modelled organisms

such as other fish or mammals) and even an approximation of the senescence if the super-individual exceeds the maximum longevity for the species. On the other side, a super-individual can predate other super-individuals but also plankton and/or benthic invertebrate groups (the biomass fields of these prey being provided by an ECO-MARS-3D biogeochemical model). Depending on the success of predation, i.e. the amount of food eaten compared to maintenance requirements, super-individuals undergo starvation mortality or variable growth. Finally the reproduction process operates before the end of the time step. The production of new super-individuals (i.e. eggs) depends on the spawning stock biomass, the relative fecundity and seasonality of spawning.

Figure 53: Processes undertaken by a super-individual during a 2-weeks time step : 1) movement of individual in a 2D grid either driven by input maps or due to random walk; 2) interactions and mortalities (3): explicit predation upon other super-individuals present in the same cell and upon LTL groups with associated predation for the prey groups, as well as fishing mortality and additional natural mortality; 4) growth and 5) reproduction which creates new super-individuals “eggs” for the next time step (source, Travers-Trolet et al., submitted).

The model is adapted to forecast the impact of some fisheries management measures (e.g. Marine Protected Areas with the use of spatial fishing mortality rates), but due to the absence of explicit discards and fleet dynamics in previous versions of the model, some changes had to be done to evaluate the effect of the landing obligation on French OTB. These improvements of the exploitation module of the OSMOSE model are done by coupling a fleet-dynamics model, DSVM (Dynamic State Variable Model), with the current OSMOSE model.

During a simulation the total fishing mortality applied to each species in OSMOSE is decomposed into a fraction representing fishing mortality attributed to the simulated fleet (F_{DSVM} for French OTB) and

another fishing mortality (F_{others}) corresponding to the other French fleets and all other countries impacting these stocks. The model developed here is mostly derived from models developed by Poos et al. (2009) and Batsleer et al. (2013), in which individual fishers have a set of choices to select simultaneously at each time step: i) to go out fishing in a particular fishing ground or to stay in their home port, and ii) to discard or not a part of their catches in order to maximize their profit at the end of the year.

French large OTB are also a priori easier to model than smaller vessels because their activity covers a wider part of the EEC, more in adequacy with spatial species distributions represented in the OSMOSE model than coastal fleets. The number of vessels explicitly modelled is spread over the two main ports for the modelled fleet (i.e. corresponding to more than 73% of French OTB fishing effort in hours in EEC in 2008-2015), for a total of 43 vessels in Boulogne-sur-Mer and 23 vessels in Port-en-Bessin.

Fishers' choices (fishing ground and discard strategy) at each time step are evaluated in order to maximize their annual realized net revenue, defined as the total quantity landed of each species weighted by each species price plus additional revenues and minus variable fishing costs, a very high fine for overshooting his individual quota and a very high fine for discarding fish if existing. The fishing operation takes into account different components: the abundance of each super-individual, the species catchability, the length-based selectivity, the time dedicated to fishing (versus travel), a seasonal effort, and a random term around the past simulated biomass of species. Once total catches are computed, the landings and discards fractions are separated for quota-regulated species according to discarding options. The different choices are either discarding everything, discarding only the undersized fish, discarding only the legal-sized fish, or discarding nothing. For species not regulated by quota in the model, all the catches are assumed to be landed.

Evaluation of fishers' possible choices is realized through backward calculation, the core of DSVM. It consists of computing all fishing options fishers will have at each moment of the year, and assessing their relative interest according to their cumulated landings of quota-regulated species at this moment of the year. It is based on fishers' revenues, landings and costs perception, and provides a matrix of optimal choices for fishing location and discarding options, containing every state a fisher can encounter at each time step of the year. Individual variability of fishers' behaviour was included through the assumption that they do not always make the optimal choice to optimize their annual net revenue, due to an imperfect knowledge of the optimal choice and the influence of their own tradition. Further details about the model can be found in Bourdaud (2018).

For computation reasons, only cod and whiting were considered to be regulated by quota here, as they are the most important species under TAC for French OTB in EEC, and don't have any survivability exemption (EC, 2016). The other 13 species considered in the model are not constrained by quota limitation, even if some of them are currently TAC species. Quotas are updated every five years from Harvest Control Rules (HCR) and values of stock biomass, and are divided into the number of vessels to obtain individual quotas that will be used for the computation of optimal choices.

As the fleet dynamics module is computer-time-consuming, the model is first run 70 years without DSVM to let the ecosystem stabilize (thereafter named "spin-up") and be no longer driven by the model

initialization. Calibration of the unknown parameters of this model is performed in two main phases. The first one allows the estimation of a set of biological parameters and corresponds to the spin-up time needed for the ecosystem to reach a stable state. The second phase of the calibration allowed to estimate species catchabilities, needed for simulating fleet dynamics, and was therefore realized with DSVM activated for an additional 20 years after spin-up.

A reference scenario, or “Business as usual” (BaU) scenario, is run with a discards fine equal to 0 €, meaning that fishers are allowed to discard regulated species as much as they want without overshooting their landing quota. For the landing obligation (LO) scenario, an extremely high value is tested to mimic the reality of European landing obligation, i.e. a fisher can't go fishing anymore if he exceeds his catch quota. The impact of the management scenarios are compared for economic and biological compartments. Among the 90 years simulated, only an average over the last 20 years, i.e. with dynamic fleets, are presented. Furthermore results are computed from the average of 30 run replicates for each scenario, due to the stochastic nature of OSMOSE.

3.1.3.2 Results

3.1.3.2.1 Impact of the scenarios on fishers' effort distribution

Annual fishing effort resulting from the individual choices of the fishers is mainly distributed offshore in the center of the EEC, with two patches in front of Boulogne-sur-Mer (from vessels coming from this port) and Port-en-Bessin (corresponding to vessels coming from both ports) in the BaU scenario (Figure 53A). When LO is implemented, most of the fishing effort is concentrated offshore in the western part of EEC, while fishing effort in front of Boulogne-sur-Mer strongly decreased as vessels from this port moved westwards (Figure 54B). With the LO, both ports display a similar fishing effort distribution, contrary to the BaU situation.

Figure

Figure 54: Mean annual relative distribution of fishing effort operated by exclusive bottom trawlers in Eastern English Channel with A) “Business as Usual” and B) Landing Obligation scenarios. “X” represents a null value.

At each time step, there is always a proportion of less than 1% of fishers on average who choose to stay at port in the BaU scenario (Figure 55). In the LO scenario, more fishers chose to stay at port. During the first two months of the year, about 20% of fishers choose to stay in their home port, and this proportion

dropped to remain stable between 1% and 3% until the last two weeks of the year when 7% of fishers stayed in port. For both ports the winter pattern is similar, but all the fishers from Port-en-Bessin go fishing from April to October, contrary to a part of fishers from Boulogne-sur-Mer.

Figure 55: Mean percentage of “not to go fishing” choices for exclusive bottom trawlers operating in the Eastern English Channel with “Business as Usual” (dashed line) and Landing Obligation (full line) scenarios. Standard deviations are represented in grey.

3.1.3.2.2 Impact of the scenarios on fishers’ catches

In comparison to the BaU scenario, landings realized by fishers under LO were more than doubled for whiting and cod on average (Figure 56). Landings slightly increased with LO also for squids and cuttlefish, while there were moderate decreases for horse mackerel and mackerel, and more severe ones concerning lesser-spotted dogfish, red mullet, pouting, sole, plaice, herring and sardine.

Figure 56: Relative changes in landings (averaged over the last 20 simulated years) of exclusive bottom otter trawlers in the Eastern English Channel with the Landing Obligation scenario in comparison to the “Business as Usual” scenario. Minimum and maximum simulated landings are represented by the short segments. Grey boxes represent Q1, median and Q3 ranges of simulated landings, over 30 replicates. Dashed line represents the basal value of median landings in the “Business as Usual” scenario.

3.1.3.2.3 Impact of the scenarios on fishers' revenue

The effects on the revenues of exclusive bottom otter trawlers of the landing obligation compared to BaU are shown in Figure 57. Revenues exhibited on average a 8.3% decrease from the beginning to the end of the 20 years simulated with the BaU scenario. The decrease is the most pronounced after 5-10 years of simulation and the revenue seems to stabilize during last ten years. With the LO implemented, fishers' revenues were stable during the first ten years, 2.9% lower than in the base line BaU scenario on average, with a high variability among replicates but increased during the last ten years to reach 7% increase above the base line BaU scenario at the end of the 20 years. During the last five years, fishers' average revenue is 15.3% higher with the LO than with the BaU scenario. The trends of revenues are similar for both ports.

Figure 57: Relative changes of the revenue of exclusive bottom otter trawlers in Eastern English Channel with "Business as Usual" (full line) and Landing Obligation (dashed line) scenarios. Standard deviations are represented in grey.

3.1.3.2.4 Impact of the landing obligation on EEC ecosystem

Four size or trophic ecosystem indicators were compared between the BaU and LO scenarios: the slope of the abundance size spectra, the Large Fish Indicator (LFI), the Mean Maximum Length (MML) and the Marine Trophic Index (MTI). LFI and MTI exhibited highly similar values in both scenarios. The slope of the size spectra was slightly steeper in the BaU scenario than in the LO one, and MML was slightly lower when the LO was implemented than in the BaU scenario. This small change of size-structure towards more smaller fish and/or less larger fish are not clearly explained by change of species biomass. When LO is implemented, the biomass of the large species lesser-spotted dogfish decreased by 75% in comparison to the BaU situation, while it was approximately three times higher for whiting and twice higher for cod, two other large species. Concerning the other species, variations were +/- 20% beyond the base line value according to the species. The biomasses of pouting, sole, plaice, horse mackerel and mackerel decreased, while they expanded for, dragonet and cuttlefish and remained stable for red mullet, herring, sardine and squids.

3.1.3.3 Discussion

When the LO is implemented, exclusive bottom otter trawlers exhibited strong changes in their fishing effort distribution. Even if tradition partly drives their choice, they moved away from their traditional fishing grounds, but also partly limited their fishing effort, particularly during winter. This shift of effort

distribution resulted from the necessity for fishers to avoid areas where they faced a risk to exceed their quota when they were able to discard in the BaU scenario. The fact that the reduction of fishing activity mostly occurred during the first quarter of the year demonstrated that fishers have chosen to use their quota preferably towards the end of the year. This is *a priori* due to a combination of several parameters. First, the prices of quota-regulated species, such as whiting and cod, are higher in the last quarter. Second, other species composing their landing profile, e.g., cuttlefish, one of the main commercial species in the EEC (Gras et al., 2014), are increasingly accessible in the second part of the year (Bourdaud et al., 2018). Fishers perhaps also had to deal with the fact that winter is the main season for discards in EEC, especially for whiting (Viðarsson et al., 2016). This quota reservation at the beginning of the year is typically a result on fishers' behaviour that can only be predicted by the DSVM. It is noteworthy that the fishing effort reallocation is more strongly impacting trawlers from Boulogne-sur-Mer in their fishing habits and, as they had to move further offshore to avoid economically risky fishing grounds.

According to the simulations, total catches of whiting and cod were indeed strongly reduced during the first years of the simulations, mostly due to the reallocation of fishing effort. From this perspective, the LO seems to reach the goal of reducing fishing mortality for both whiting, and stabilizing the one for cod, without other incentives than quota limitation and landing taxes. These events had consequences for the revenues of fishers, which were slightly reduced in the first ten years compared to the BaU scenario, but reached higher levels in the last ten years. This increase is mainly caused by the higher landings of whiting and cod, allowed by the increase of quotas, themselves following the increase of their biomass. Short-term consequences of a LO for fishers were explored in several models and our results corroborated their findings. Our results exhibited an inversion of the economic profitability for fishers at the medium-term (20 years) simulated, which was absent from these other models, due to the fact that trophic interactions and management evolution were together accounted for in the coupling of OSMOSE and DSVM. At the ecosystem level, no improvement could be evidenced. Clearly our results demonstrated that with the new policy, an improvement of state is highly directed on whiting and cod, while the main part of other species' biomasses was lower in the medium-term with the LO than with the BaU scenario. For most species, the implementation of the LO directly induced a reduction of the catches, due to the fishing effort reallocation. Cod are high trophic level predators in the EEC, and their change in biomass (here their stabilization) has consequences on the mortality by predation exerted on a majority of potential preys in the ecosystem (Worm and Myers, 2003; Frank et al., 2005). Our results seemed to indicate that these managed stocks are the main levers of change in the community, as many small species' biomasses decrease while most of these did not suffer higher fishing mortalities.

3.2 Bay of Biscay

Aiming at simulating the implementation of the LO in a more realistic way, results of a bioeconomic model have been used to drive the forward simulations with EwE, to analyze the status of the Bay of Biscay ecosystem in the short-medium term (from 2013 to 2024). Two scenarios have been simulated, the baseline being the Discards as Usual scenario (DaU) where the situation basically continues equal to the last three years of the modelled period. The alternative scenario is the Landing Obligation scenario (LO), where the regulation is assumed to be fully implemented in 2018.

The fishery simulations have then been performed using FLBEIA (Garcia et al., 2016) which simulates the reaction of the fishing firms to the management in place. The fishing mortalities of the fishing stocks modelled the reaction of the fleet to the two scenarios (LO and DaU), following the main management regulations in place (mainly a system of TACs and quotas). The inputs and outputs from the specific conditioning of the FLBEIA can be seen in Prellezo et al. (2016) and also delivered in WP2 of DiscardLess. The F trajectories obtained from FLBEIA have been used in Ecosim to drive the forward simulations for the two scenarios described above. In particular the F trajectories used are those referred to the species affected by the LO in this CS and for which an analytical assessment exists: hake and megrim (Figure 58).

The ecosystem model used is the one described above, but using the previous version of EwE, where some tricks need to be used to adequately handle discards in Ecosim. Actually, in EwE version 6.5, distinguishing between discards and landings in the temporary dynamic module Ecosim was not possible, and to solve this situation, each of the fleets were split in two subfleets, one targeting landings and the other one targeting discards. This allowed us to solve the problem and continue with the work in the time EwE 6.6 was not available yet.

The DaU scenario always represents the situation of the last years before the implementation of the landing obligation. Here existing management rules based on the F_{MSY} target (or the last three years average F value if F_{MSY} is not defined) have been used for projecting the population forward in the short term. The LO scenario, represents the current situation where the implementation of the LO is already in place for some of the fleets and species considered in this study.

Figure 58: Observed and simulated fishing mortalities (F) of hake and megrim. Source Prellezo et al (2016).

The DaU scenario the simulation is based on having the quota of hake (the species driving the fishery) as the one that is going to limit the effort level. If any of the others' quotas are exceeded, this excess has to be discarded.

The LO scenario assumes full implementation of the LO from 2018 to 2024 without any exemption or flexibility to the no discard rule. The implementation of this scenario is based on considering that the effort of this metier cannot be increased once the quota share of the first species is reached.

In both scenarios there is a period not observed (at the time in where the conditioning was decided to be finished) but that has to be simulated, the period that goes 2014 to 2017. In this period we assume that LO has not been entering into force (for simplicity this common period is used for all the stocks and fleets).

One of the requirements for sharing data between models is the compatibility of the data used in both approaches. Therefore, the main input data for the two models (Ecosim EwE and FLBEIA) from the observed period (1996-2013) comes from the same sources. The fishing mortalities applied to the different stocks comes from the same sources (ICES Stock Assessment Database, 2016/2. ICES, Copenhagen). Discard data are also the same, those coming from the different ICES working groups when available.

The relative effect of the landing obligation

In terms of the overall characteristics of the ecosystem three indices have been analyzed: The Total System Throughput (TST), Finn's cycling index (FCI) and Trophic level of the catches (TLC) indices, results in terms of % of change between scenarios are shown in Figure 59.

For the case of the TST its relative value of comparing LO with DaU has a positive trend. It implies that the value of this index with LO is higher than the value without it (DaU). It is especially remarkable the difference of the last three years simulated where in average the index is a 0.4% higher in the LO scenario than in the DaU scenario. Considering this change with the overall change from 1996 obtained from the Ecopath model, the overall change will be a decrease of 1.2% in the case of LO scenario and of 1.6% in the case of DaU scenario. This implies that the main change has occurred due to the dynamic evolution of the ecosystem and that the LO is likely to increase this value.

For the case of FCI we have the opposite result. It implies that under the LO scenario less detritus is retained within the system than in the no LO scenario (0.35%). It implies that the system is slightly less resilient or in other words that the lower recycling under LO will reduce the speed of eliminating the effects of the perturbations from the system.

If finally we look at the mean trophic level of the catches in the last three years of the evolution the evolution from 1996 to the last three years of the simulation this value is likely to increase in 1.5% comparing with the DaU scenario. This change will be of 1.4% if it is compared with the LO scenario implying that difference between both is lower than 0.1%. In other words, the trophic average value of the catches is not likely to change.

In Figure 60, it is shown how seabirds and carnivorous benthic invertebrates are likely to be those suffering from the LO, with an overall biomass in the last three years of the simulation a 10% lower with LO than without LO. On the contrary we have "winners" such as hake that will increase their overall abundance.

Figure 59: Relative change of TST, FCI and TLc values between the DaU and the LO scenarios.

Figure 60: Winners and losers by group of species for the last three year of the scenario

3.3 North Sea

3.3.1 An analysis of demersal discards by fleet in the North Sea affected by the Landing Obligation

3.3.1.1 Introduction

Discarding is a common practice in fisheries, especially those targeting mixed demersal species with non-selective gears such as trawls. Fish are discarded for a variety of reasons that include fish caught below marketable size, low value species or catch limits that prevent fish being retained. It is a generally held view that discarding, for whatever reason, is wasteful and not an efficient use of a valuable resource. In an effort to address public concern about discarding the European Union introduced the Landing Obligation (LO) (EU, 2013) which requires fishing vessels to retain and land all species in the catch that are subject to quota management. This new regulation is likely to have far reaching effects on the operation of many fisheries as estimates of discard rates in the North Sea suggest approximately 35% of all biomass caught in the demersal fisheries is discarded (Heath and Cook, 2015). Eliminating discards through an obligation to land all fish that are caught can broadly be met in two very different ways. Either the fish that were previously discarded are brought back to port and landed, or fishing practices change to avoid catching the “unwanted” catch. In the first of these scenarios, “discards landed” (DL) the catch remains the same except that biomass previously returned to the sea is disposed of ashore, while in the second scenario “discards avoided” (DA), the catch is potentially much reduced and the biomass previously returned to the sea dead (since most fish do not survive being caught) now remains in the sea alive. In the DL case the fishing mortality on the stocks is unchanged, while in the DA case such mortality is likely to be greatly reduced on the smaller and younger fish.

In evaluating the consequences of these scenarios it is convenient to distinguish between the direct and immediate effects on stocks that result from reduced exploitation rates and the longer term effects that arise from changes in the relative abundance of different species due to this lower mortality. The longer term effects might be considered “ecosystem effects” since they arise from the interaction between species and the change in energy flows through the system. In this paper we consider direct effects of the change in fishing mortality rate that arise from the DA scenario and use single species population models to evaluate stocks under differing fishing assumptions. The DL case is less significant in this instance since there is no change to the fishing mortality rate and the consequences of this scenario arise through ecosystem effects caused by the disposal of dead biomass. Such effects require the use of ecosystem models that can account for species interactions and other biological factors. Clearly the failure to account for ecosystem effects in single species models is a significant limitation. However, this drawback has to be set against the ease of parameterisation and greater model robustness that single species models can offer while still providing some insight into population change.

Discards are by their nature difficult to observe since they occur during fishing operations. Observer programmes have been established to monitor discards and in recent years estimates have become available for an increasing number of species (EC 2008). However, most of the longer time series of discard estimates are restricted to a few well studied species such as cod, haddock, whiting plaice and sole. Similarly, while fully age-structured population models have been developed for stock assessment of these major species (e.g. Nielsen and Berg, 2014), many of the minor species that are caught in these fisheries are not assessed or are assessed using methods that do not use population models amenable to

investigate alternative fishing scenarios. In order to address the DA case it is necessary to construct population models for all species to investigate scenarios. While models already exist for some of the major species referred to above, here we develop common modelling framework for all species to avoid variability in approach that may lead to inconsistent results arising from differing methodologies. In particular we draw on the work of Heath and Cook (2015) and Cook and Heath (2018) who distinguish between size based discarding and non-selective “bulk” discarding. By modelling the discard process in this way it is possible to make estimates of quantities of minor species that are discarded where direct observations are limited or absent. Moreover, incorporating this process into a full population model provides a means of investigating population dynamics under different assumptions about discarding behaviour.

In conventional ICES stock assessments of the main species where discards are explicitly accounted for, age structured population models readily accommodate size based discarding through estimates of fleet selectivity on younger fish. Unfortunately, for most species age structured data are not available and building fully age structured population models is not possible. The model developed by Cook and Heath (2018) considers population numbers only, without either size or age being explicitly included and while useful for describing whole population dynamics is unable to simulate changes in selectivity that will arise in the DA scenario. To overcome this problem their model is elaborated to account for size with a specific parameter quantifying the selectivity on fish of discard size. Changing this parameter allows the investigation of alternative selectivity scenarios.

3.3.1.2 Data

Survey data: The longest running and most comprehensive survey of demersal fish in the North Sea is the International Bottom Trawl Survey (IBTS). The survey covers all of ICES Sub-area 4 (North Sea) and Division 3a (Skagerrak) using a standardised high headline otter trawl, the “GOV”. Multiple research vessels sample each 30x30 km statistical rectangle at least twice in the period January-March each year with a 30 or 60 minute tow. Sampling protocols are generally considered to have been standardised since 1983 (ICES 2015b) and this forms the base year for the analysis presented here. The data were downloaded from the ICES DATRAS data centre (<http://www.ices.dk/marine-data/data-portals/Pages/DATRAS.aspx>). We extracted data on number at length to calculate an overall mean number per hour and an associated length distribution for each species each year for the period 1983-2015. This allowed the calculation of the associated annual mean weight of individual fish in a size category (i.e. the mean weight averaged over all length bins in a size class). Length to weight conversions were carried out using standard relationships for the North Sea given in Coull et al (1989). In addition, the IBTS data contain estimates of maturity which we used to obtain the length at which 75% of fish were mature in order to be able to calculate spawning stock biomass. The maturity data are sporadic but provide the best available information on maturity for the area, so for each species we aggregated the data across all years to obtain a mean value for the whole period.

In the case of haddock, saithe, anglerfish and megrim the ICES assessment includes ICES Division 6a (West of Scotland). In order to obtain a survey index consistent with this assessment unit we included the Scottish first quarter survey data with the IBTS data to calculate an abundance index for the combined area. The Scottish survey uses the same sampling protocol as the IBTS and takes place at the same time of year and was therefore treated simply as an extension of the North Sea survey. Hake in the North Sea

are included in the “Northern” stock which covers a wide area. We used only North Sea catches and survey data in the analysis and therefore does not cover the whole stock.

Landings and discard data: Official statistics on the total annual landed weights of all species, by all nations engaged in fisheries in North Sea, between 1983 and 2015 were accessed from the FAO/ICES FishSTAT dataset (accessed 31/03/2016). In some cases species were aggregated into broader taxonomic groups to accommodate national and temporal differences in the way species were recorded. These were “mulletts” (Mugilidae), “skates and rays” (Rajidae) and “tub and red gurnards” (Chelidonichthys cuculus and Chelidonichtys lucernus, Triglidae). Where ICES assessment working group estimates of landings differed from the official landings, the working group values were used and taken from ICES 2015b or ICES 2015c in the case of anglerfish and megrim. Discard data, where available, were taken from the ICES assessment working group reports ICES 2015b and ICES 2015c. Data on the effective minimum landing sizes (EMLS) of fish were taken from Heath and Cook (2015).

Fleet data: STECF has compiled data by gear and species giving landings and discards for recent years. These data were provided by Marine Scotland.

Species chosen: We selected all species, or groups of species, that had a coherent time series of landings data and that were routinely sampled in the IBTS survey. The principal limitation was the landings data where official records frequently do not accurately identify species or geographical area. A full list of the 25 species considered is given in Table 11.

3.3.1.3 Models

For convenience, in order to consider discards explicitly, we model the population of fish in the sea as three size categories, recruits, discard sized and landing sized fish. The population model equations are set out in Table 12. For the discard sized fish, a proportion will remain in this size category each year but decline due to mortality. Those that remain will be augmented by a proportion of new recruits each year (equation T2.1). The fishing mortality on this category is modified by a parameter, s , that expresses relative selectivity compared to landing sized fish.

The landing sized fish will also decline according to fishing mortality but will be augmented by survivors of fish growing from the discard sized category and a proportion of the recruits (equation T2.2). We assume that recruitment is a lognormally distributed random variable and that fishing mortality follows a random walk (equations T2.3 and T2.4).

The observed quantities, catches, landings and discards are related to the population as set out in Table 13, equations T3.1-T3.3 and are based on the standard Baranov catch equation. Discards are the sum of fish of discard size and a proportion of the landing size fish that are discarded due to factors such as low value or quota limits. The survey index is assumed to be proportional to the population in the sea (equations T3.4).

The core population model outlined above forms the basis for projections. In order to consider discarding by fleet in modelled scenarios the selectivity parameter, s , is partitioned into fleet specific values (equation T4.1 in Table 14) and fishing mortality is similarly distributed by fleet (equation T4.2). The fleet specific catches can then be calculated using standard Baranov equations T4.3 while total stock biomass (TSB) is calculated directly as the weighted sum of the numbers of fish in each size category. It is

assumed that mean weight in the total stock is an indicator of the proportion of mature biomass since if this increases, the proportion of larger fish must be higher and these are more likely to be mature. This can be used to estimate the spawning stock biomass as described in equations T4.4-4.7.

3.3.1.4 Methods

In order to parameterise the model for projection scenarios, the population model described in Table 12 and Table 13 was fit to landings and IBTS survey indices. Where discard data were available these are also included as observations in the fitting procedure. The survey indices were derived as described in Cook and Heath (2018) except that separate indices were calculated for each size category. The size split was made on the basis of the effective minimum landing size (EMLS) and is given in Table 11. Natural mortality, M , was assumed known and derived from the Lorenzen (1996) relationship with weight. M was scaled as described in Cook and Heath (2018) to the species specific mean values given in Table 11.

Model parameters were estimated using the R package “rstan” (Carpenter et al 2017) which uses MCMC to derive posterior distributions of the quantities of interest. The error assumptions for the observations are given in Table 15 and are all lognormal. Prior distributions on the parameters are shown in Table 16. For most, priors were uniform or log uniform. For the prior on the bulk discarding proportion, Q , a beta distribution was used with a mean of 0.15 for high value species or a mean of 0.4 for low values species. The initial value for fishing mortality was given a lognormal prior with a mean of $\log(0.6)$ which reflects a typical value estimated for North Sea demersal species in ICES assessment for the start year of 1983.

The model simulations were run with four MCMC chains with a minimum length of 2 million iterations and a burn in period of 1 million. Samples were thinned by a factor of 500. For some species the Rhat statistic indicated inadequate convergence and for these the chain length was increased to 10 million to ensure Rhat reached 1.

The mean parameter values from the model fit in the most recent 5 years were used as the basis for forward projections under different scenarios. The estimated discard selectivity parameter, s , was partitioned according to equation T4.1 using observed values of discards and landings by fleet from the STECF data in the last five years. The same data were used to partition total fishing mortality to fleet level.

The proportion mature was calculated from survey data using the same procedure as described in Cook and Heath (2018) where a length-maturity ogive derived from IBTS data was applied to the survey length frequencies. The parameters in equation T4.6 were then estimated from the historical IBTS data using logit regression of the proportion mature on mean weight in the stock as calculated from the survey length frequencies.

The projections were run for a time horizon of 50 years using the population model described in Tables 2-4. Parameters were fixed except for recruitment which was modelled as a stochastic variable drawn from a lognormal distribution as estimated from the model fit. For each scenario, 500 replicates were carried out in order to obtain distributions of landings, discards and stock biomass. Two main scenarios were considered. These were:

1. Base case. Fishing mortality was held at the value for the most recent 5 years estimated from fitting the model to historical data. This represents “business as usual”.
2. DA. The selectivity parameter was set to zero for all species to simulate “discards avoided”.

In addition to the scenarios, a sensitivity analysis was performed for the base case. In this analysis elasticities were calculated for landings, discards and stock biomass for a 10% change in discard selectivity or fleet effort. The elasticities, Δ , were defined for a response variable y as:

$$\Delta(y) = \frac{y' - y}{y}$$

Where y is the value of the response value in the base case and y' is the value when effort or selectivity are disturbed.

3.3.1.5 Results

The results of fitting the model to each stock are summarised in Appendix A which shows the fit to the data and the posterior distributions of critical parameters. Typically the landings data are fitted most closely. In most cases the discard data, where available, are well fitted with grey gurnard as an exception. The survey data are generally fitted well but for the less abundant species, the data are very variable the model does not detect any consistent population signal. In some cases the survey index of discard size fish is very low (e.g. pollack) and the model is unable to find any information in the data.

The posterior distributions of the selectivity parameter, which measures selectivity of discard sized fish relative to landings sized fish, tend to be very wide and in some cases close to the (uniform) prior distribution indicating that for these species the data offer weak information on the parameter (e.g. saithe). This results in a default value close to 0.5. However for many species the distribution shows a clear mode including cod, haddock, common dab, plaice and sole, all species that make large contributions to the total discard weight in the North Sea.

Where ICES assessments of the stocks exist, the model results follow the same trend in fishing mortality and SSB though the scale may differ somewhat (Figure A. 5, Figure A. 9, Figure A. 13, Figure A. 15, Figure A. 18, Figure A. 19, Figure A. 23). The scale difference is not surprising given different assumptions about natural mortality and the fact the fishing mortality from the model described here is an abundance weighted mean over all size groups rather than unweighted arithmetic mean over selected ages as used by ICES. The model estimates of fishing mortality tend to be lower than ICES values and this would be expected given the higher abundance of smaller fish that weight the mean value toward fish of lower selectivity.

Table 17 gives the parameter values derived from the model fit used in the projections. These represent a five year mean of the most recent values in the historical time series to form the baseline for projection.

The relationships between the proportion mature and mean weight in the stock used in the projections are shown in Figure 61. In most cases there is a strong positive relationship. In a few species including saithe, tusk and flounder there is no relationship and the fitted regression is effectively flat. As the regression effectively predicts a constant proportion mature for all mean weights, this was nevertheless used in the projections. For skates and rays, as these are a mixture of species, a single maturity proportion is not meaningful and the estimated biomass is therefore the total biomass.

The sensitivity analyses when either selectivity or effort is disturbed by 10% are summarised in Figure 62 and Figure 63. Most of the sensitivity is apparent in fleets BT2, TR1 and TR2 and arises for the obvious

reason that these fleets account for most of the total catch of demersal species. Not surprisingly, improved selectivity results in lower discards with higher landings and larger SSB. As would be expected beam trawls (BT2) are most important for flatfish. Otter trawls (TR1 and TR2) are most important for roundfish and gurnards. The TR2 fleet is also most important for the effects on whiting. The “BEAM” fleet, directed at shrimp, shows particular sensitivity for sole.

The sensitivity to a change in effort is somewhat different and is higher. The pattern of beam trawls affecting flatfish and otter trawls affecting roundfish remains apparent. However, many more species in the BT2, TR1 and TR2 fleets are affected and despite a positive change in SSB, the change in landings is negative. This implies that the current level of fishing as estimated from the model is below MSY for most species.

The largest reductions in discards resulting from improved selectivity are seen in fleets BT2 and TR2 (Figure 64). There is a very large reduction in discards of plaice and common dab in the BT2 fleet with these species also important, along with haddock and whiting in the TR2 fleet. A mixture of roundfish show modest reductions in the TR1 fleet, especially haddock. It is notable that in most fleets common dab discards are reduced substantially.

Improved selectivity results in higher landings (Figure 65) with the BT2 fleet the main beneficiary for plaice. Both the TR1 and TR2 fleet show improved landings for a mixture of species, mainly roundfish in the TR1 fleet. Despite the larger reduction in discards in the TR2 fleet, it is the TR1 fleet that benefits more in terms of landings. This is because the release of discards from the TR2 fleet allows more fish to reach landing size and are taken by the TR1 fleet in greater quantities which has a larger fishing mortality rate.

While most discards arise due to disposal of small fish, a proportion of landing size may be discarded in bulk and model estimates of these are shown in Figure 66. Improved selectivity will not affect the quantity of these fish caught but their fate will depend on the compliance with the Landing Obligation. If it is assumed that compliance is high, then these fish potentially would augment the landings. Typically the quantity of bulk discards is small and the resulting additional potential landings are therefore small. Of the more valuable species, plaice benefits BT2 and cod TR1.

Reducing discards would be expected to result in increased SSB. The percentage increase in the SSB for the species considered is shown in Figure 67. With a few exceptions the improvement is 20% or less with the five main demersal species, cod, haddock, whiting, plaice and sole falling into this category. A few species apparently show very large improvements including grey gurnards, common dab and hake. Whether these values are realistic is open to question, though the very large quantities of common dab discards, seen from sampling programmes, is consistent with increased SSB if selectivity was improved.

3.3.1.6 Discussion

The model developed here explicitly considers the dynamics of the discard sized fish in the stock in order to establish a basis for simulating changes in selectivity that might arise through the implementation of the Landing Obligation. It can be used with survey data to model minor species where age/size structured data from the fishery are absent and where there are few samples of discarded fish. The model typically fits the observed survey and commercial catch data well and reproduces the trends in fishing mortality and spawning stock biomass for species where full stock assessments are available. This provides some

reassurance that applying the model to other species is likely to be satisfactory. However, estimates of the discard selectivity parameter are subject to large uncertainty in a number of species. The assumed uniform prior of (0,1) will mean that in the absence of information in the data, the mean value of the estimate will be approximately 0.5. This uncertainty will matter less when comparing scenarios (e.g. base case to perfect selection, DA) since the base case model reproduces the correct scale of discards but it does mean that as an absolute measure of selectivity it may not be reliable.

The sensitivity coefficients show that there is an important difference between improving selectivity and reducing fishing effort. In the former scenario, the reduction in discards leads to an improvement both in the long term landings and the SSB. For the effort scenario both landings and discards are reduced and it is only the SSB that shows an increase. The difference in outcome is due to the differentially higher survival of small fish in the DA that grow to the landing size where the fishing mortality is unchanged. In the effort case, fishing mortality is reduced for all sizes and the increase in stock biomass is insufficient to compensate the lost catch at reduced fishing mortality. It implies that for this selectivity pattern, fishing is occurring below MSY and is consistent with the low values of fishing mortality estimated for most species (Table 17).

These results are conditioned on the assumption that recruitment is independent of SSB and that it varies only around a stationary mean. While it is likely that recruitment is dependent on SSB, the effect will be most important at low biomass. Since most of the species considered show improving biomass this is unlikely to be a serious problem.

As might be expected, the smaller mesh fleets, BT2 and TR2, generate the greatest amount of discards. BT2, in particular, generates very large quantities of common dab and plaice discards. In targeting a small flatfish, common sole, the fleet takes a large bycatch of larger flatfish such as plaice which are of lower value and more likely to be discarded. Clearly the elimination of discarding in this fleet would be highly beneficial to a number of flatfish including plaice and dab. The TR1 fleet discards are lower in quantity but spread over a wider range of fish and include unwanted species such as grey gurnard. This fleet benefits most from reduced discards in the TR2 fleet through increased landings of the more valuable roundfish such as haddock and cod.

The discard process is modelled here as two components, one related to size and the other to bulk discarding. Estimates of bulk discarding in the model are more speculative as the absence of size in the discard data offer little information to quantify this element. The informative priors assume that for valuable species the mean rate of bulk discarding is 14% and for bulk discards 40%. For many species the posterior mean is little influenced by the data (Table 17) indicating that this process is driven very much by the prior assumption. The quantities of bulk discards are typically low in comparison to the size related element and are therefore not influential in the scenario modelling. However, the question does arise as to the consequences of the LO. While it is theoretically possible to eliminate size discards through improved selectivity, bulk discards can only be prevented by landing this element of the catch. That in turn means that for valuable species, TACs need to be able to accommodate these additional fish, or in the case of low value species where TACs are less restrictive, such as dab and grey gurnard, there needs to be a market for such fish to provide an incentive to land them, especially as compliance to the LO is likely to be hard to enforce.

Single species analysis of the consequences of discarding do not take into account the biological interactions between species and since many of the species considered in this study are piscivorous to some degree, the results may suggest larger improvements to stock biomass and expected landings than can be realised. If larger predatory fish such as cod, for example, increase in abundance, there may be a suppressive effect on their prey species. This problem will be greatest if the model predictions suggest major changes to the relative balance in biomass of the various species. The model estimates of mean biomass in the DA scenario typically suggest modest increases of up to 20% so that it might be expected that biological effects might also be modest. However, this analysis only considers demersal species and omits key planktivorous species such as sandeel and herring that may be suppressed by the higher biomass of demersal species (Heath et al, 2014).

The DA scenario modelled here is clearly artificial and could not be achieved simultaneously for all species. It therefore represents the extreme maximum of what might be achieved through technical improvements to selectivity and is at best an indicator of the direction and magnitude of the benefits eliminating discards. The results suggest that improved selectivity would be beneficial to long term landings and SSB and that it offers more benefit than simply reducing fishing mortality. The difference between these two alternatives from this analysis implies that the changed selection pattern in the DA scenario results in a higher MSY for same scale of fishing.

3.3.1.7 References

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Table 11. Species included in the analysis with corresponding values used to configure the model. The EMLS is taken from Heath and Cook (2015). ICES stock areas are; 3a=Skagerrak, 4=North Sea, 6=West of Scotland, 7d=Eastern channel. The greater North Sea is the combined area 4+3a

Stock	Acronym	Species	ICES stock area	M	Length at 75% maturity	EMLS (cm)	q prior
cod	cod	<i>Gadus morhua</i> , Gadidae	3a+4+7d	0.2	68.5	35	beta(0.5,2)
haddock	had	<i>Melanogrammus aeglefinus</i> , Gadidae	3a+4	0.3	27.5	30	beta(0.5,2)
whiting	whi	<i>Merlangius merlangus</i> , Gadidae	3a+7d	0.3	21.5	27	beta(0.5,2)
plaice	ple	<i>Pleuronectes platessa</i> , Pleuronectidae	4	0.1	25.5	27	beta(0.5,2)
sole	sol	<i>solea solea</i> , Soleidea	4	0.1	22	24	beta(0.5,2)
turbot	tur	<i>Scophthalmus maximus</i> , Scophthalmidae	3a+4	0.2	25	30	beta(0.5,2)
megrims	meg	<i>Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis</i> , <i>Lepidorhombus boscii</i> , Scophthalmidae	3a+4+6	0.2	25.5	20	beta(0.5,2)
witch	wit	<i>Glyptocephalus cynoglossus</i> , Pleuronectidae	3a+4	0.2	42.5	28	beta(0.5,2)
lemon sole	lso	<i>Microstomus kitt</i> , Pleuronectidae	3a+4	0.2	18.5	25	beta(0.5,2)
hake	hak	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i> , Gadidae	Northern	0.2	35	27	beta(0.5,2)
common dab	cda	<i>Limanda limanda</i> , Pleuronectidae	3a+4	0.2	11.5	25	beta(2,3)
flounder	flo	<i>Platichthys flesus</i> , Pleuronectidae	3a+4	0.2	18	27	beta(2,3)
Brill	bri	<i>Scophthalmus rhombus</i> , Scophthalmidae	3a+4	0.2	25.5	30	beta(0.5,2)
Anglerfish	ang	<i>Lophius piscatorius</i> , <i>Lophuis budegassa</i> , Lophiidea	3a+4+6	0.2	29	32	beta(0.5,2)
ling	lin	<i>Molva molva</i> , Lotidae	3a+4	0.2	48.5	63	beta(0.5,2)
spurdog	spu	<i>Squalus acanthius</i> , Squalidae	3a+4	0.2	70	50	beta(0.5,2)
pollack	pol	<i>Pollachius pollachius</i> , Gadidae	3a+4	0.2	40	30	beta(0.5,2)
saithe	sai	<i>Pollachius virens</i> , Gadidae	3a+4+6	0.2	40	35	beta(0.5,2)
mullet	mul	Mugilidae	3a+4	0.2	15	16	beta(0.5,2)
tusk	tus	<i>Brosme brosme</i> , Lotidae	3a+4	0.2	42	40	beta(0.5,2)
seabass	bas	<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i> , Moronidae	3a+4	0.2	31.5	36	beta(0.5,2)
gurnards	gur	<i>Chelidonichthys cuculus</i> , <i>Chelidonichthys lucernus</i> , Triglidae	3a+4	0.2	22.5	30	beta(0.5,2)
grey gurnard	ggu	<i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i> , Triglidae	3a+4	0.2	22	30	beta(2,3)
skates + rays	ray	Rajidae	3a+4	0.2	NA	40	beta(0.5,2)
wolf-fish	wol	<i>Anarhichas lupus</i> , Anarhichadidae	3a+4	0.2	35	30	beta(0.5,2)

Table 12. Population equations

No.	Equation	Description
T2.1	$N_{t+1}^d = pN_t^d \exp(-sF_t - M_t^d) + \pi R_t$	The population, N, decays with fishing mortality rate F and natural mortality rate, M. A proportion, p, remain in the discard size population. The parameter s, is the relative selectivity of discard fish compared to landing sized fish. A proportion π of recruits, R, joins the discard sized population. The superscript, d, denotes discard sized fish and the subscript, t, denotes year.
T2.2	$N_{t+1}^l = N_t^l \exp(-F_t - M_t^l) + (1-p)N_t^d \exp(-sF_t - M_t^d) + (1-\pi)R_t$	The population of landing sized fish decays with mortality rates F and M and is augmented with a proportion of surviving discard sized fish that grow to landing size, and by a proportion of the recruits. The superscript, l, denotes landing sized fish.
T2.3	$R_t \sim \text{Lognormal}(\bar{r}, \sigma_r)$ <p>Where $\bar{r} = \log(h\bar{U}/q)$</p>	Recruitment is a random variable with lognormal errors and mean \bar{r} . For convenience, \bar{r} is scaled to the mean of the observed indices with a constant, h.
T2.4	$F_{t+1} = F_t \exp(\varepsilon_t), \varepsilon_t \sim \text{Normal}(0, \sigma_f)$	Fishing mortality follows a random walk with a multiplicative normal error where $\sigma_f = 0.2$
T2.5	$M_t^d = f(w_t^d)$ $M_t^l = f(w_t^l)$	Natural mortality is a function of mean weight, w. The function, f, is the Lorenzen relationship.

Table 13. Observation equations

No.	Equation	Description
T3.1	$C_t^d = sF_t N_t^d [1 - \exp(-sF_t - M_t^d)] / (sF_t + M_t^d)$ $C_t^l = F_t N_t^l [1 - \exp(-F_t - M_t^l)] / (F_t + M_t^l)$	The catch in number for each size category is derived directly from the Baranov catch equation.
T3.2	$D_t = w_t^d C_t^d + Q w_t^l C_t^l$	Total weight of fish discarded is the sum of fish discarded by size and a proportion, Q, of landing sized fish. Weights for each size category are denoted by w.
T3.3	$L_t = (1-Q)w_t^l C_t^l$	Total landed weight is the proportion of landing sized fish that are retained.
T3.4	$U_t^d = s'qN_t^d$ $U_t^l = qN_t^l$	The survey index, U, is proportional to the true population with catchability, q. The parameter, s', is the relative selectivity of

discard sized fish to landing sized fish in the survey.

Table 14. Fleet based equations used in the projection model.

No.	Equation	Description
T4.1	$s_k = \frac{D_k \sum_k C_k}{C_k \sum_k D_k} s$	Selectivity for the kth fleet, s_k , is derived from whole fleet selectivity, s , using the ratios of the fleet discards and fleet catch to the total discards and total catch.
T4.2	$F_{k,t} = F_t C_{k,t} / C_t$	Fleet fishing mortality, F_k is derived from total fishing mortality F using the fleet-total catch ratios.
T4.3	$C_{k,t}^d = s_k F_{k,t} N_t^d [1 - \exp(-sF_t - M_t^d)] / (sF_t + M_t^d)$ $C_t^l = F_{k,t} N_t^l [1 - \exp(-F_t - M_t^l)] / (F_t + M_t^l)$	Fleet catches $C_{k,t}^d$ are given by Baranov equation.
T4.4	$TSB_t = N_t^d w_t^d + N_t^l w_t^l$	Total stock biomass is the sum of the biomasses of discard and landing sized fish.
T4.5	$w_t^s = TSB_t / (N_t^d + N_t^l)$	Mean weight of the stock is given by total biomass divided by total population number
T4.6	$\rho_t = \frac{\exp(a + b w_t^s)}{1 + \exp(a + b w_t^s)}$	The proportion mature biomass, ρ is derived from the mean weight in the stock where a and b are regression constants.
T4.7	$SSB_t = \rho_t TSB_t$	Spawning stock biomass is derived from total biomass and the proportion mature.

Table 15. Observation error assumptions.

Equation	Description
$\widehat{D}_t \sim \text{Lognormal}(\log(D_t), \sigma_d)$	Observed (hatted) quantities have lognormal error distributions with standard deviations σ .
$\widehat{L}_t \sim \text{Lognormal}(\log(L_t), \sigma_l)$	
$\widehat{U}_t^d \sim \text{Lognormal}(\log(U_t^d), \sigma_d^u)$	
$\widehat{U}_t^l \sim \text{Lognormal}(\log(U_t^l), \sigma_l^u)$	

Table 16. Priors for the parameters to be estimated in the model.

Prior distribution
$\sigma_r \sim \text{Uniform}(0,5)$
$\sigma_d \sim \text{Uniform}(0,1)$
$\sigma_l \sim \text{Uniform}(0,1)$
$\sigma_d^u \sim \text{Uniform}(0,10)$
$\sigma_l^u \sim \text{Uniform}(0,10)$
$s \sim \text{Uniform}(0,1)$
$s' \sim \text{Uniform}(0, s)$
$\pi \sim \text{Uniform}(0,1)$
$p \sim \text{Uniform}(0, \pi)$
$Q \sim \text{beta}(0.5,3)$
$Q \sim \text{beta}(2,3)$
$\text{Log}(q) \sim \text{Uniform}(-10,10)$
$F_1 \sim \text{Lognormal}(\log(0.6), 0.5)$
$h \sim \text{Uniform}(0,2)$

Table 17. Summary of parameter estimates from fitting the model to historical data. For time varying quantities, N , F and Q , values are the mean of the most recent 5 years in the time series.

Species	Discard wt	landings wt	N: discard size	N: landing size	$\log(r)$	σ_r	Fishing mortality, F	Selectivity, s	Bulk discard proportion Q	Proportion of recruits, π , entering discard size	Proportion remaining discard size, p
Angler	0.17	2.59	70835	74943	10.50	0.41	0.06	0.28	0.07	0.91	0.46
Seabass	0.23	0.80	40341	26502	9.34	1.18	0.18	0.70	0.15	0.76	0.53
Brill	0.21	0.84	4440	18937	8.83	0.24	0.13	0.51	0.07	0.50	0.27
Dab	0.05	0.17	8290003	338209	14.86	0.13	0.45	0.37	0.56	0.99	0.98
Cod	0.13	1.73	305489	145287	11.97	0.44	0.23	0.55	0.17	0.93	0.66
Flounder	0.13	0.37	5122	34143	9.63	0.27	0.34	0.45	0.21	0.28	0.16
Grey gurnard	0.08	0.23	61277	6374	10.29	0.20	0.82	0.60	0.38	0.94	0.91
Other gurnards	0.11	0.28	370407	58322	11.73	0.22	0.19	0.40	0.10	0.99	0.93
Haddock	0.09	0.38	1761771	994790	13.51	1.16	0.14	0.66	0.06	0.98	0.64
Hake	0.05	0.53	138138	78839	11.25	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.13	0.88	0.51
Ling	0.49	4.10	14026	16170	9.27	0.04	0.23	0.32	0.18	0.81	0.51
Lemon sole	0.07	0.22	155252	156292	11.88	0.10	0.20	0.60	0.12	0.72	0.57
Megrim	0.02	0.36	13919	70598	10.53	0.25	0.17	0.39	0.11	0.30	0.14
Mulletts	0.02	0.13	62279	48575	10.19	0.92	0.28	0.60	0.16	0.73	0.44
Plaice	0.08	0.25	8140923	7329897	14.87	0.18	0.06	0.88	0.14	0.91	0.82

Pollack	0.07	2.51	14	2674	7.23	0.33	0.41	0.39	0.16	0.01	0.01
Rays and skates	0.18	1.94	8157	31124	9.10	0.24	0.01	0.57	0.21	0.61	0.42
Saithe	0.12	1.19	35404	965849	12.43	0.47	0.10	0.48	0.08	0.13	0.06
Sole	0.03	0.21	951117	540728	12.69	0.24	0.16	0.22	0.06	0.97	0.82
Spurdog	0.15	1.83	27759	118233	10.41	0.11	0.00	0.37	0.58	0.61	0.27
Turbot	0.30	1.57	4752	19078	8.90	0.13	0.15	0.37	0.12	0.52	0.20
Tusk	0.30	1.57	7609	25079	9.07	0.15	0.09	0.32	0.12	0.58	0.27
Whiting	0.05	0.19	2684263	750824	14.06	0.46	0.20	0.50	0.08	0.93	0.80
Witch	0.05	0.24	43179	74537	10.51	0.27	0.19	0.59	0.10	0.71	0.45
Wolf fish	0.15	2.79	106	4221	6.99	0.08	0.08	0.40	0.14	0.09	0.04

Figure 61. Relationship between proportion mature and mean weight in the stock derived from survey data. R squared values are shown for each stock.

Figure 62. Delta coefficients for a 10% improvement in selectivity. Red=discards, green=landings and blue=SSB.

Figure 63. Delta coefficients for a 10% reduction in fleet effort. Red=discards, green=landings and blue=SSB.

Figure 64. Quantity of size related discards (tonnes) avoided in the perfect selectivity scenario, DA. The species shown in rank order account for 99% of the total size related discards by weight within each fleet.

Figure 65. Increase in landings (tonnes) in the perfect selectivity scenario, DA. The species shown in rank order account for 99% of the total landings by weight.

Figure 66. Additional increase in landings (tonnes) arising from landing "bulk" discards in the perfect selectivity, DA, scenario. The species shown in rank order account for 99% of the total bulk related discards by weight

Figure 67. Percentage increase in SSB arising from perfect selectivity, DA.

3.3.2 StrathE2E modelling of the Landing Obligation in the North Sea

3.3.2.1 Introduction

In this project, we aimed to determine the ecosystem-wide consequences of alternative approaches to implementing the EU Landing Obligation in the North Sea. The underlying logic behind the project was that the effects of human-induced pressures such as fishing, applied to any part of an ecosystem are eventually felt everywhere to some extent through the phenomenon known as a 'trophic cascade' (Pace *et al.* 1999). Cascading effects are attenuated or amplified as they propagate through the food web, depending on the nature of the pressure and details of the ecology. There is no universal theory of trophic cascade propagation (Heath *et al.* 2014b), so diagnosing the type and magnitude of disturbances that an ecosystem can sustain before being fundamentally altered requires simulation with mathematical models that aim to represent the key ecological components and processes which govern cascades.

We used an end-to-end (microbes to megafauna) food web and ecosystem model (StrathE2E) to diagnose the consequences of different discarding scenarios. The study builds on previous work on this topic using an earlier version of the model (Heath *et al.* 2014a).

3.3.2.2 Methods

3.3.2.2.1 General description of the StrathE2E model.

We used a development of the StrathE2E marine food web/ecosystem model (Heath 2012, Heath *et al.* 2015) to address questions about the ecosystem effects of discarding practices in the North Sea. The model spans the entire ecosystem from inorganic nutrients and detritus through to birds and mammals but, in order to do so, takes a highly macroscopic view of ecology, aggregating over the many microscopic details of taxonomy, demography and spatial structure (Figure 68). The aim was a scheme which represents the gross dynamics of the ecosystem with a tolerable parameter count, and is fast to run so enabling computational optimisation and sensitivity analysis of model outputs. The model comprises a fishing fleet model and an ecology model, with one-way coupling between the two. The fishing fleet model aggregates data on the activity, distributions, and properties of a range of fishing gears over the area covered by the model, and generates the information that is required in the ecology model to simulate the catch, landings, discards, and biomass-dynamics of the targeted and by-catch ecology groups in the sea.

3.3.2.2.2 Ecology model description

The ecology model is a network of mass conserving coupled ordinary differential equations (ODEs) describing spatially averaged rates of change in state variables representing organic detritus, dissolved inorganic nutrient, and living biomass. To simplify the description we can think of the variables as being divided between two coupled sub-networks: a predator-prey network - the food web - and a nutrient recycling network. Between the two, all marine life-forms are explicitly or implicitly included, ranging from bacteria to birds and mammals, but aggregated into coarse groups or 'guilds' defined primarily by feeding characteristics and diet preferences (Figure 68). All state variables, except macrophytes, are expressed solely in terms of nitrogen mass, since this element is the most commonly limiting in temperate shelf seas. Macrophytes are

expressed in terms of both nitrogen and carbon mass with dynamic stoichiometry since these organisms have an exceptional capacity to seasonally absorb and store nitrogen.

Each ODE comprises a set of rate-of-change terms representing a variety of biological and physical processes. Biological terms describe the balance between gains due to assimilation of food, and losses due to mortality and metabolism. Some components of the food web are resolved into life-stages and for these the equations also include the balance between gains due to recruitment and losses due to developmental progression or spawning. In addition, all components of the model are, in principle, replicated across homogeneous spatial compartments, so each ODE also includes terms representing advection, mixing and migration flows through the system.

The spatial structure is highly stylised, consistent with the coarse guild-definitions of the living and chemical components of the system. Two horizontally distinct but interconnected bathymetric/hydrographic zones are distinguished – a shallow, vertically mixed zone mostly influenced by tides and freshwater inputs, and a deeper, potentially seasonally stratified zone mostly influenced by exchange with an external ocean (Figure 69). For convenience here, we refer to these as the inshore and offshore zones respectively, though there is no necessity for the inshore zone to be adjacent to the coast – in principle it could represent a shallow offshore bank. The water column in the offshore/deep/seasonally stratified zone is divided vertically into two compartments or layers, whilst the inshore/shallow/mixed zone is represented by a single compartment. Seabed habitats are represented by exposed rock and up to three compartments of different sediment properties in each zone, each defined by median grain size and natural disturbance rates. Vertical and horizontal exchanges between the spatial compartments are modelled as combination of sinking, mixing and active migration. State variables are resolved hierarchically to spatial compartments representing the seabed habitats, water column layers and bathymetric zones, with the largest (in terms of body size) and/or most mobile groups being represented at the coarsest spatial resolution (Table 18).

3.3.2.2.3 Representation of fisheries

Living biomass groups considered vulnerable to capture by fishing activity are the top-predators (birds, pinnipeds and cetaceans); planktivorous, demersal and migratory fish; carnivorous/scavenge and filter/deposit feeding benthos, carnivorous zooplankton, and macrophytes. In each case, the fishing process is represented as an optional flux from the relevant living components of the food web to the discards class of organic detritus (or macrophyte debris in the case of macrophyte harvesting), and a residual export flux from the model representing landed biomass. To achieve this, capture is represented as a first-order rate processes in the ODE for each group, defined by a harvest ratio (proportion of instantaneous biomass captured per unit time). Then, a proportion of the catch is directed to the discards class, comprising whole-animal rejects and viscera arising from at-sea processing of the remaining catch. Only the residual fraction of the catch weight is exported from the model. The rejection rate of catch, proportion of retained-catch which is processed at sea, and the proportion of body weight regarded as viscera, are defined for each group by external parameters generated by the separate model of fishing fleets (Table 19).

In addition to the direct capture process, three incidental effects of fishing activity are represented in the model - release of pore-water nutrients, resuspension of sediment detritus, and damage mortality of benthos, due to sea-bed abrasion by bottom-contact mobile fishing gears. These processes are driven by the area-proportion of each seabed sediment habitat abraded per unit time, which is generated by the fishing fleet model and delivered as an input to the ecology model.

3.3.2.2.4 Fleet model description

The fishing-related driving data required by the ecology model are integrals over a range of different fishing gears. Each gear will have its own spatial pattern of activity, selectivity for resource groups, discard and at-sea processing practices, and contact rate with the seabed. The fishing fleet model performs these integrations across up to 12 different types of fishing gears and assembles the data for input to the ecology model.

The fleet model, developed from a prototype by Heath et al. (2015), is a static, matrix-based scheme. Key inputs are, for each gear type, the activity density and its proportional distribution across seabed habitat types, fishing power, seabed abrasion rate, discard (rejection) rate, and at-sea processing rate for each living resource group (Table 19). Activity density is defined as the deployment duration of a given gear per unit sea surface area in a given time interval, integrated across all vessels (units: m^{-2}). The power of a gear is a measure of its efficiency at catching biomass of a given resource group. The product of activity density and power is a quantity that we refer to as fishing effort. For a given resource group, effort is proportional to the harvest ratio and can be summed across gears.

The fleet model also transfers to the ecology model, a set of parameters for relationships describing systematic changes in proportions by weight of non-target by-catch and undersize (less than legal minimum or marketable landing size) demersal fish in commercial catches, as a function of biomass in the sea. The default parameters for these relationships are based on observational data from e.g. trawl survey data, and allow discard patterns to vary dynamically during a simulation rather than according to static parameters.

3.3.2.2.5 Model configuration

The data which define the model for a specific geographic region and period of years are grouped into physical oceanographic, ecological, and fishing-related parameters. The physical parameters include bathymetry and the area-proportion and median grain size of each sediment habitat, monthly sea temperatures, river freshwater and nutrient inflows, ocean transport and nutrient flows, atmospheric deposition of nutrient. The ecological parameters include feeding rates and prey preferences of each biological group in the food web, geochemical rates governing the processing of organic matter by bacteria, migration rates for fish and top-predators, and external stocks of migratory fish (mackerel). For the fishing fleet model, the inputs are the activity rates and spatial distributions, selectivity, seabed abrasion, and discarding rates, and processing-at-sea rates of each of the twelve gear types which are represented. For the North Sea model, these include 11 groups of STECF gears, plus Norwegian whaling vessels which operate in the Norwegian sector of the North Sea. Details of the compilation of data from STECF and the Norwegian Fisheries Directorate are given in Appendix 1.

The selectivity parameters of the fishing gears represented in the model are particularly important. These define the catching efficiency for each harvestable group in the ecology model groups. For example, demersal otter trawls target demersal fish, but also takes a by-catch of planktivorous fish and benthos, so we need to represent this in the model in order to fully represent the effects of otter trawls on the food web. The selectivity parameters of each gear for fish and benthos groups were derived from the activity, landings and discards data by gear held in the STECF database (Appendix 2). In addition to fish and benthos, certain fishing gears are also known to take an unintended by-catch of top predators (seabirds, seals and cetaceans). The selectivity parameters for these groups were estimated from an analysis of by-catch data gleaned from the literature (Appendix 3).

We configured a model of the North Sea ecosystem (Figure 70) for two time periods 1970-1999, and 2003-2013. The primary calibration period for the ecology model was 1970-1999, since harvest ratios for the coarse groups of taxa are reasonably known for this period (Heath 2012) and there exists a large quantity of observational data for parameter optimisation. However, but fishing gear activity rates are unknown since there was no system equivalent to the STECF data gathering process at that time. We then fitted the harvest ratios for the 2003-2013 period assuming the ecology model parameters from 1970-1999, and the known STECF gear activity rates. This provided the scaling relationships between gear activity density and harvest ration needed for the fishing fleet model. Once these were known, we could then use the fleet model in isolation to estimate what gear activity must have been during 1970-1999 in order to generate the known harvest ratios during that period, assuming constant selectivity and catching power.

3.3.2.2.6 Model outputs

At the end of each run, the annual averaged biomasses of model components were calculated for the final year of the simulation, together with annual integrals of production rates, dietary fluxes, landings and discards. In addition, a range of network information indices were derived from the annual integrated food web flow matrix for the final year, using the R package NetIndices v1.4.4 (Soetaert et al. 2015).

The flow matrices constructed for the final year of each model contained the annual integrated fluxes of mass between all compartments in the whole-domain (spatially integrated) system. These included the fluxes between all prey-to-predator links defined by the preference parameter matrix, all individual excretion and defecation fluxes to ammonia and detritus, all exchange fluxes between water column and sediment states, spawning, recruitment, all external imports by advection, atmospheric deposition and migration, and all exports by advection, migration, denitrification and fishery landings.

Using the “TrophInd” function in NetIndices we calculated the mean trophic level and omnivory index for each living group in the model, including the various larval stages.

The “AscInd” function in NetIndices provided a matrix of Ascendency, Overhead, Capacity, and the AC ratio (Ascendency/Capacity) for all flows (including imports and exports), the internal flows, imports, exports and dissipation terms. Capacity is a measure of the maximum information flow through the system, and is related to Total System Throughput (TST) - the sum of all fluxes in

the network including the imports and exports, and is a measure of the 'size' of the system. Ascendency is a measure of the organisation, or the extent to which the Capacity is being utilised. The ratio of Ascendency:Capacity (AC ratio) is proposed as a useful index of the 'maturity' of a network (Patricio et al 2006).

3.3.2.2.7 Parameter estimation

Parameters of the ecology model which could not easily be independently established were estimated by computational optimisation, using a specially developed penalised-likelihood simulated annealing scheme. This fits the stationary state model to a range of long-term average ecosystem metrics derived from observed data, using Markov Chain Monte Carlo methodology (Metropolis-Hastings algorithm) to search the parameter space for a combination giving the maximum likelihood of the observed data given the model and its parameters. A total of 128 parameters are estimated by this means (Appendix 4). The predator-prey preference matrix which defines all of the food web connections in the model is given in Appendix 5.

Table 18: Ecology model state variables and spatial hierarchy

Differentiated by horizontal zone and sediment habitat	Differentiated by horizontal zone and water column layer	Differentiated by horizontal zone with modelled vertical distribution	Differentiated by horizontal zone only
Sediment bacteria and labile detritus	Nitrate	Omnivorous zooplankton	Suspension/deposit feeding benthos
Refractory sediment detritus	Ammonia	Carnivorous zooplankton	Carnivore/scavenge feeding benthos
Pore-water nitrate	Suspended bacteria and detritus	Larvae of suspension/deposit feeding benthos	Planktivorous fish
Pore-water ammonia	Phytoplankton	Larvae of carnivore/scavenge feeding benthos	Demersal fish (divided into fishery quota-limited and non-quota components)
Fishery discards		Larvae of planktivorous fish	Migratory fish
Corpses		Larvae of demersal fish	Pinnipeds
Macrophytes (confined to inshore rock habitat)			Seabirds
			Cetaceans

Table 19. Fishing fleet model inputs and outputs

<p>Input data for each gear type (maximum 12 types)</p> <p>Annual model domain averaged fleet activity density (number of boats x time spent fishing per boat, per day, per unit area)</p> <p>Proportion of annual activity over each model seabed habitat</p> <p>Selectivity (catching power) for each ecology model resource group</p> <p>Rejection (discard) rate for each ecology model resource group</p> <p>Proportion of each catch group processed (gutted) at sea</p> <p>Seabed area abraded per unit activity</p>
<p>Gear-independent parameters</p> <p>Parameters for scaling effort (activity x power) to harvest ratio for each ecology model resource group</p> <p>Seabed sediment penetration depth (common value across all gears)</p> <p>Damage-related mortality rate of benthos per bottom-contact gear pass (common value across all gears)</p> <p>Proportion by weight of viscera for catch groups processed at sea</p>
<p>Model outputs</p> <p>Bathymetric zone harvest ratios and processing-at-sea and discard rates for each ecology model resource group due to all gears combined (required for input to the ecology model)</p> <p>Area-proportion of each seabed habitat abraded per unit time by all gears combined (required for input to the ecology model)</p> <p>Proportion of discards (rejects and offal) from all gears combined, which are deposited over each seabed habitat (required for input to the ecology model)</p> <p>For each horizontal zone separately, proportion of total effort directed at each ecology model resource group which is attributable to each gear (required for disaggregating simulated landings and discards to individual gears from ecology model output)</p>

Table 20: Ecology model parameters, input and outputs

<p>Static configuration data</p> <p>Model domain sea surface area; area-proportions of bathymetric zones and water column layer thicknesses; area-proportions of seabed habitats and median grain sizes of sediments</p> <p>Parameters for deriving sediment porosity, permeability and organic nitrogen content in each seabed habitat from median grain size, and light attenuation coefficients from suspended particulate matter (SPM) concentration</p> <p>Ocean biomass of migratory fish stock and the annual proportion entering the model domain</p>
<p>Monthly resolution internal driving data</p> <p>Proportion of each seabed habitat sediment layer volume disturbed by natural bed shear stress per unit time.</p> <p>Vertical mixing and horizontal advection rates between compartments within the model</p> <p>Temperature and suspended particulate matter concentrations in water column layers, sea surface irradiance in each depth zone, significant wave height adjacent to the coast</p>
<p>Monthly resolution external boundary influxes of nutrient</p> <p>Volume inflows across the external ocean boundaries of the model and from rivers, and concentrations of nutrient, phytoplankton and suspended detritus in the inflows</p> <p>Atmospheric deposition of nutrient to the sea surface</p> <p>Other nutrient discharges into the model domain (assumed to enter the inshore zone)</p>
<p>Inputs from the fishing fleet model</p> <p>Inshore and offshore zone harvest ratios, proportions of catch rejected (discarded) and proportions of retained catch processed at sea for each resource group</p> <p>Area-proportion of each seabed habitat abraded by trawling per unit time</p> <p>Proportion of discards and offal deposited over each seabed habitat</p>
<p>Biological parameters (* indicates fitted parameters)</p> <p>*Prey preference parameters for each predator-prey pairing</p> <p>*Maximum uptake rate and prey half saturation concentration for each consumer group</p> <p>*First-order rate coefficients for microbial processes</p> <p>*Density dependent mortality coefficients</p> <p>*Coefficients for active horizontal migration rates of fish and top-predators</p> <p>*Sinking rates for detritus</p> <p>*Parameters for the exploitable fraction of biomass for each group subjected to fishing.</p>

Saturating irradiances for nutrient uptake by phytoplankton, and carbon uptake by macrophytes

Assimilation efficiency for each consumer group

Maximum and minimum nitrogen:carbon ratios for macrophytes

Food-independent metabolic rates for each consumer group, and density-dependent carbohydrate excretion rate for macrophytes

Q₁₀ temperature dependency coefficients for autotrophic and heterotrophic maximum uptake rates, metabolic rates and microbial processes

Annual weight-specific fecundities for fish and benthos groups; start and end dates for egg production, and for recruitment of larval stages to the settled stocks

Start and end dates for immigration and emigration of migratory fish

Parameters for relationship between demersal fish biomass and a) proportion of non-quota demersal fish and b) proportion of undersize quota-limited and non-quota fish in the catches

Model outputs (all at daily intervals)

Mass of each state variable

Model import and export fluxes (transport, atmospheric deposition, river inflows, denitrification, fishery landings)

Derived internal fluxes: consumption flux for each prey-predator pair, consumption and production fluxes of nitrate and ammonia in each depth zone and layer, fishery discards and offal

Figure 68: Schematic of the food web compartments of the StrathE2E model. Birds, seals and cetaceans are combined into a single group for the purposes of the diagram, but are separate entities in the actual model. Green arrows represent advection, mixing and migration; orange arrows represent fishery-related fluxes; black arrows represent biological fluxes. Red labelled components are active migrators whilst blue are subject to passive advection and mixing and black are anchored. Pale blue boxes represent quantities that are exported from the model whilst yellow are imported. The model also includes fluxes from living components to ammonia, detritus and corpses due to excretion, defecation and death but these are not shown for clarity.

Figure 69: Schematic showing the horizontal and vertical spatial structure of the model. The compartments S0-S3 and D0-D3 refer to shallow and deep seabed sediment habitats respectively. S0 and D0 are rock habitats which reflect, rather than absorbing, settling material back into the water column.

Figure 70: Map of the StrathE2E model region. Within the North Sea the model resolves sub-area of seabed sediment habitat divided into inshore (shallower than 30m) and offshore. Within each zone, three sediment classes are represented – fine (muddy), medium (sandy) and coarse (gravel). Within each of the six sediment habitats a proportion of the seabed area may present as exposed bedrock (not shown) which has different geochemical properties and in the inshore zone supports the macrophyte forests which are included in the model food web.

3.3.2.2.8 Modelling of discarding scenarios

Baseline model configuration

We considered two baseline situations corresponding to the heavily exploited North Sea system during 1970-1999, and the more lightly exploited (with respect to finfish) situation during 2003-2013. In each case, our baseline model was a stationary solution with the appropriate environmental and fishing driving conditions for each period. By stationary, we mean a model which has converged to a repeating annual cycle of output given a repeating annual cycle of model inputs reflecting the climatology of the required baseline period.

The discarding behaviours during 2003-2013 are known for each gear from the STECF database, and were prescribed as inputs to the model. However, there are no such data for the 1970-1999 period. In this case, we generated the discard rates of demersal fish internally within the model from an empirical relationship between proportion (by weight) of demersal fish catch smaller than the minimum landing size, and demersal biomass in the sea. Essentially, the proportion of

undersize fish in the catches decreased exponentially with biomass in the sea. This relationship was parameterised from an analysis of North Sea IBTS and landings data (Heath and Cook 2015; Heath et al. 2014b). The evidence suggests that in the earlier period the majority of discards were undersized fish, while more of the discards during 2003-2013 were of landable sizes but ‘over-quota’.

Also parameterised in the model from an empirical data, was a relationship between the proportion by weight of demersal fish catches comprising non-quota species (e.g. gurnards, halibut, pollack, ling, mullet, tusk, catfish). The empirical evidence suggests that this also decreases exponentially with bulk demersal fish biomass. These species have a higher discard rate than the targeted quota-limited species in the catches (Heath and Cook 2015)

Discarding scenarios

For each baseline period, four different discarding scenarios were simulated (Table 21)

Table 21: Configuration of discarding scenarios in the model.

Scenario	Demersal fishing mortality	Demersal discarding	fish	Other discarding (pelagic fish, invertebrates)	taxa	Comments
Baseline - Discarding as usual	As per baseline conditions	As per baseline conditions, including any over-quota discarding	As per baseline conditions	As per baseline conditions	As per baseline conditions	Represents conditions prior to any application of the Landing Obligation
‘Land everything’	As per baseline conditions	Entire catch is landed	Entire catch is landed	Entire catch is landed	Entire catch is landed	Extreme implementation of the Landing Obligation
‘Improved selectivity’	Reduced harvest rate to reflect selective capture only of fish larger than the Conservation Reference Size	Entire catch is landed, but consists only of ‘large’ fish	Entire catch is landed	Entire catch is landed	Entire catch is landed	Landing Obligation achieved through technical improvements
‘Landing Obligation’	As per baseline conditions	Entire catch of quota-limited species is landed; non-quota species discarded as per the baseline	Entire catch of quota-limited species is landed; non-quota species discarded as per the baseline	Entire catch is landed	Entire catch is landed	Landing Obligation applied only to demersal species governed by TAC limitations.

3.3.2.3 RESULTS

3.3.2.3.1 Baseline models

The differences in activity rates of the fishing gears between the two baseline periods are shown in Figure 4. The 2003-2013 activity rates are ‘known’ from the STECF database, while the equivalent rates in 1970-1999 were estimated using the fishing fleet model as described above.

The results indicate that the activity rates of the gears targeting demersal finfish were between 4 and 8-times higher in 1970-1999 than in 2003-2013. Conversely, the activities of creels, shrink trawls and the Nephrops trawls (TR2) were 50-80% less in 1970-1999 than in 2003-2013. Pelagic trawls and seines were more active in 1970-1990, but sandeel and sprat trawls were estimated to be around 30% less active, despite the higher catches of especially sandeels in the earlier period.

Figure 71: Percentage differences in the activity rates of fishing gears between the 2003-2013 and 1970-1999 baseline model period. Green bars to the right indicate that a gear was more active in 1970-1999, and red bars to the left that a gear was less active, compared to 2003-2013.

The catches (landings, by-catch and discards) simulated by the baseline models are shown in Figure 72, and the difference in biomass (mMoles Nitrogen) between the two models in Figure 73. The biomass results show that all living components of the food web except planktivorous fish and omnivorous zooplankton were less abundant in the 1970-1999 baseline model than in the 2003-2013 model.

Figure 72: Stationary state simulated catches of each resource group in the baseline models. White and grey bars represent 2003-2013 landings and discards respectively. Green and black bars represent landings and discards for 1970-1999. The inset panel shows the corresponding data for the top-predator groups (birds, pinnipeds (seals), and cetaceans). By-catch of birds is too small to distinguish on the axis scale. The landings of cetaceans refer to catches of Minke whales in the Norwegian whale fishery. Catch weights (live weight) are expressed as tonnes from the whole North Sea domain of the model.

Figure 73: Percentage differences in the mass of each chemical and biological group in the food web between the 2003-2013 and 1970-1999 baseline model periods. Green bars to the right indicate that a group was more abundant in 1970-1999, and red bars to the left that a group was less abundant, compared to 2003-2013. Upper panel shows components of the water column ecosystem (including larvae of benthic fauna), lower panel shows components of the seabed ecosystem.

3.3.2.3.2 Discarding scenarios (1970-1999)

As expected from the definitions of the discarding scenarios, the catches of all resource groups in the model were identical to the baseline case for the 'Land everything' and Landing Obligation' scenarios, but the proportions discarded were different (Figure 74). In the 'Improved Selectivity' scenario, the effective harvest ratio (fishing mortality) for demersal fish was lower than in the baseline, and this resulted in an increase in catch compared to the baseline, all of which was landed. Catch increased in the 1970-1999 'Improved Selectivity' scenario because the baseline

harvest ratio was higher than that generating maximum sustainable yield (MSY) for demersal fish in the model. Since all of the 'Improved Selectivity' catch was landed this represented a substantial increase in landings compared to the baseline.

The 'Land everything' and Landing Obligation' scenarios resulted in only very small (<1%) changes in the mass of living components of the model food web (Figure 75). In contrast, 'Improved Selectivity' produced large changes. The demersal and benthic components of the food web showed increases in biomass of up to 80% compared to the baseline, while omnivorous zooplankton, planktivorous fish and cetaceans showed reductions in mass.

Figure 74: Stationary state simulated catches of each resource group in the 1970-1999 baseline model (white and grey bars represent landings and discards respectively), and in each of the discarding scenarios (green and black bars represent landings and discards respectively). The inset panels show the corresponding data for the top-predator groups (birds, pinnipeds (seals), and cetaceans). By-catch of birds is too small to distinguish on the axis scale. The landings of cetaceans refer to catches of Minke whales in the Norwegian whale fishery. Catch weights (live weight) are expressed as tonnes from the whole North Sea domain of the model.

Figure 75: Percentage differences in the mass of each chemical and biological group in the food web between the 1970-1999 baseline model and each of the three discarding scenarios. Green bars to the right indicate that a group was more abundant in the discarding scenario than in the 1970-1999 baseline, and red bars to the left that a group was less abundant. Upper panel shows components of the water column ecosystem (including larvae of benthic fauna), lower panel shows components of the seabed ecosystem.

3.3.2.3.3 Discarding scenarios (2003-2013)

As for the 1970-1999 case, catches of all resource groups in the model were identical to the baseline case for the 'Land everything' and Landing Obligation' scenarios, but the proportions discarded were different (Figure 76). However, in contrast to the 1970-199 case, the reduction in harvest ratio implicit in the 'Improved Selectivity' scenario resulted in a decrease in catch compared to the baseline. This was because the 2003-2013 baseline harvest ratio was lower than that generating maximum sustainable yield (MSY) for demersal fish in the model. However, the overall demersal fish landings were still greater than in the baseline case.

As in the 1970-1999 case, the 'Land everything' and Landing Obligation' scenarios result in only very small (<1%) changes in the mass of living components of the 2003-2013 model food web (Figure 77). 'Improved Selectivity' produced larger changes, but significantly smaller than in the 1970-1999 case. The demersal and benthic components of the food web showed increases in biomass of up to 5% compared to the baseline, while omnivorous zooplankton, planktivorous fish, birds and cetaceans showed reductions in mass.

Figure 76: Stationary state simulated catches of each resource group in the 2003-2013 baseline model (white and grey bars represent landings and discards respectively), and in each of the discarding scenarios (green and black bars represent landings and discards respectively). The inset panels show the corresponding data for the top-predator groups (birds, pinnipeds (seals), and cetaceans). By-catch of birds is too small to distinguish on the axis scale. The landings of cetaceans refer to catches of Minke whales in the Norwegian whale fishery. Catch weights (live weight) are expressed as tonnes from the whole North Sea domain of the model.

Figure 77: Percentage differences in the mass of each chemical and biological group in the food web between the 2003-2013 baseline model and each of the three discarding scenarios. Green bars to the right indicate that a group was more abundant in the discarding scenario than in the 2003-2013 baseline, and red bars to the left that a group was less abundant. Upper panel shows components of the water column ecosystem (including larvae of benthic fauna), lower panel shows components of the seabed ecosystem.

3.3.2.3.4 Food web network indicators

Two types of network indicators derived from the model outputs were compared. Omnivory, which measures diet diversity, generally increased with trophic level in the model, though this was primarily a function of the discretisation of life-forms into functional groups (Figure 78). However, differences between the two baseline models were accentuated with trophic level. Omnivory was lower in the 2003-2013 model compared to 1970-1999. This was entirely a consequence of the pattern of flows through the food web, since the structure was identical in each case.

Focussing on the top-predators (Figure 12, upper panel), the effects of curtailing discarding were to reduce the omnivory index for each group of animals. The effect was greatest in the 1970-1999 set of models.

Comparing the Ascendency and Capacity indicators for each of the baseline and scenario models (Figure 79, lower panel), it is clear that the greatest effect originates from changes in harvest

ratio, rather than discarding per-se. Reductions in harvest ratio, whether from the 'Improved Selectivity' scenario or systemic between the baseline cases, resulted in higher Ascendency and Capacity in the food web.

Figure 78: Trophic level and omnivory index data derived from the annual integrated food web flow matrices resulting from the stationary state baseline model for 1970-1999 and 2003-2013. Each symbol represents a single living group in the model food web. Phytoplankton and detritus are assigned trophic levels 1 and 0 respectively and are omitted from the diagram. Planktivorous and demersal fish, and top-predator groups are highlighted.

Figure 79: Upper panel: trophic level and omnivory index data for the top-predator groups in the food web, derived from the annual integrated food web flow matrix resulting from the stationary state baseline and scenario models. Lower panel: Ascendency and Capacity network indices derived from the annual integrated food web flow matrices generated from the stationary state baseline and scenario models. In both panels, open symbols refer to the 1970-1999 models, filled symbols refer to the 2003-2013 models.

3.3.3 Discussion

The results obtained here extend those generated from an earlier version of the StrathE2E model (Heath et al. 2014). The general outcome is similar, in that implementing the CFP reform by simply fishing-as-usual but landing all of the catch achieves no significant conservation benefits. Our 'Landing Obligation' scenario was close to 'Land everything' since non-quota demersal species (which were allowed to be discarded in this scenario) were only a small fraction of the catches.

By far the greatest conservation benefits the three discarding scenarios arise from the 'Improved Selectivity' scenario. Here, the effects depend on the intensity of exploitation of the baseline system, in particular on whether the baseline harvest ratio for demersal fish is greater than or less than that generating MSY (HR_{MSY}). The scale of the reaction to 'Improved Selectivity' increases with the baseline harvest ratio. Our 1970-1999 case represents the North Sea under heavy exploitation with demersal harvest ratios well in excess of HR_{MSY} . Conversely, harvest ratios in 2003-2013 were much reduced and less than HR_{MSY} , and the effect of 'Improved Selectivity' was smaller.

Our conclusions are reinforced by the network indicators (Ascendency and Capacity) derived from the model outputs. These indicators measure the pattern and quantity of flows through the food web, and our results clearly show that they are only weakly sensitive to discarding pre-se, and much more sensitive to harvest ratios, whether resulting from differences in effort (1970-1999 vs 2003-2013), or technical measures ('Improved Selectivity').

The effects of discarding patterns on the diet diversity (omnivory index) and trophic levels of the top-predator groups in the model are no so straightforward as the Ascendency/Capacity results. The situation here is complicated by the by-catch mortality effects on these groups generated by the different gear activity rates in 2003-2013 and 1970-1999. Higher exploitation rates and discarding rates in the 1970-1999 baseline model lead to greater omnivory for birds and pinnipeds (seals) but not for cetaceans. Curtailment of discarding results in a decrease in omnivory for birds, but not for pinnipeds. For the latter, the greatest effect on omnivory arises from the 'Improved Selectivity' scenario.

Simply changing discarding practices while fishing as usual, has a negligible conservation benefit at the level of the ecosystem as a whole. On the other hand, tacking the curtailment of discarding by reducing the capture of unwanted fish has the potential to deliver noticeable conservation benefits.

3.3.4 References

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4 Appendices

4.1 Supplementary material for section 3.3.1: Results of fitting the model to survey, landings and discard data

Solid dots show data used in fitting the model. Open dots show the results of ICES assessments where available. Dashed lines show the 95% credible intervals. Vertical lines indicate mean values. For the proportions reaching landing size, green indicates recruits and red discard sized fish.

Figure A. 1. Anglerfish

Figure A. 2. Seabass.

Figure A.3. Brill

Figure A. 4. Common dab

Figure A. 5. Cod

Figure A. 6. Flounder

Figure A. 7. Grey gurnard

Figure A. 8. Other gurnards

Figure A. 9. Haddock

Figure A. 10. Hake

Figure A. 11. Ling

Figure A. 12. Lemon sole

Figure A.13. Megrims. For SSB the reported ICES values (open circles) are on a scale relative to Bmsy. In order to compare trends these values have to rescaled to the same mean value as the model estimated SSB from the current analysis.

Figure A. 14. Mulletts

Figure A. 15. Plaiice

Figure A. 16. Pollack

Figure A. 17. Skates and rays

Figure A. 18. Saithe

Figure A.19. Common sole

Figure A.20. Spurdog

Figure A. 21. Turbot

Figure A. 22. Tusk

Figure A. 23. Whiting

Figure A. 24. Witch

Figure A. 25. Wolffish

4.2 Supplementary material for section 3.3.2

4.2.1 Processing of Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) and Norwegian landings data analysis

STECF make publically available all data from on the landings, discards, effort and economic performance of the fleet sectors of all EU countries (<https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dd/effort>). From 2000 onwards, the landings and effort data are resolved by at least 1 longitude x ½ latitude cells (approximately 30 x 30 nautical miles). Discard data are available only at a more aggregated spatial resolution. The dataset for NW European water includes records on 101 different species covering mostly finfish. Invertebrates are under-represented in the records. We aggregated the species data into the coarse 'functional' categories defined in the StrathE2E model.

The data contain 32 different fishing gear designations. Some of which are local variants appropriate to particular countries or regions. We aggregated the STECF gear types up into 11 coarser groups for use in our further modelling of the implications of enforced changes in fishing patters. The aggregation rules are shown in Table A1.1

Table A1.1 Correspondence between raw STECF gear codes and gear categories in the analyses presented here.

STECF Code	Gear description	StrathE2E model gear type
PELAGIC TRAWLS	Pelagic trawls	Pelagic trawls & seines
PEL_TRAWL	Pelagic Trawl	
PEL_SEINE	Pelagic seine nets	
TR3	Bottom trawls and seines of mesh size equal to or larger than 16 mm and less than 32 mm – mostly targeting sprat.	Sandeel & sprat trawls
OTTER	Bottom trawls (for sandeel)	
LL (landings in a statistical rectangle >50% by weight mackerel)	Drifting longlines (for pelagic fish)	Longline mackerel
BT2	Beam trawls of mesh equal to or larger than 80 mm and less than 120 mm.	Beam trawl demersal
BT1	Beam trawls of mesh equal to or larger than 120 mm	
DEM_SEINE	Danish and Scottish seiners	Demersal seine
TR1	demersal trawls/seines with larger mesh sizes > 100MM	

TR2 (landings in a statistical rectangle <30% by weight Norway lobster)	Demersal trawls and seines with mesh 70-99mm	Demersal otter trawl (mainly TR1)
BOTTOM TRAWLS	Bottom trawls	
3A	Bottom trawler mesh size ≥ 32 mm)	
LL (landings in a statistical rectangle <50% by weight mackerel)	Set longlines (for demersal fish)	Longline & gillnets demersal
GN1	Gill nets, entangling nets.	
GILL	Drift and fixed Nets except Trammel Nets	
3B	Gillnet ≥ 60 mm	
TRAMMEL	Trammel nets	
GT1	Trammel nets	
BEAM	Beam trawl targeting shrimp (in the North Sea)	
TR2 (landings in a statistical rectangle >30% by weight Norway lobster)	Demersal trawls and seines with mesh 70-99mm	Nephrops trawl
POTS	Pots and traps	Creels and pots
DREDGE	Dredges (targeting scallops in the North Sea)	Mollusc dredges

There were some specific considerations involved in the gear aggregations, depending on the species targeted in specific areas.

Beam trawls: The STECF beam trawl categories BT1 and BT2 more or less exclusively target demersal finfish species in the North Sea. It is therefore reasonable to combine BT1 and BT2 into a single model gear. However, care must be taken with the BEAM class. In the North Sea, landings from BEAM gears are more or less exclusively common shrimp (98.7% of the total). Elsewhere, landings from BEAM are more or less exclusively demersal fish. We therefore created a 'Beam trawl shrimp' gear in the North Sea.

TR2 trawls: The TR2 category covers gears used in a variety of fisheries in the North Sea:

A fishery for Nephrops, which has a significant bycatch of demersal fish

Mixed fishery in the southern North Sea, with whiting and other finfish species as the main components

Danish and Swedish fishery targeting demersal finfish in the Skagerrak.

Since the targeted Nephrops fishery operates exclusively in muddy areas and there are particular concerns about the seabed impact of this fishery we sought to disaggregate TR2 to identify the Nephrops trawl component. Country level landings data help us with the disaggregation. If the TR2 landings by an individual country from an individual ICES statistical rectangle comprised more than 30% Nephrops then we assigned that rectangle's TR2 landings and activity to the Nephrops gear. If it was less than 30% we assigned it to the demersal otter trawl category.

Longlines (LL): Longlines are extensively used in drifting, near-surface set model for catching mainly mackerel and tuna, and in a near-seabed set mode for catching e.g. cod and ling. Apart from the very different species targeting of these two modes of operation, there are consequences for by-catch of non-target species. In particular, various seabird species are vulnerable to

A shortcoming of using the STECF data is that it includes data only from EU Member States. So, while effort and landings from EU nation activity in Norwegian and Faroese territorial waters are included, the equivalent data for Norwegian and Faeroese vessels are not. This is a problem for analysis of spatial and national shares of total yields and effort in the North Sea where Norway has a very significant share of the total catch. The Faeroe Islands also have an access agreement with the EU, but their activities in the North Sea are relatively minor. We made a request to the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries, Statistics Department, who kindly provided all the Norwegian annual landings data from the North Sea and west of Scotland regions, resolved by species and 1 longitude x ½ latitude cells for the years 2003-2016.

We processed the Norwegian data to conform with the STECF data, but still we lacked a breakdown of the landings by gear, or any record of the effort expended by Norwegian vessels to compare with the EU effort data. However, given that each of the STECF gears largely targets particular species (e.g. OTTER targets sandeels, TR3 targets sprat, etc), and assuming that the pattern of targeting and the selectivity of the gear types is the same in the EU and Norwegian fishery, we developed a scheme to impute the Norwegian effort, and the distribution of Norwegian landings across gear types for a given year and geographic area (Figure A1.1).

Figure A1.1. Workflow for imputing Norwegian effort per gear type, and the distribution of Norwegian landings across gear types in a given year and geographic area, given the STECF data and the Norwegian landings data obtained from the Directorate of Fisheries. Red cells indicate the data that we have from STECF and the Norwegian Fisheries Directorate, blue cells indicate the data we wish to impute. EU = European Union fleet data, NO = Norwegian fleet data. Estimates of Norwegian effort and landings per gear alone, is simply the imputed total (EU+NO) minus the known EU component.

4.2.2 Catching power (mMN s⁻¹) of each gear with respect to each resource group category in the ecology model.

Values calculated as the ratio of catch rate : activity rate for each gear, for the period 2003-2013. The product of power and activity for each gear is the term regarded as 'effort' in the fishing fleet model, and is considered to be proportional to the harvest ratio.

Gear category	Planktivorous fish	Demersal fish	Migratory fish	Suspension/ deposit feeding benthos	Carnivore/ scavenge feeding benthos	Carnivorous zooplankton	Birds	Seals	Cetaceans
Pelagic trawls & seines	1932.115	0.893477	1077.415	0	0.002671	0	0.175037	0	0.351402
Otter & TR3 (sandeel & sprat trawls)	1013.869	2.121686	38.43438	0.000885	0.76763	0	0	0	0
Longline Mackerel	0.01219	0.049588	7.381184	4.93E-05	0.025221	0	0.085223	0	0
Beam trawl demersal	0.001209	80.89548	0.161385	0.001074	0.389643	0	0	0	0
Demersal Seine	0	10.6404	10.94104	0	0.01525	5.090975	0	0	0
Demersal otter trawl	0.848966	77.63192	9.424984	0.001409	0.699461	1.496856	0	0	0
Longline & gillnets demersal	0.261574	8.664901	0.056018	0.000893	0.069122	0	0.010659	0.749952	1.812262
Beam trawl shrimp	0.247803	5.175162	0.020466	9.52E-06	27.90855	0	0	0	0
Nephrops trawl	0.006521	16.06754	0.164696	0.000232	5.723924	0.13704	0	0	0
Creels & pots	0.00039	0.020078	0.039839	0.001443	1.676333	0	0	0	0.032667
Mollusc dredges	0.123106	0.048141	0.007589	5.800855	0.005832	0	0	0	0
Norwegian whalers	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	127.4624

4.2.3 Parameterisation of by-catch selectivity for top predators

The parameters linking activity density (time spent fishing per km² per year) of each gear-group in the model and the resulting harvest ratio on each top-predator group (proportion of stock biomass caught per year) were established from a thorough survey of literature and national reports, analyses of by-catch and strandings data on birds, seals and cetaceans (e.g. ICES 2018), and results from statistical modelling of line-survey data on seabirds-at-sea and cetacean abundances (pers.comm, Dr James Waggitt & Dr Peter Evans, Bangor University). Data on catches of Minke whales in the Norwegian sector of the North Sea were provided by the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries (Table A3.1).

Table A3.1. Fishing gears for which there are quantitative data on by-catch weights of particular species of top-predators, together with North Sea-wide estimates of total harvest ratio (proportion of vulnerable stock caught per year) during 2003-2013.

Gear	Vulnerable seabird species	Vulnerable seal species	Vulnerable cetacean species	Seabird group harvest ratio	Seal group harvest ratio	Cetacean group harvest ratio
Demersal gillnets	Guillemot, razorbill, fulmar, gannet	Grey seal	Common dolphin, striped dolphin, harbour porpoise	2.58×10^{-5}	4.98×10^{-3}	4.39×10^{-3}
Pelagic trawl	Gannet		Common dolphin, bottlenose dolphin, striped dolphin, pilot whale	1.47×10^{-4}		2.64×10^{-4}
Pelagic seine	Gannet		Common dolphin			3.07×10^{-5}
Pelagic longlines	Fulmar			4.41×10^{-5}		
Creels & pots			Fin whale, Minke whale			3.04×10^{-4}
Norwegian whaler			Minke whale			1.52×10^{-3}

For each combination of gear and by-catch species, we assembled a scatter plot of the activity rate (effort, hours fished per km² per year) by a given gear and national segment of the fleet in a region, and the corresponding species harvest ratio (proportion of biomass captured per year). By aggregating across species, regions and nations, we produced scaling relationships between activity and harvest ratios for each ecological group (seabirds, seals, cetaceans). Examples of these scatterplots are shown in Figures A3.1-A3.3.

Figure A3.1. Scatterplots of the relationship between demersal gillnet effort and the harvest ratio (y^{-1}) on seabird species. For each species, each point represents an individual national assessment of by-catch and effort in a given region.

Figure A3.2. Scatterplots of the relationship between demersal gillnet effort and the harvest ratio (y^{-1}) on seal species. For each species, each point represents an individual national assessment of by-catch and effort in a given region.

Figure A3.3. Scatterplots of the relationship between demersal gillnet effort and the harvest ratio (y^{-1}) on cetacean species. For each species, each point represents an individual national assessment of by-catch and effort in a given region.

4.2.4 Fitting results for the baseline models

Figures A4.1 and A4.2 show, for the two baseline model periods (1980-1999 and 2003-2013) the values and uncertainty ranges for all of the observation-based data to which the models were fitted by optimising either the ecology model parameters, or the scaling parameters between effort and harvest ratio.

For the 1980-1999 model, the harvest ratio for the model groups were known from data analysis (Heath 2012), and the model was fitted by optimising the ecology parameters. For the 2003-2013, the ecology model parameters from the 1970-1999 fitting were assumed, and the fit to the observational data was optimised by fitting the harvest ratios.

Figure A4.1. Best-fit model of the 1970-1999 North Sea ecosystem with the StrathE2E food web model. Each panel shows a different group of measures of the state of the ecosystem. The box and whisker plots show the median and uncertainty (box = quartiles, dashed whiskers = 55 and 95th centiles) of the observed data. The red dash above each box shows the best-fit model results.

Figure A4.2. Best-fit model of the 2003-2013 North Sea ecosystem with the StrathE2E food web model. Each panel shows a different group of measures of the state of the ecosystem. The box and whisker plots show the median and uncertainty (box = quartiles, dashed whiskers = 55 and 95th centiles) of the observed data. The red dash above each box shows the best-fit model results.

4.2.5 Maximum likelihood preference parameters for all resource-consumer links in the model, estimated using the penalised likelihood simulated annealing scheme. Preferences for each consumer guild (columns) sum to 1.0

Resources	ID	Consumers															
		8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
Water column ammonia (shallow layer)	1	0.271	0.271														
Water column nitrate (shallow layer)	2	0.729	0.729														
Suspended detritus (shallow & deep layers)	3			0.001							0.976	0.311	0.294				
Labile sediment detritus (3 shallow & 3 deep habitat classes)	4												0.478				
Macrophyte debris	5													0.007			
Corpses (3 shallow & 3 deep habitat classes)	6									0.010				0.419	0.100	0.057	
Fishery discards	7									0.097					0.220	0.065	0.119
Macrophytes	8													0.013			
Phytoplankton (shallow & deep layers)	9			0.906								0.024	0.689	0.227			
Omnivorous zooplankton	10				0.653	0.147	0.947	0.362	0.366								0.010
Carnivorous zooplankton	11							0.152	0.014	0.075					0.100	0.000	0.020
Pelagic fish larvae	12				0.017			0.128	0.050	0.116							
Demersal fish larvae	13				0.041			0.178	0.058	0.110							
Pelagic fish adults	14									0.106					0.200	0.184	0.292
Migratory fish	15									0.018					0.180	0.052	0.392
Demersal fish adults	16									0.006					0.200	0.641	0.162
Suspension/deposit feeding benthos larva	17			0.002	0.192	0.589	0.043	0.088	0.286								
Carnivorous/scavenging feeding benthos larvae	18			0.092	0.096	0.264	0.010	0.092	0.226								

4.3 Technical specifications for changes in the EwE algorithm